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SPECIFIC METHODS APPLIED IN CONDUCTING FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS IN REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article covers issues related to conducting functional analysis, which aims to derive given trends and processes in regional development. The aim of the article is to characterize the main elements selected platform supporting the implementation of professional functional solutions in regional development and the experience of evaluation a its development. The approach requires in the field of regional development to approach in an integrated way or with a variety of methods of space and territory assessment. Thus, the model of functionality and usability is imposed in regional development. The stated objective is used to implement the method of analysis and critique of the literature on the subject, the method of observation and individual case methods. The main result of the work done is a detailed presentation of the chosen platform to create a detailing of the results of functional processes in regional development.

KEY WORDS: regional development, functional analysis, region, planning, productivity, settlements

ABSTRAKT

Dieser Artikel behandelt Fragen im Zusammenhang mit der Durchführung von Funktionsanalysen, die darauf abzielen, bestimmte Trends und Prozesse in der regionalen Entwicklung abzuleiten. Das Ziel des Artikels ist es, die wichtigsten Elemente ausgewählt Plattform zur Unterstützung der Umsetzung der professionellen funktionalen Lösungen in der regionalen Entwicklung und die Erfahrung der Bewertung einer ihrer Entwicklung zu charakterisieren. Der Ansatz erfordert im Bereich der regionalen Entwicklung, um in einer integrierten Art und Weise oder mit einer Vielzahl von Methoden der Raum und Territorium Bewertung Ansatz. So wird das Modell der Funktionalität und Nutzbarkeit in der Regionalentwicklung durchgesetzt. Das erklärte Ziel wird verwendet, um die Methode der Analyse und Kritik der Literatur zu diesem Thema, die Methode der Beobachtung und Einzelfallmethoden umzusetzen. Das Hauptergebnis der Arbeit ist eine detaillierte Darstellung der gewählten Plattform, um eine Detaillierung der Ergebnisse der funktionalen Prozesse in der Regionalentwicklung zu erstellen.

STICHWORTE: Regionalentwicklung, Funktionsanalyse, Region, Planung, Produktivität, Siedlungen

RÉSUMÉ

Cet article couvre les questions liées à la conduite de l'analyse fonctionnelle, qui vise à dériver des tendances et des processus donnés dans le développement régional. L'objectif de l'article est de caractériser les principaux éléments de la plate-forme sélectionnée pour soutenir la mise en œuvre de solutions fonctionnelles professionnelles dans le développement régional et l'expérience de l'évaluation de son développement. L'approche nécessite dans le domaine du développement régional d'aborder de manière intégrée ou avec une variété de méthodes d'évaluation de l'espace et du

territoire. Ainsi, le modèle de fonctionnalité et d'utilisabilité s'impose dans le développement régional. L'objectif énoncé est utilisé pour mettre en œuvre la méthode d'analyse et de critique de la littérature sur le sujet, la méthode d'observation et les méthodes de cas individuels. Le résultat principal du travail effectué est une présentation détaillée de la plateforme choisie pour créer un détail des résultats des processus fonctionnels dans le développement régional.

MOTS CLÉS: développement régional, analyse fonctionnelle, région, planification, productivité, établissements humains.

INTRODUCTION

Various attempts to answer the question of what the emergence of knowledge-based regional development means for the functional nature of the spatial development of human settlements are found in the research conducted. It is emphasized that in the short run regional development depends on factors such as the structure of the economy, sectoral specialization, the quality and distribution of infrastructure, and other factors affecting the efficiency of a country or region. In the long run, it depends on the ability to sustain change in the factors that drive productivity growth (technology, human resources, research spending and the structure of the economy and how policy tries to shape it). Investment in human and physical capital, labour productivity, enterprise innovation, the institutional environment and social capital are as important as institutional and organisational change. The scope of the regional economy's impact, in addition to its functionality, rests on knowledge and includes that part of the economy that develops under the influence of science, which can mean both new sectors of the economy focused on high-tech production and traditional industries introducing innovation into their activities (Higgins, 2017). The public sector and regional businesses are at the core of the concept, where they play a key role (Tsonkov, 2023). In order to clarify specific methods that are applied when conducting functional analysis in regional development, it is necessary to assess and analyze the regional economy. In this part, we set ourselves the task of highlighting the problems of regional development through the prism of territorial governance (Tsonkov, 2022, 2021). Finding solutions for local development is essential for territorial development. The development of the knowledge-based economy is largely determined by the tendency of companies to innovate and acquire knowledge for their purposes from external sources. Thus, the functional analysis shows us the state of the environment and its location in relation to other postulates and features of development (Ignatyeva, Mariev, 2013, Torre, Wallet, 2016). Quantitative impact assessments should be abandoned. They should be done whenever possible, as the assessment is more objective and together with qualitative assessments represent tools to document risk. The current level of economies such as Bulgaria's and its integration into global economic life means that sudden changes, economic downturns and crises taking place not only in the immediate vicinity of Bulgaria but also in other regions of the world can have a negative impact on the stability of the Polish economy and, consequently, on the security of the country. The economic crisis of recent years has had a significant impact on the global security situation, slowing or eliminating the economic growth of a large group of countries, including Bulgaria's close partners and allies.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Exhibition. The shift of the centre of the global balance of power from the Euro-Atlantic region to the Asia-Pacific region will be accompanied by a gradual evolution of the importance and opportunities for global influence of China, India, Brazil and other emerging powers. "Western" countries still lead in many areas, but the authoritarian model is becoming a viable alternative to Western universalism in the eyes of some countries and their leaders, which means that they are being

used to exert political pressure and increasingly substitute military force to achieve state objectives. At the same time, the EU countries need changes after the military clash between Ukraine and Russia. The tensions caused by temporary restrictions on gas supplies to some countries show the weakness of the energy market and the negative impact of politics on the economy. The depletion of rare metal resources could also become an important and dynamic challenge. Potential threats remain: the growing number of failed and failed states, tensions and conflicts in areas of reduced stability in or near the Euro-Atlantic area, terrorism, and international organised crime, negative phenomena in cyberspace and crisis situations resulting from natural or man-made disasters.

Thus, countries such as Bulgaria need to bring analytical tools to the forefront that will allow the state government and private business to find a better way to develop and manage the territory (Torre, Wallet, 2016). The scientific approach of planning has the position of a mandatory principle for all levels and activities in spatial planning, which is justified by the scale of studies, the scope of the issues, changes in socio-economic and regional development. It supports decision-making by arguing for conceptual solutions that have a scientific basis and knowledge of global practice. Public interests protected as a priority - they ensure the balance with individual interests in the implementation of the ideas and priorities of the national spatial policy. Here, priority is given to areas of national and supranational importance in order to regulate and guarantee the protection of resources related to the development of leading sectors and the implementation of sites of importance for technical and transport infrastructure. The conservation and adequate use of important cultural and natural assets shall be used as a stimulant for development. Publicity, transparency, partnership and citizen participation in the decision-making process - these are the guiding principles in the process of elaboration of the NCPD, in all stages of the collection, processing and updating of information. Continuity, coherence and continuity of the planning process - these support the adequate use of experience gained over the years in the development of important documents for the whole country. These include both the 1976 Unified Spatial Plan of the country and the 2012-2022 National Strategy for Regional Development. Through these principles, the strategic objectives and priorities set are coordinated with documents of a higher hierarchical level, to further develop the priorities related to the main elements of the spatial structure - poles and axes of development, agglomeration areas and their interconnection in the national space. Concentration, which is thematic, financial, geographic, resource and temporal, offers more appropriate behaviour in the use of limited resources where they are most needed or where they will have the greatest impact. This 19th principle also includes efficiency and effectiveness in the use of scarce resources and responds to the new emphasis in cohesion policy through the poles and axes of growth, territories and intervention areas identified in the NSRF that have the greatest national and regional relevance.

The management of regional development is one of the most important activities of the state, aimed at ensuring its existence and development in the changing conditions of the security environment the division of executive power adopted in the Constitution of the Republic of Bulgaria can potentially pose challenges to the effective management of regional development (Tzonkov, 2023, Petrov, 2020). Competence issues and related difficulties in the management of regional development may arise from the interdependence of constitutional prerogatives for the effective cooperation of executive authorities, which is a necessary condition for the introduction of interdisciplinary, encompassing crisis management regulated by separate provisions and the management of regional governance. In this part, the state does not have a legal framework that combines activities undertaken by the public authority as a coherent system of national security management.

This introduces the possibility of risk analysis in regional development. It can be explored as an available risk identification procedure, whether it involves a dual assessment of identified risks on their likelihood of occurrence and the extent of their impact on regional development policy implementation and their impact on local business and infrastructure development. It should be stressed here that risks identified as important are subject to two types of action with corresponding measures. They are in the direction of preventive action: these measures are designed to prevent the event that constitutes the risk from occurring. The other group are 'remedial' (or corrective) actions: these are measures that prepare on the assumption that the event posing the risk will still occur. It is examined whether the risks associated with the resources have been analysed. These cover random events that would result in a shortage of the necessary quantity or quality of resources to perform a function, provide a service or exercise control. Processes refer to random events that may occur during the execution of the process and that would circumvent the process. Performance includes random events that, if they occurred, would disrupt the actual delivery of the service or performance of the function - on availability, availability (sufficient volume) or quality. Impacts cover accidental events whose occurrence would undermine the objectives, regardless of the correct implementation. The extent to which the identified risks are systematised into the following groups is reviewed. The first relates to strategic risk: a strategic objective is affected, and the second relates to systemic risk, where the risk that affects one (or more) strategic objectives to such an extent that it has a material impact on the mission, vision and values. It examines whether the systemic risks are linked to plans or the specific management plan and whether procedures are in place to review and update the plan. This method has corresponding advantages and disadvantages. The advantages of the method track what risk analysis and risk management procedures have been implemented. It also provides a baseline approach for risk assessment if it is found that one has not been implemented. The disadvantages of the method are that it does not actually go through risk analysis and assessment. The external environment analysis describes the influence of external factors on the organisation, the development trends over the next few years and describes activities/examples resulting from this influence (factors), the so-called PEST (LE) analysis, which is based on political factors. These have implications for the regulatory framework of the institution. These are factors that help or hinder the institution to meet government priorities and government agenda force the institution to review and make appropriate amendments to strategic plans. Economic factors follow. These reflect the development of the country's economy (of the area or sector concerned). Social factors follow. These reflect changes in demographics and values, lifestyles and the like that are characteristic of a particular stage of society's development, as well as environmental and cultural factors. We move on to technological factors. These are relevant in assessing the impact on the area which is the subject of regulation by the institution, in relation to new technologies, information flows, management organisation and interinstitutional relations. Environmental factors are also assessed. Factors such as climate, environmental and ethical issues, pollution, waste, recycling can have a direct impact on the planning of future activities and must be taken into account when drawing up the action plan. Finally, legislative factors are also assessed. Regulations, standards, legislation. The analysis also includes an analysis of the direct environment for the organisation and examines which factors are directly related to the orientation of the organisation and can have a strong influence. Sometimes this part of the analysis is called micro analysis. The analysis is structured, and it is advisable to use a checklist of possible elements to the most important factors, trends to be analyzed. The checklist can remain the same for a long time and for this it is a working aid. A weakness of the PESTLE method is that it takes into account

external influences on policy. In order to account for internal influences on policy implementation, it is necessary to analyse internal factors as well.

The analysis should cover their status and consider the impact on policy development, the system and the administrative structure. Advantages and disadvantages of the method are that it gives the big picture of the environment and impact factors; It clarifies the relationships between factors and outlines strategic perspectives. Disadvantages of the method are that it is too general and difficult to capture specifics, requires heterogeneous knowledge and is time consuming. The choice of method or combination of methods for analysis is a professional judgement of the team. The appropriate methods depend on the specific needs to achieve a more in-depth and detailed analysis - desk research or on-site familiarisation with specific documents and/or activities, obtaining information on a given issue through the provision of questionnaires and surveys, conducting interviews, observations in the work environment, etc. Cost-benefit analysis is the preferred tool for cost-benefit analysis when the functional analysis is focused on regulatory policy. Essentially, it is an impact assessment tool and can only be applied in a functional policy analysis if it is explicitly stated in the scope of the analysis and the necessary resources are provided for it.

The programming process and the spatial development model in Bulgaria. For good risk management at all management levels, heads of departments at the first management level designate risk officers. They identify and collect the risks related to the objectives and/or activities undertaken by the head of department and oversee the process of implementing risk management.

In this direction, risk management in Bulgaria is entrusted to the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works through the adoption of the National Concept for Spatial Development. Bulgaria has managed to climb another step on its way to sustainable urban and regional development and risk management with the assumption of risk management. A project long awaited, but also long delayed, the NSRF builds on and further develops what was proposed in the 2012-2022 NSRF, indicating the pathways to move to a higher level. The assessment of the urban centres, arranged in 6 hierarchical levels, has been carried out through indicators of demographic dynamics and their importance as administrative, transport, health, educational, cultural, and economic and tourist centres. Now that most of the 2021-2027 programming period has passed and a significant number of urban areas have received development grants, it is now the turn of smaller settlements to benefit from EU funds. The development of a specific policy to stabilise the network of small towns will 'bring them together' in a 4th hierarchical level. The direction of development of peripheral rural and mountainous areas will largely depend on them. The national concept does not neglect the towns and villages of the 5th hierarchical level, which have the potential to be further developed so that they too can benefit from financial support from the European Union (Georgieva, 2024, 2023). This is where the role of Integrated Urban Development and Regeneration Plans comes in. Improving the quality of life in cities, which is the focus of Union policies, should be achieved by implementing the projects set out in the IDP and by creating the conditions for balanced urban development outside the regulatory boundaries in up-to-date general spatial plans (GSPs), which for large cities and agglomerations should be developed with their area of active influence.

The National Spatial Development Concept aims to counter internal migration and depopulation of settlements. The main focus is on equitable access to essential goods and services. After technical and transport infrastructure, the subsystems of health and education are placed first in business location and choice of place to live. The indicators for the facilities of the system are also very important for the lower levels of the hierarchical system, because the demographic balance and the retention of the working population depend on the availability of adequate educational facilities. The

Concept is the most important long-term strategic document that should harmonise sectoral policies, coordinate private and public interests in restored land and forest ownership in all its forms, an increased number of actors in the planning and management process and a more democratic decision-making process. The concept should be functionally linked to the digitalization and digital development of Bulgarian territories, using best practices from other European countries (Korchagina, Sychjova-Peredero, Korchagin, 2019; Popelo, Garafonova, Tulchynska, Derhaliuk, Berezovskyi, 2021).

The NSRF integrates and guides sectoral policies for horizontal and vertical integration at several levels - community, national and regional. Integrated planning also applies to areas with specific characteristics, such as the Black Sea and Danube coasts. There, the principle of integrated spatial planning and management is applied. Through the National Spatial Development Concept, different approaches are applied in Integrated Urban Regeneration and Development Plans.

The cities of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd hierarchical levels form the main support network of urban centres in the national territory. The economic importance of these cities is reflected in the fact that they account for the bulk of the gross domestic product and economic growth. They play a major role in the provision of high-level public services. They are home to the country's universities and the main centres of science and innovation. The main network of high-value health facilities is developed in these cities. They are important centres of culture. They are all included as planning sites through the PIRP, on the basis of which resources and efforts for integrated urban development will be coordinated and directed over the next plan period and quality of life improved. Essential for the implementation of this development are the General Spatial Plans (GSPs) of these cities as the territorial basis for guiding all investment initiatives and actions. A small number of these cities have up-to-date Master Plans approved or in the process of approval. For the rest, the requirements of the Law on Amendment and Supplementation of the Law on Spatial Planning will apply. For the 4th hierarchical level, small towns of micro-regional importance in the territory of groups of municipalities, the NSRF foresees 90 small towns. These towns play a crucial role for peripheral rural and mountainous areas, offering jobs and basic public services to more than one municipality. Criteria for the selection of these towns are: suitable location in the territory of the districts, demographic size, social, education, health and culture.

Functional analysis of European instruments in regional development. Risk management involves identifying and assessing risks, identifying and establishing a risk response to reduce the opportunity to protect against the risk, and mitigating the consequences arising from the materialisation of risks. Thus, with the National Spatial Development Concept 2013 - 2025, the Integrated Municipal Development Plans (IMDPs) and the Operational Programme Regions in Growth 2021-2027 (OPGR) also play an important role in development. The risk identification process always takes into account the objectives and the activities that contribute to their achievement. In order to properly identify risks, it is absolutely necessary to have a document that contains the objectives adopted at enterprise level. This can be a management plan, an institutional strategic plan or any other document that includes: general objectives, specific objectives, activities that contribute to achieving the objectives. Thus, the National Spatial Development Concept (NSCD) proposes a set of cities suitable for support according to an elaborated spatial model of the national territory. Moreover, the functional nature of the operational programme for regional development is brought out as an instrument for "integrated urban development" through the preparation of Integrated and Urban Development Plans (IUDP). The proposal includes all 35 cities of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd hierarchical levels as major urban poles of growth and development. It is essential to support some of the smaller cities at the 4th hierarchical level which are important for the development of peripheral, rural and border

areas. At this level, the ODA interacts with the RDP, which supports the majority of Level 4 cities. It is essential at this city-centre level that there is good differentiation between the two programmes to achieve the desired impact in a resource constrained environment. In this respect, taking into account the possibilities of the ODA for the period 2021-2027, the NCPF considers that 32 pcs of Level 4 cities, identified through the application of certain reasoning and the adopted selection criteria, are suitable for ODA support. The main motivations relate to the need to stimulate a sufficiently large number of medium and small towns located in peripheral rural, mountainous and border areas. These towns are centres offering jobs and basic services of importance to more than one municipality and good communication and transport links with them will be essential in the future. The criteria for selection are a suitable location within the territory of the districts and good transport accessibility, demographic size, available functions of municipal importance in the economic, social, health, educational, cultural spheres. The choice of cities to support integrated urban development so that it is located on a major or minor axis of development, To play an important role as a balancer in the development of the district in addition to the regional center (example: the city of Dupnitsa versus the city of Kyustendil), To be located in a peripheral territory to make important links with neighboring territories and settlements, including outside the country. To be a service centre of more than one municipality (example: the city of Pernik versus the towns of Radomir and Batanovtsi). The National Spatial Development Concept for the period 2013-2025 (NSDC) in its updated version of 2020 focuses on the context of the main documents of the European Union for sustainable spatial and urban development. It provides the guidelines for the balanced spatial planning, smart management and integrated conservation of the country's resources in line with the Europe 2020 Strategy's objectives of developing a competitive economy based on knowledge and innovation, reducing resource dependence and energy consumption, economic, social and territorial cohesion. Directly linked to the development of national space is the improvement of infrastructure to ensure better connectivity with Europe, with centres of growth, innovation, science, business and culture. Priorities for improving the quality of education and diversifying forms of access to education will increase the competitiveness of the younger generation and are reflected in the spatial polycentric model, in urban development policies and in linking them to adjacent rural areas. The creation of a better business environment in the country and in the EU and increased trust in institutions will be reflected through administrative and institutional capacity and appropriately reformed legislation in the implementation of the spatial, social and economic development proposals. The NSRF adopts the approach to rural and cross-border areas of the European Union's Territorial Agenda (TA 2020), which adds to polycentric spatial and integrated urban development the concern to preserve the vitality of small settlements. This differentiated approach is used in the proposals to target support to small towns and larger villages in rural and border areas and to build on the disconnected links with them, while taking into account the specificities of different rural and mountain areas and the access to services offered by medium-sized towns. Europe 2020 proposes three mutually reinforcing priorities for smart growth: building a knowledge-based economy and innovation. So too the quest for sustainable growth: promoting a greener and more competitive economy with a more efficient use of resources. As well as inclusive growth to stimulate an economy with high levels of employment, leading to social and territorial cohesion.

CONCLUSION

Risk exposure is a probabilistic concept directly related to the likelihood of risk materializing. It only has meaning before the risk occurs. Risk exposure works with an implicit hierarchy of identified risks. Risk exposure is a combination of probability and impact, as it is a two-dimensional indicator of

matrix type. This can be represented in several forms, depending on the model adopted to assess the probability and impact of risk materialization especially in regional development. It is necessary to provide an information framework to make the risk management process known to all staff by creating a section on the entity's intranet where experiences are learned and solutions are translated. In addition, regional development is inherently functional in nature and often integral approaches are needed to take advantage of to achieve quality regional development management. On the other hand, a functional analysis of risk management in regional development must distinguish between inherent risk and residual risk. Inherent risk is the specific risk associated with achieving the objective without risk management measures having been taken, while residual risk is that risk which remains after the risk response has been established and implemented. Residual risk is an expression of the fact that inherent risks cannot be fully controlled. No matter how many measures are taken, uncertainty cannot be eliminated. Risk tolerance represents the amount of risk that a public organisation is prepared to bear or expose itself to at a given time in situations where risk may be an opportunity or a threat to the management of regional development processes. An effective risk management process at the level of the public entity must also take into account the priorities of the coordinated or subordinate institutions that contribute to the achievement of the objectives of the public entity concerned in order to consolidate and develop risk. In the governance process, it is recommended that public entities communicate when sharing best practices in the field, especially if the public entity has subordinated other institutions.

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ANALYSIS AND ASSESSMENT OF RETAIL PARKS' IMPACT ON REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with topics in the field of regional development, or more specifically, topics related to the expansion of the retail network and how this positively affects a region. Several ways in which this can be done are shown, with one possible approach to regional development being through the rational management, development, and optimization of the retail network, which can have a highly positive and beneficial effect on regional development. Modern tools for locating retail outlets and their impact on individual territories are discussed in this regard. In this direction, examples are taken from large retail chains such as Bila, Kaufland, Lidl, etc., and it is shown what added value they have for the regional development of the territories in Bulgaria.

KEY WORDS: Regional development, retail, localization, optimization, expansion, retail parks

ABSTRAKT

Der Artikel befasst sich mit Themen im Bereich der Regionalentwicklung, genauer gesagt mit Themen im Zusammenhang mit der Ausweitung des Einzelhandelsnetzes und wie sich dies positiv auf eine Region auswirkt. Es werden mehrere Möglichkeiten aufgezeigt, wie dies geschehen kann. Ein möglicher Ansatz für die regionale Entwicklung ist die rationelle Verwaltung, Entwicklung und Optimierung des Einzelhandelsnetzes, die sich sehr positiv und förderlich auf die regionale Entwicklung auswirken kann. In diesem Zusammenhang werden moderne Instrumente zur Ansiedlung von Einzelhandelsgeschäften und ihre Auswirkungen auf die einzelnen Gebiete erörtert. In dieser Richtung werden Beispiele von großen Einzelhandelsketten wie Bila, Kaufland, Lidl usw. herangezogen, und es wird gezeigt, welchen Mehrwert sie für die regionale Entwicklung der Gebiete in Bulgarien haben.

STICHWORTE: Regionalentwicklung, Einzelhandel, Lokalisierung, Optimierung, Expansion, Fachmarktzentren

RÉSUMÉ

L'article traite de sujets dans le domaine du développement régional, ou plus précisément de sujets liés à l'expansion du réseau de vente au détail et à la manière dont cela affecte positivement une région. L'une des approches possibles du développement régional est la gestion rationnelle, le développement et l'optimisation du réseau de vente au détail, qui peut avoir un effet très positif et bénéfique sur le développement régional. À cet égard, les outils modernes de localisation des points de vente et leur impact sur les territoires individuels sont examinés. Dans cette optique, des exemples de grandes chaînes de distribution telles que Bila, Kaufland, Lidl, etc. sont pris en compte et la valeur ajoutée qu'elles apportent au développement régional des territoires bulgares est démontrée.

MOTS CLÉS: Développement régional, commerce de détail, localisation, optimisation, expansion, parcs d'activités commerciales

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, we have witnessed processes of different natures and scopes in the social, economic, environmental, demographic, financial, informational, public, and military spheres. These processes are changing the economic systems of countries and, at the same time, setting a new course for the development of individual regions both supranational and regionally within individual countries. As a result of these processes, countries and their regions are being transformed - digitalized, and greened, introducing a circular economy and systems for the rational management of natural resources. In this context, regions (especially at the national level) are becoming particularly important. That is why their development is the subject of both scientific and public interest in terms of their rational and efficient management, including attracting more investment. One of the major investors in recent years has been the country's international retail chains, which contribute to higher employment in an area, as well as to its improvement, by investing in the improvement of infrastructure and providing easy, fast, and convenient access to modern commerce.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research methodology. In this article, the author provides an analysis and overview of the development of retail parks in Bulgaria. The present issue is multidisciplinary and contemporary given the fact that retail outlets interact with different regions. Therefore, the main objective is to characterize the relationship of retail parks with regional development by analyzing the state of the major retail chains in Bulgaria. For the needs of the study, the author uses territorial and systemic approaches, which are complemented by retrospective analysis, systemic, analytical, inductive, and deductive methods, as well as causality analysis. The author goes through several stages of research. At the beginning, a brief analysis of the specialized literature in the field of regional development retail research, and retail parks. On this basis, the author examines the state of retail in Bulgaria, and the development of large retail chains, and their contribution to regional development in the country. Finally, some generalizations are made regarding the development of retail parks in the country and what is their future added value for regional development. The author assumes the following research thesis, which attempts to confirm that the development of retail parks in Bulgaria stimulates the economic and regional development of the country.

Literature Review. The works that relate to regional development are related to theories of many scientists, as well as works that are relevant today and answer some of the questions related to the development of a region and the correct assessment of the location of logistics, raw materials, and the market, also help in the calculation of transport costs, which are an important part for companies and households. One such book is *Regional Economics* by Roberta Capello, which aims to provide an authoritative and up-to-date treatment of the evolution of key theoretical developments of the last 10 years (Capello, 2015). Topics covered range from the earliest theories of location to the latest theories of regional growth. Together with the contemporary debate on development strategies developed by the EU to design new convergence policies, this book provides a comprehensive guide to the subject. Key elements included in the new edition include theories of proximity and innovation; the concept of territorial capital; and the debate on the role of agglomeration economies in urban growth. The book also examines some of the earliest theories of agglomerations and locations, Alfred Weber's model of localization and transport costs, and Edgar Hoover's model. Other theories of regional growth, such as territorial competitiveness, are also discussed. Cappello's study explains location and physico-metric space. It describes the first and earliest group of theories in regional economics, which falls under the heading of "location theory". This group adopts a purely geographical concept of continuous physico-

metric space, which can be defined in terms of physical distance and transportation costs. This interprets the patterns of price and cost variations in space and their implications in terms of location choice and market partitioning between firms. This was the concept of space used by the great geographers of the first half of the twentieth century. An important place in the research that Cappello does is related to the description of location theory. The author seeks to explain the distribution of activities in space, the aim being to identify the factors that influence the location of different activities, the distribution of different parts of the territory between different types of production, the division of the spatial market between producers and the functional distribution of activities in space. An important study in the Bulgarian scientific literature is by Lyudmil Georgiev, who deals with the issue of regional economics (Georgiev, 2012). In his book "Regional Economy" the author analyses the main questions that the regional economy answers, namely "What is where?" "Why is it there?", "What does it serve?". He also describes methods to quantify location impacts. The author defines what a good location is and how it is located. According to him, a good location ensures the maximum profit and full return on invested capital. Georgiev contributes to improving the location process by proposing a methodology for determining location impacts. In doing so, he provides clarity on the construction of the locational factors evaluation mechanism. Related to localization approaches is the work of Stanka Tonkova, who analyzes localization choices in detail (Tonkova, 2006). An analysis of localization processes is provided in the book Regulatory Models for Territorial Development (Tonkov, 2022). The author presents his vision of the possible toolkit for regulating socio-economic processes and economic activity in regions to achieve territorial development.

We find not a few studies in the specialized periodicals. For example, the article related to the expansion of foreign chains in Bulgaria is interesting (Stoyanov, 2012). Another article related to expansion and how it could affect and improve the region is "The Expansion of Foreign Retail Chains at Regional and National Level and the Prospects for the Development of Our Domestic Retail Market" (Yolov, 2017). The municipality has an important role in attracting retail outlets and locating retail parks. Its role is related to the favorable business environment formation and assessment (Tsonkov, 2023). Here the author aims to assess the performance of Bulgarian municipalities, which is the key to creating good living conditions and a favorable business ecosystem for investment attractiveness. Logically, for the good performance of Bulgarian municipalities, the results of effective regional policy are important (Petrov, 2024). The focus of the study is the need for a working regional policy that gives importance to rural development and influences demographic and socio-economic processes in Bulgaria. Several studies can be found that present good practices in other countries. One of them focuses research interest on the development of retail chains and their contribution to the region (Johansson, Jonasson, Reim, 2023). In other studies, we can find an analysis of the current state of the market, comparing it to past years and forecasting the future development of international and domestic retail chains, as well as which regions of the country would be interested in expanding. In this case, the example of Colliers, which has been a leading international property consultancy for about 30 years, can be given. It is also one of the leading companies in this sector in Bulgaria, so we can consider its reports as one of the most objective when it comes to the property market and its development in the country.

Birth of regional development as a science. Problems of regional development have preoccupied scientific thought since antiquity. Ancient Greek encyclopedic thinkers generated ideas that had regional overtones and became the basis for the further research pursuits of scientists over the centuries. The modern theory of regional issues, mainly in its economic direction, began to take shape after the 16th century, when challenges of an objective nature - the development of major

industrial centers, the Great Geographical Discoveries - placed demands on theory to formulate views on the territorial division of labor and the direction of economic geography. In the 19th and 20th centuries, as a result of the dynamic development of scientific thought, specific directions and scientific schools in regional issues were formed, which are still relevant today. The scientific works of Kristaller, Loesch, Weber, Bunge, Eisard, the Alexandrov-Baransky school, Kolosovsky, and many others are world-renowned (Dokova, Petrov, 2008).

From a contemporary point of view, the problems of regional development are associated with the evolving processes of globalization, the scientific and technological revolution, and the boom of information and communication technologies. A special contribution to the development of the global view of regional development was made by M. Geneshki, who substantiates the need to apply a regional approach to solve contemporary global problems (Geneshki, 2002). Diverse human work and life activity takes place in space and time. However, it is characteristic of the Earth's space that it is limited and in the context of modern global development is constantly "shortening" The reasons for this are mainly related to the trends of accelerated economic and demographic development, which significantly increases the pressure on natural systems and resources. Humanity's progressive forward movement requires the limited space of the earth, on the one hand, to be a territorial base for ever-expanding settlement structures and modern forms of urbanization, a source of resources for aggressive human activity, and, on the other hand, to absorb the waste from this same economic and living activity. The development of mankind and the world economy as a whole is many times outstripping the capabilities of the earth. The threshold of sustainable extraction from the natural system has long been crossed, as the world-renowned scientist L. Brown. According to him, unless the approach of space utilization and the philosophy of development is changed, consumption can only grow by consuming the resource base itself, which is extremely limited (Brown, 1989).

And while the earth's space is being 'shortened', being subject to complex global processes of various kinds (socio-economic, demographic, natural resource, environmental, etc.), the development of present and future generations faces another threat - the growth of regional contrasts. The regional projections of the outlined global problems are shaping a variety of problems of relations between natural and social systems, which have specific dynamics and manifestations. All this necessitates the study of the earth's space with a view to its most rational regulation and use in perspective in combining globalism with a regional approach.

The development of modern trade as a way to support regional development. The internationalization of retail is an objective, dynamic, and evolving process, covering more and more markets and regions. This paper examines the complex process and the extent to which it is manifested in the Bulgarian market. It outlines the different ways used by large retailers (retailers) to enter international markets, highlighting the most applied - organic expansion, another type of expansion is through the appropriation or takeover of entire retail chains. The paper traces the development of the process of retail internationalization in Bulgaria and its impact on the concentration of retail activity.

As an example of an active expansion of an international chain, the development of the expansion in the retail chain Billa Bulgaria is taken into account for the specific analysis. Both over the years and to date, it is the earliest chain in the country and has the largest number of outlets at this time.

BILLA Bulgaria was the first international supermarket chain to enter the Bulgarian market in 2000. Currently, the chain has 160 stores in 50 cities in the country. The company continues to develop its supermarket network and to provide its customers with quality and fresh meat, bread, fruit and

vegetables, delicatessen, and everything they need for everyday shopping at good prices that suit the individual capabilities of each customer. As an added value related to regional development and national development, it can be noted that Billa successfully partners with over 40 Bulgarian producers - supplying a wide variety of seasonal fruits and vegetables from over 180 vegetable gardens, greenhouses, and vineyards throughout Bulgaria. The food chain has also provided over 5,000 jobs in the country. In addition, it is worth mentioning that both Billa and other food and non-food chains have provided the local population with quick and easy access to all kinds of food and household products. The same can be said for not a few Bulgarian food chains, in particular, the Fantastico food chain can be distinguished as the largest Bulgarian food chain in the country, which has 95% representation in Sofia and the region.

The retail park as a new form of modern trade development. If we look more specifically at an area and the added value a food chain can bring, as in this case we are looking at Billa, we can look at a few examples. In the last 2/3 years, retail park-type outlets have entered Bulgaria at a serious pace. A retail park is a collection of several retail outlets at ground level with a large car park for customers, with quick and easy access, and the parks can be integrated into the city, next to it, or outside it. Billa was the first chain in the country to propose this idea to local investors and with the help of this it opened the first retail parks in the country. This expansion of retail parks was subsequently supported by the entry of new non-food retail chains in the country, as malls and high streets were already occupied and an alternative option had to be found for the expansion of new players in the market. Currently, Billa is and continues to be the most represented retail chain in the country's retail parks.

As a concrete example of the analysis one can consider "Retail Park Srednogorie/Pirdop". Srednogorie is an area that is an hour's drive from Sofia and there is no other major city nearby. The population of the area is mainly formed by the inhabitants of Chelopech, Pirdop, and Zlatitsa and is about 15 000 people. In addition, it can be said that companies such as Dundee Precious Metals, Aurubis, and Asarel Medet contribute to the added value of the area, providing jobs and good wages for the population in the area. The Billa store can contribute to the area's development by providing at least 30-40 jobs and offering the local population easy and convenient access to a wide range of food products. Apart from that, when a developer decides to build such a large retail project, the first and most important thing for him is to provide a "food court" or food chain, because people need food most often or daily and these will be the customers who will visit the retail park most often. It is therefore important that the food chain is well represented in the market, and that it is a recognizable brand to attract as many customers as possible. With a lease already signed with a food chain and the idea of building more retail units with a large car park with easy and convenient access for customers, the next tenants will be more interested in taking part in such a project which in itself will also contribute to the attractiveness of the location by attracting customers with other needs such as fashion stores, building materials, furniture stores, pharmacies and offices of banks or telecommunications operators in the country. All of these retailers, in addition to providing a convenient and easy way of shopping close to their homes, offer a variety of different goods or services or put another way, bring the conveniences of a big city to less populated, less commercial, and even underdeveloped areas. Moreover, a project such as a retail park becomes a major employer for the area, thus providing satisfaction to both the investor and the local population. From my experience in this field over the years, I can confirm that whenever such a project has been built in smaller population areas, there has always been a positive attitude, starting from the ordinary resident to the mayor of the locality, everyone has welcomed such an investment and support has been received. This is proof

that such projects have a future in small population centers with a population of around 5,000. Such a project would add a lot of value to an area in the country, but it requires a suitable location, an investor who is convinced of the business plan and the success of the project, and support from the local leadership.

Fig. 1. Existing retail parks and those under construction. Source: own interpretation

Location selection procedure. To choose a location, a comprehensive study of the area is made, including analyses of demographics, economy, infrastructure, underground infrastructure, and competition is studied quite extensively if of course, it is available. Planned infrastructure projects and future investments in the area are also taken into account. Once all these indicators are examined and it is decided that this area has potential, the search for a suitable location begins. Here every retail chain has strict requirements to follow, of course, a compromise can always be made if there is another added value. For example, if there is no possibility of parking at the store, this can be compensated by the fact that the location has a strong foot traffic. Another criterion for location selection is distance from the chain's retail outlet as well as distance from a competitor, and here too a compromise can be made if, for example, the competitor is separated by a river or a multi-lane boulevard that acts as a barrier and limits access between the two outlets. The demographic factor is also examined, taking into account the population within a kilometer or two radius. The population purchasing power in the area is also an important criterion for a location. After taking into account all these criteria and their analysis and if it is positive and meets the requirements for the location of the company proceeds to the initiation of the procedure for the realization of the commercial object.

Analysis of the situation in the country. The specific situation in the country is presented by a Colliers International report for 2023. With a total of 11 retail parks open in 11 different locations in the country - three of the Holiday Park brand (Stara Zagora, Haskovo and Pernik), Retail Park Silistra, Retail Park Razlog, Knyazhevo Shopping Center (Sofia), Retail Park Arena - Shumen, Kaufland Retail Park (Sandanski), as well as 1 retail park each in Dimitrovgrad, Karlovo and Nessebar. With the new openings, the total gross lettable area of all the retail parks in operation in the country by the end of 2023 amounts to 501,500 sqm, spread across 58 sites. Shopping centers (malls) mainly present in the cities are experiencing record growth in terms of high occupancy and rental levels. Vacancy rates in

shopping centers vary between 0.1% and 5%. As a result of high demand and lack of supply, rents in shopping centers and on high streets have risen significantly to record levels over the last five years. Figure 1 also visualizes the situation with the development of retail parks in the country.

The prediction for the market is that retailers continue their expansion and this trend is expected to continue through 2024. Retail parks will continue to grow in number and coverage across the country. The market is reaching its saturation point and developers will no longer rely on being the only project in a location. The success of new parks will depend on their adequate positioning and the availability of competitive advantages. The focus of major investors is in Sofia, where a significant increase in retail space is expected. Over the past year, new trends have been noticed in retail parks, no longer relying on just one floor, but resorting to a second floor. This trend is expected to continue especially in Sofia, in the context of rising land prices in prime locations. Another trend is that many retailers are switching to online sales. In this situation, some of them are starting to optimize their physical presence by closing inefficient stores and investing in the development and improvement of well-performing locations. In 2024, this situation will continue with the focus remaining on expansion with physical stores.

The conclusion is that retailers have become more selective in their choice of locations for expansion. Increased investment in technology integration is expected. While rental rates in shopping malls and high streets saw significant growth during the past year. With stable tenant demand and a lack of supply, this trend will continue through 2024/2025.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study show that supporting regional development through a network of retail outlets is not in a period of market saturation and there are still regions and cities where there is potential for retail parks to open.

The topic is far from being exhausted and needs new theses and material on it, but can serve as a basis for further research on how to develop regions through a network of retail outlets. The basic causes of the current situation are outlined, but this does not mean that they are all the causes. More in-depth research can be done on optimizing the network of outlets, the state of companies, their expansion plans in the country, the level of property prices in different regions, and how this influences the choice of optimal locations, possible future investments in the region, and attention to government intervention in the economy.

In summary, the research thesis is largely confirmed. Retail parks have an important place in the regional development of the Bulgarian state because they provide significant added value to the regional economy and stimulate its development.

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CORPORATE MANAGEMENT IN EMPOWERING CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

The European Commission defines corporate social responsibility as a concept whereby companies voluntarily integrate concern for social issues and environmental protection into their business activities and relationships with stakeholders (owners, shareholders, employees, consumers, suppliers, government, media, and the wider public). The purpose of current article is to identify the key factors of corporate management to empower the corporate social responsibility.

This paper has presented social responsibility in the context of corporate governance. It highlights the importance of corporate governance in relation to corporate social responsibility (CSR) and the significance of a well-established corporate governance system for stable and sustainable growth. Good corporate governance can significantly influence socially responsible business practices, which is why CSR should be integrated into this system. Specific activities where the introduction of CSR can be recognized include fostering innovation, continuous training and education, partnerships, ongoing measurement of financial and non-financial business factors, reporting, control, and more.

KEY WORDS: corporate management, social responsibility, principles of management, efficiency

ABSTRAKT

Die Europäische Kommission definiert die soziale Verantwortung der Unternehmen als ein Konzept, bei dem die Unternehmen auf freiwilliger Basis soziale Belange und den Umweltschutz in ihre Geschäftstätigkeit und in die Beziehungen zu den Stakeholdern (Eigentümer, Aktionäre, Mitarbeiter, Verbraucher, Lieferanten, Regierung, Medien und die breite Öffentlichkeit) integrieren. Ziel des vorliegenden Artikels ist es, die Schlüsselfaktoren der Unternehmensführung zur Stärkung der sozialen Verantwortung von Unternehmen zu ermitteln.

In diesem Beitrag wird die soziale Verantwortung im Zusammenhang mit der Unternehmensführung dargestellt. Er unterstreicht die Bedeutung der Unternehmensführung in Bezug auf die soziale Verantwortung der Unternehmen (CSR) und die Bedeutung eines gut etablierten Systems der Unternehmensführung für ein stabiles und nachhaltiges Wachstum. Eine gute Corporate Governance kann sozial verantwortliche Geschäftspraktiken erheblich beeinflussen, weshalb CSR in dieses System integriert werden sollte. Zu den spezifischen Aktivitäten, an denen die Einführung von CSR erkannt werden kann, gehören die Förderung von Innovationen, kontinuierliche Aus- und Weiterbildung, Partnerschaften, laufende Messung finanzieller und nichtfinanzieller Geschäftsfaktoren, Berichterstattung, Kontrolle und mehr.

STICHWORTE: Unternehmensführung, soziale Verantwortung, Grundsätze der Unternehmensführung, Effizienz

RÉSUMÉ

La Commission européenne définit la responsabilité sociale des entreprises comme un concept selon lequel les entreprises intègrent volontairement les questions sociales et la protection de l'environnement dans leurs activités commerciales et leurs relations avec les parties prenantes (propriétaires, actionnaires, employés, consommateurs, fournisseurs, gouvernement, médias et grand

public). L'objectif de cet article est d'identifier les facteurs clés de la gestion d'entreprise pour renforcer la responsabilité sociale de l'entreprise.

Cet article présente la responsabilité sociale dans le contexte de la gouvernance d'entreprise. Il souligne l'importance de la gouvernance d'entreprise par rapport à la responsabilité sociale des entreprises (RSE) et l'importance d'un système de gouvernance d'entreprise bien établi pour une croissance stable et durable. Un bon gouvernement d'entreprise peut influencer de manière significative les pratiques commerciales socialement responsables, c'est pourquoi la RSE devrait être intégrée dans ce système. Parmi les activités spécifiques où l'introduction de la RSE peut être reconnue, citons la promotion de l'innovation, la formation et l'éducation continues, les partenariats, la mesure continue des facteurs financiers et non financiers de l'entreprise, les rapports, le contrôle, etc.

MOTS CLÉS: gestion d'entreprise, responsabilité sociale, principes de gestion, efficacité

INTRODUCTION

The European Commission defines corporate social responsibility as a concept whereby companies voluntarily integrate concern for social issues and environmental protection into their business activities and relationships with stakeholders (owners, shareholders, employees, consumers, suppliers, government, media, and the wider public). Corporate social responsibility is not a passing trend but has a long-term impact on the strategic directions and practices of modern organizations. Companies in the market face daily challenges of the global economy, and without clear strategic direction and effective strategic management, it is impossible to expect their average business performance. The key question arises: why should companies behave socially responsible? The answer has three dimensions: business ethics, corporate social responsibility, and ideology, values, and attitudes as key parts of organizational culture. It is important to emphasize that all three dimensions have roots in different scientific disciplines, and on the other hand, they are all interconnected and influence each other. Thus, socially responsible business practices will significantly impact the visibility of the company, and it will also mean its free advertising and greater interest from others in forming partnerships. By demonstrating social responsibility, companies present themselves as institutions that care about the social environment in which they operate, as well as about the people who work in them. This paper links the importance of corporate management with corporate social responsibility, i.e., the significance of good corporate management and its impact on social responsibility and society in general.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Concept and Definition of Corporate Social Responsibility. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) or socially responsible business has numerous definitions and meanings. It is generally understood that CSR involves the proper payment of taxes, proper employee registration, and maintaining good relations with customers, suppliers, and others. However, CSR encompasses much more. It includes all voluntary actions taken by companies that demonstrate their concern for certain groups, such as young people, employees, the local community, the environment, and everything that surrounds the company. Over the past decades, CSR has gained greater importance as an idea, as a corporate strategy and as a practical programme in corporations (Cannon, 1994; Carroll, 1999; Carroll, 2008). An array of concepts has emerged around the phenomenon: stakeholder theory that comes from ethics (Freeman, 1984; Donaldson and Preston, 1995; Phillips et al., 2003); shareholder value (Halme and Niskenan, 2001); (Borisov, Nikolov and Radev, 2020); CSR (Carroll, 1979; Mintzberg, 1983); corporate citizenship related to the political concept of citizen (Andriof and McIntosh, 2001; Logsdon and Wood, 2002); corporate social performance related to sociology (Callan and Thomas,

2009); and corporate codes of conduct (Sethi, 2002) to name just a few of the many CSR theories suggested. (For an excellent overview and comparison of CSR theories like corporate social performance, shareholder value theory, stakeholder theory and corporate citizenship, please pay attention to Melé (2008).)

Terms like corporate sustainability and responsibility (CSR) are used to better describe the areas for which companies are accountable. There are also various definitions of CSR. One such definition states that CSR is a company's obligation to utilize its resources in a socially beneficial way, thereby bringing benefits to both the company and society as a whole. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development considers CSR to be one of the three dimensions of corporate sustainability, as illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 1. The Relationship between Corporate Sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility

Source: Matešić, M., Pavlović, D., Bartoluci, D.: Društveno odgovorno poslovanje, VPŠ Libertas, Zagreb, 2015., pp. 18.

The image depicts the relationship between the social dimension with environmental and economic dimensions, defined as "the business world's commitment to sustainable economic development that contributes by working with employees, their families, the local community, and society as a whole to improve their quality of life (Matešić et al., 2015)." Corporate sustainability supports sustainable development and implies the long-term stability of a company's performance and survival. Social responsibility is presented here as an equal dimension, alongside economic and environmental dimensions, differing from some previous definitions. Some authors argue that socially responsible business is a constant that changes in response to environmental expectations and needs. As expectations and priorities change, so does the company adapt to the new situation."

"CSR is the responsibility of enterprises for their impact on society"—this is the currently accepted definition of corporate social responsibility (Matešić et al., 2015). According to this, companies are responsible for all their impacts on society and the environment. CSR can also be the willingness of a company to consider all economic, technical, and legal requirements in its operations. Corporate social responsibility should be visible and tangible, specific to each company. CSR is tailored to the needs and capabilities of the company, as well as the needs of all stakeholders. It is wrong to consider corporate social responsibility as donations, which are essentially a cost to the company if no

other benefit such as increased sales or a good image in society is derived from this action. Corporate social responsibility deals, in a way, with profit-making, but it is very important how it is done. How it is done is precisely defined by CSR definitions, i.e., by meeting the interests of all stakeholders (Matešić et al., 2015).

Some of the responsibilities of companies differ, so it is necessary to determine the strategy before implementing CSR, i.e., the direction in which they want to go. A strategic approach to problem-solving is the foundation for sustainable competitive advantage. Some companies incorporate behavior patterns into their management structure, internal control systems, and research programs. Therefore, CSR does not have a single definition; rather, it is known that there are defined groups of activities carried out in a company. CSR is in a way an obligation to create a "social contract" between the business and social sectors, as companies commit to long-term welfare, minimizing negative impacts in their operations.

Social responsibility can be defined as the degree of responsibility manifested in the operational and strategic activities of organizations that have a daily direct impact on various stakeholder groups and the environment, or the way of achieving commercial success by promoting ethical behavior and respecting the needs of people, communities, and the natural environment. Thus, today, companies are expected not only to create value but also to actively participate in what is called the practice of socially responsible behavior (Tipurić, 2008). Over the years, the concept of corporate governance has shifted from a model focused solely on profit to a model where responsibility lies at all levels of management and towards all stakeholders. Corporate social responsibility represents just such a concept, a concept where profit is achieved while simultaneously meeting social and environmental criteria with the ultimate goal of sustainability and the satisfaction of all involved stakeholders. Corporate social responsibility defines the relationship between society and the company on many levels to include all stakeholders and consider their needs. The world's most powerful institutions have become business organizations, and their responsibility can be monitored precisely from these two mentioned aspects.

The second meaning of corporate social responsibility lies in the word "responsibility." Responsibility is similar to initiative, used as recognition of a situation in which, if a certain purpose is to be achieved, one takes on some responsibility instead of expecting it from others. In business ethics, moral responsibility refers to the responsibility related to carrying out business actions, or in cases where some action is not taken, resulting in harm to an individual, group, or society. Social responsibility is not a static concept but a process of continuous negotiation. Being responsible is not an unchangeable state preset due to certain business activities. Being responsible is more about the willingness and capabilities on which organizations learn and align changing societal expectations with their management. Social responsibility is a current issue that can change processes and systems, and these should ensure long-term stability in the organization. When we talk about business ethics, it refers to the individual level, while at the organizational level, we talk about corporate social responsibility, and at the industry level, about sustainable development.

Today, managers should perform their duties in a transparent and responsible manner, which can be easily seen in the quarterly or annual reports of companies, crucial for increasing the competitiveness of the company. Such managerial behavior is based on sustainable development, respect for human rights, employee motivation, company reputation, and meeting the environmental dimension of business. Managers strive to identify potential problems and limitations they may face in the process of implementing social responsibility and determine the interdependencies between indicators of business performance on one hand and indicators of socially responsible business on the other. By defining possible problems before implementation, one can avoid customer disloyalty, employee demotivation, decreased sales, and a subordinate market position. In many examples in

global practice, it is difficult to determine if it is socially responsible business because companies do not always behave consistently. Large multinational companies behave better in some countries considering their business practices in other countries, especially if the market development and the strength of stakeholder groups determine it. Therefore, social responsibility is not the same in France, the United Kingdom, Japan, Germany, and Croatia. If a company needs to invest in alternative energy sources or help a local hospital through donations, the responses will vary in the aforementioned countries because there is no universal answer. Creating a socially responsible company is a long-term strategy developed through a negotiation process with all stakeholders. Authors emphasize that the test of good philanthropy is that a company continues with good business practices without anyone knowing that their activity resulted in recognizable positive shifts for society (Tipurić, 2008).

Some authors state that the definition of CSR has a normative meaning according to which companies must meet basic conditions: economic, legislative, ethical, and discretionary. Economic implies value creation and profit, legislative compliance with laws and regulations, ethical alignment with ethical and moral standards, and discretionary refers to voluntary activities beneficial to society. Philanthropic CSR is also mentioned, an altruistic approach mentioned in biblical records, where it was necessary to help and share with those less fortunate. Philanthropic CSR serves to invest in the community to solve some social problems, whose resolution simultaneously benefits society and the company.

Corporate Governance and Social Responsibility. Corporate governance is a system of supervisory mechanisms through which all suppliers of key inputs ensure returns on their investments in the corporation without compromising its long-term survival (Tipurić, 2008). Therefore, corporate governance represents the management and includes a set of relationships between management, the board, shareholders, and the stakeholders of the company, defining the framework for setting goals and determining the means to achieve those same goals while monitoring the performance and effectiveness of the company. Over the years, the primary definition of corporate governance has expanded, and today it is associated with stakeholders or interest groups. Every company should consider their rights, interests, and desires, be ethical, responsible, and profitable, as this way of managing leads to economic growth and the creation of a modern corporation. Corporate governance connects various areas, thereby distinguishing successful corporations from less successful ones. If a company is well managed, it will progress in the short term, which can mean its long-term survival. The management system should be set in such a way that it primarily starts from the managers. It is crucial to determine who the managers represent, to whom the managers are accountable, how they are supervised, and what the relationship is between managers and company owners. Then, the question arises about the relationships between shareholders, primarily majority and minority shareholders, and their rights. Last but not least, the area of action related to corporate social responsibility, i.e., how it is expressed, the relationship with the public and potential investors, and the relationship with other stakeholders such as workers. A quality corporate governance system will affect the reduction of capital costs and the more efficient use of resources (Račić and Cvijanović, 2005).

The modern corporation is a phenomenon that began to spread in the last century, representing a form of business where the owners are no longer personally responsible for the obligations or any other actions the company performs to create the final product. The ownership function separated from the function of managing the company's resources, one of the most significant events in economic history. Thus, in the 19th century, the importance of corporations grew, and organizing economic activity became the main form of business activity in all developed countries of the world. The modern corporation enabled the spreading of financial risk among millions of individual investors, allowed resource allocation in creating new technologies, products, and services, and became an

accelerator of economic growth. Accordingly, the modern corporation creates wealth in several different ways, such as compensation for employees, earnings for investors, and other benefits compared to costs for customers. By achieving individual benefits, a benefit is created for all. Investors, i.e., owners, have the opportunity to participate in the company's profit without taking on the responsibility of operations, and management has the opportunity to run the company without personal investments. Owners have limited liability but have the very important right to choose the top management of the company.

With the emergence of the modern corporation, managers gained the freedom to manage the company according to their own goals. They became more oriented towards decisions in the direction of long-term development and stability, not just in the direction of profit-making. Viewed from the outside, various goals, economic and non-economic, intertwine in the corporation, and managers should be representatives of the entire company, not just the shareholders. They are expected to balance the interests of the public and shareholders, creditors, employees, and others. The success and survival of the company depend on their work. They determine the goals, set the directions and tasks, direct resources, and organize work and production processes. Besides, managers have their own goals, which may not align with maximizing the long-term wealth of shareholders. Naturally, every manager wants to achieve personal satisfaction, status, job security, and personal income. All their goals must be agreed upon with the company's owners, as the knowledge that managers possess puts them at a significant advantage over owners in the modern corporation.

Challenges of Corporate Governance. The fundamental requirement for a modern corporation is to create wealth for key stakeholders in a responsible manner. Without responsibility, there is no success in a democratic world. Corporate governance is based on the principles of "be ethical, be responsible, and be moral (Tipurić, 2008)." As the author notes, in the context of developing economic democracy, efficiency remains a key criterion of business and corporate life, taking into account social responsibility and the demands of key stakeholders.

At the end of the last century, the ideas of "managerial capitalism" about a different definition of the corporation did not disappear but were enhanced in the new concept, the stakeholder approach, focusing on the interests of stakeholders. This approach places greater emphasis on the social dimension. Managerial capitalism was based on abandoning the understanding of managers' roles as exclusively representing shareholders' interests and accepting the definition of managers as representatives of the company's interests as a separate entity whose existence is not closely tied to shareholders. Critics saw problems in this approach, such as an excessively strong and often arrogant management position without special regard for shareholders. The ownership approach recognized the purpose of the company as an instrument to satisfy owners' interests, considering they bear certain business risks. Proponents of this approach believe that all interests will be best satisfied if the company bases its operations on maximizing owners' returns.

However, advocates of the stakeholder approach disagree with this thinking. They argue that shareholders are not the only ones bearing risks associated with the company's activities. Employees with specific qualifications related to a particular company also have a stake in the company, exposed to risks just as shareholder investments are. On the other hand, the problem with the stakeholder approach is its lack of specificity. Who is actually responsible for managing the interests and demands of stakeholders? According to the stakeholder approach, the company should treat both external and internal stakeholders equally and ethically, which is difficult to achieve in practice. Thus, modern corporate governance emerged from the ownership movement but is influenced by the stakeholder approach in many societies. There are opinions that companies should use ownership instruments more and adopt important ideas from the stakeholder approach. Increasingly, an organization's ability depends on its comparative advantage in making knowledge workers productive. The problem of

managing the corporation will resurface quickly. The purpose of management will need to be redefined to satisfy both legal owners, such as shareholders, and owners of human capital, such as knowledge workers, who give the organization the ability to create wealth.

A good system of corporate governance results in reduced capital costs and efficient use of resources by the company, which will affect the building of a competitive advantage while simultaneously contributing to the development of a fairer society by promoting responsible business practices and protecting the rights and interests of stakeholders.

Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has, over the past two decades, become a part of daily life not only for businesses and managers but also for civil society entities, governments, and conscientious individuals. CSR refers to activities that are not exclusively profit-oriented and are described through various terms, such as sustainable development, ethical business practices, corporate citizenship, and corporate sustainability.

Before the 20th century, there was no room for social responsibility as capable managers tied to strong companies held the greatest societal power. There was no other interest beyond strengthening their personal rights, and the sole responsibility of companies was financial, directed only towards the owners. In the 20th century, things began to change. In the United States, a managerial revolution occurred, separating the ownership and management of large companies. It was concluded that economic theory was too simplistic and superficial and that it was impossible to apply natural laws in controlling individuals and their social needs. Conflicts arose in the market due to companies whose sole aim was profit-making. Companies needed to behave socially responsibly; otherwise, the state would have imposed increased regulation and bureaucracy on them, leading them to become "socialized." It can be said that socially responsible behavior, in this context, arose as a consequence of avoiding social or state penalties. Companies began to act in accordance with expected social norms.

Today, the concept of CSR does not have clearly defined definitions. It is considered a new management approach as an alternative to the classical model of growth and profit maximization. There have been numerous events in the not-so-distant past aimed at addressing sustainable development issues, such as conferences, agreements, agendas, ISO standards, and more. Sustainable development is envisioned as a political model of society on a global level, while socially responsible business is a concept within the micro-level of society. In the 1980s, a management policy was created according to which an organization must align its activities with stakeholder expectations. Such a policy marked the beginning of a new approach in strategic management, based on acting in accordance with stakeholders' interests. In the 21st century, this concept set a new direction for defining corporate strategy.

Today, CSR is implemented either for long-term profit generation or due to legal obligations. For a company, CSR means increased profit and recognition. The markets in which companies operate demand quality standards and ethical behavior towards all stakeholders. Large companies should integrate social responsibility into the foundations of their business operations, which requires significant effort and reorganization of overall activities and management. Therefore, CSR was initially conceived as a voluntary initiative but later became legally regulated. Over time, companies began to introduce quality management standards and environmental awareness into their operations (ISO standards). Business codes of conduct, improvements, and reporting on socially responsible activities were also introduced. Reporting on socially responsible business practices by companies is a crucial element of successful communication between the company and other stakeholders, especially society. Increasingly, organizations and companies have successfully implemented the idea of

sustainability and social responsibility into their business practices. They demonstrate that collaboration with existing natural resources and human potential is possible.

CONCLUSION

This paper has presented social responsibility in the context of corporate governance. It highlights the importance of corporate governance in relation to corporate social responsibility (CSR) and the significance of a well-established corporate governance system for stable and sustainable growth. Good corporate governance can significantly influence socially responsible business practices, which is why CSR should be integrated into this system. Specific activities where the introduction of CSR can be recognized include fostering innovation, continuous training and education, partnerships, ongoing measurement of financial and non-financial business factors, reporting, control, and more. Corporate governance encompasses a set of internal and external mechanisms such as boards, management compensation, ownership concentration, corporate reporting, stakeholder relations, legislative and regulatory frameworks, and others. Properly establishing and utilizing these mechanisms in corporate governance will significantly impact efficiency. From the analyzed insurance companies, it can be concluded that all three companies have well-established these mechanisms. In all the analyzed companies, the dual model or so-called closed model of corporate governance prevails, which is characteristic of European countries. In the analyzed companies, two bodies have been established, as depicted in the dual model: the supervisory board and the management board. The role of the supervisory board in the analyzed companies is to oversee the company and monitor operations, while the management board is authorized to manage operations and represent the company.

In corporations with a closed system of corporate governance, there can also be co-ownership of corporations, or interconnections, such as between banks and large companies, which was the case with the observed insurance companies. The analyzed companies place significant emphasis on employee care, further education, client loyalty, and attracting new clients with innovative and technological solutions, as well as environmental protection, various sponsorships, and donations. All companies timely and publicly share truthful information about the company, its financial state, and annual reports are available on their websites.

Thus, it can be concluded that in the observed insurance companies, management has well-established business strategies and embedded social responsibility at the core of the company's organizational structure. Today, corporations have become focused on value creation, which is evident in the observed companies and their mission and vision statements. For a company, it is a great challenge to simultaneously meet the demands of various stakeholder groups. The company should respond equally to the needs of employees and clients, which requires the organizational structure to be adaptable, flexible, and equipped with timely information.

Creating a culture within a company essentially means developing mutual trust. This approach achieves harmony within the company, which is the key to future success and development, both for individuals and the company. When employees gain trust, they will work together towards achieving success, ultimately bringing success to the company.

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THE IMPACT OF DISASTERS AND ACCIDENTS ON THE FUNCTIONING OF RURAL AREAS IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the impact of disasters and accidents on the conditions for socio-economic and demographic development of rural areas in Bulgaria. The topicality of the topic is caused by the necessity in the new conditions of globalization to overcome regional and local risks related to the way of life of the population. To a large extent, the processes of urbanization and the relocation of the population in urban areas lead to the creation of threats to its security, mainly by disrupting the reliability of the functioning of the natural-ecological and socio-economic systems. Rural areas and their potential for security and regional development must therefore be strengthened. In this regard, it is important to create the necessary basic conditions for the life and development of the population - minimum infrastructure, taking measures to reduce natural and environmental risks through a system encompassing activities and facilities for monitoring, maintaining and cleaning riverbeds and forests in sparsely populated areas in Bulgaria.

KEY WORDS: accident, disaster, conditions, work, region, system, management

ABSTRAKT

Dieser Artikel befasst sich mit den Auswirkungen von Katastrophen und Unfällen auf die Bedingungen für die sozioökonomische und demografische Entwicklung der ländlichen Gebiete in Bulgarien. Die Aktualität des Themas ergibt sich aus der Notwendigkeit, unter den neuen Bedingungen der Globalisierung regionale und lokale Risiken für die Lebensweise der Bevölkerung zu bewältigen. Die Verstädterungsprozesse und die Verlagerung der Bevölkerung in städtische Gebiete führen in hohem Maße zu Bedrohungen für die Sicherheit der Bevölkerung, vor allem durch die Störung der Zuverlässigkeit des Funktionierens der natürlichen, ökologischen und sozioökonomischen Systeme. Der ländliche Raum und sein Potenzial für Sicherheit und regionale Entwicklung müssen daher gestärkt werden. In diesem Zusammenhang ist es wichtig, die notwendigen Grundvoraussetzungen für das Leben und die Entwicklung der Bevölkerung zu schaffen - eine Mindestinfrastruktur, Maßnahmen zur Verringerung von Natur- und Umweltrisiken durch ein System, das Aktivitäten und Einrichtungen zur Überwachung, Instandhaltung und Reinigung von Flussbetten und Wäldern in dünn besiedelten Gebieten Bulgariens umfasst.

STICHWORTE: Unfall, Katastrophe, Bedingungen, Arbeit, Region, System, Management

RÉSUMÉ

Cet article se concentre sur l'impact des catastrophes et des accidents sur les conditions de développement socio-économique et démographique des zones rurales en Bulgarie. L'actualité du sujet est due à la nécessité, dans les nouvelles conditions de la mondialisation, de surmonter les risques régionaux et locaux liés au mode de vie de la population. Dans une large mesure, les processus d'urbanisation et de relocalisation de la population dans les zones urbaines entraînent des menaces pour sa sécurité, principalement en perturbant la fiabilité du fonctionnement des systèmes naturels, écologiques et socio-économiques. Il faut donc renforcer les zones rurales et leur potentiel de sécurité et de développement régional. À cet égard, il est important de créer les conditions de base nécessaires à la vie et au développement de la population - une infrastructure minimale, en prenant des mesures pour réduire les risques naturels et environnementaux grâce à un système englobant des activités et

des installations de surveillance, d'entretien et de nettoyage des lits des rivières et des forêts dans les zones peu peuplées de la Bulgarie.

MOTS-CLÉS: accident, catastrophe, conditions, travail, région, système, gestion

INTRODUCTION

In the context of dynamically evolving processes brought about by globalization and integration of the national economy, population migration gives rise to a new type of problems in rural areas of the country. There is a wide range of problems to be solved in the rural areas of Bulgaria, but we will focus on the importance of disasters and accidents as a factor for the functioning of rural areas, and hence the good health of the population. Solving such a range of problems is linked to the different rates of economic development growth, which leads to increasing disparities between different territorial communities. In other words, the different rates of economic development in countries such as Bulgaria also set the daily difficulties in terms of optimal functioning of rural areas, and the human capital problems in them lead to the deterioration of the civil security system. In practice, civil security today is changing its focus and depends primarily on preventive measures of governance to deal with disasters, accidents, crises, epidemics and not least terrorist acts in urban areas (Dayal Saraswat, K. 2022). The agricultural and non-agricultural parts of the rural area form a separate entity from the urban area, which is characterized by a strong concentration of inhabitants and vertical and horizontal structures.

The traditional distinction between urban and rural areas in a country is based on the assumption that urban areas, as defined in that country, offer a different standard of living and usually a higher economic standard of living (Tsonkov, N. 2023). The term rural does not have a common definition across countries, making it difficult to compare rural areas globally or even at the national level. In this context, this paper considers the concept of governance from the perspective of the systems approach, according to which governance is a system that brings together a set of interrelated elements whose functioning is subordinated to a clear and well-defined goal. This system brings together two main elements - the object and the subject of governance. We can assume that the activities of planning, commanding, organizing, coordinating and controlling are indivisible and should be considered as a whole, not as separate and independent from each other (Dragnev, V. 2004). Let us recall that a disaster is any natural phenomenon such as earthquake, flood, landslide, storms, blizzards, avalanches, specific fires, prolonged droughts and epidemics. Radiological, chemical and bacteriological contamination are disasters where casualties and severe material damage to property are caused or the health and lives of the population are endangered. Forest fires are a serious environmental, social, economic and business problem. Until the late 1980s, the main statistical indicators characterising the dimensions of forest fires pointed to a relatively constant size of the problem. Data from the last decade, however, reveal a dramatic change in the forest fire situation: the number of fires and the average area per fire have increased 6-fold, and the area burned and the percentage of forested area burned per year have increased 35-fold. The increase is not in points but in tens of times. As a consequence of the drastic deterioration of the fire situation in Bulgaria's forests in the last decade of the 20th century, it is now almost comparable to that in regions and countries where forest fires are a natural and historically determined phenomenon.

Thus, at the regional level, conditions are created due to the environment for intensive and social processes to take place, which affect the pattern of environmental management and the way of life of the population (Tsonkov, N., Petrov, K., Slaveva, K., & Berberova-Vulcheva, C. 2023). The study of the settlements and their social and living conditions, as well as the institutional links between them, has always been a central point in all survey studies. A proper interpretation of each settlement and the connections it creates helps in its modelling. In other words, process management and crisis

management is an important stage in the social gravitation of regions and their governance. In this way, an environment is formed in the population of places that has the possibility of building a synthesized and simplified image of it, from which conclusions can be drawn, developments can be traced, processes can be extrapolated and decisions can be made for their future or the problems created can be directed and overcome. In the European Union, there is a particular concern for rural areas. This concern has been very pronounced since the 1980s, when rural areas were associated with values such as nature conservation. The adopted map "European rural map" gives the following definition: rural area means continental or coastal land, including villages and small towns, where most of the land is used for agriculture, forestry, aquaculture and fisheries, economic and cultural activities of the inhabitants of these regions (crafts, industry, services, etc.), the function of rest and recreation of an extra-urban nature or nature protection and other uses(Georgieva , M. 2021). The concept of village (or rural) represents a territory (area with land) in which no unanimously accepted definition has been reached so far, although the multitude of concepts and definitions given by specialists refer to the same physical (geographical) space. Rural space is not a homogeneous whole, but it is not an abstract space either (Kolev N., Chupetlovski S., Uzunov S., Dimitrov,2008). In the villages the trend of population decrease continues. In the period up to 2024 there is a constant, relatively high total mortality rate, which determines the negative natural growth. The population decline in the district is due to the decreased birth rate - 8.6% and increased death rate - 14.9‰ and to a much lesser extent migration. More than half of the district's population is of working age. The number of people over working age is approximately ¼ of the total population of the district. Ageing is more pronounced in rural than in urban areas. The demographic aging of the population, places additional demands on the structure of health needs, due to the fact that the elderly are carriers of more than one chronic disease, which also leads to higher costs for health care. the concept of "medical insurance" denotes the complex of organizational, medical-evacuation and hygiene-anti-epidemic measures to preserve the health and life of the population in crises, disasters and accidents (Kapucu, N., Hawkins, C. V., & Rivera, F. I. 2013).

RESULTS ND DISCUSSION

Methods and conceptual apparatus for rural research. Europe's rural areas are undergoing profound change, which is likely to accelerate if the countries of Eastern Europe are fully integrated into the Union, which is why the European Union has taken care of rural problems by implementing its own rural approach linked to the territory concerned. Thus, in methodological terms, it is assumed that the object of management is the rural space (including the locality and the land) of the territory of the district in conditions of normal development, change or emergency (Tonev, St. 2012). On the other hand, the diversity of terminology used in relation to the "situation" causes the need for a response of the public management system that guarantees the state of society, the functionality of the public sector and the vitality of the local population. Thus, it is necessary to bring to the fore the concept of health, which is important for the public development of settlements, because the health status of the population is very important for the regional development of rural areas (.Mihailova Il., Chakurova R. 2011). At the same time, the role of the regionalist is to manage territorial processes and to find a balance in crises, disasters, accidents, catastrophes, etc. This process is related to finding the balance between concepts. It is therefore necessary to introduce a relatively consensual term such as 'disaster medical provision. To a large extent, we also consider it appropriate to use the term crisis. We assume that the term 'crisis' is the most general and includes any sudden or expected change in the established state of life caused by human activity, events or natural phenomena, with negative consequences for the territory, environment, population, citizens and material values of the country, the prevention, containment and overcoming of which requires immediate coordinated action.

(Georgieva, M. 2021). The Crisis Management Act (2005) defined the term "non-military crisis" as "any sudden or expected change in the established state of life caused by human activity, events and natural phenomena affecting the territory, population and material values of the country and requiring immediate action for its restoration". Following the repeal of the Crisis Management Act, there is no legal definition of the term "non-military crisis" in the Bulgarian legal framework, and the term has been deleted or replaced by the term "disaster" within the meaning of the Disaster Protection Act in the existing legal documents. According to Article 2 of the Disaster Protection Act, 'a disaster is a significant disruption of the normal functioning of society caused by natural phenomena and/or by human activity and resulting in negative consequences for the life or health of the population, property, the economy and the environment, the prevention, containment and recovery of which exceeds the capacity of the system to service the normal activities of public protection'. The Disaster Protection Act also sets out definitions of natural phenomena, where 'natural phenomena' are phenomena of geological (geophysical, geological), hydrometeorological and biological origin, such as earthquakes, floods, mass movements (landslides, debris flows, avalanches), storms, hailstorms, major snow accumulations, freezes, droughts, forest fires, mass diseases of an epidemic and episodic nature, pest infestations and the like caused by natural forces. The definition of an incident is also important. An 'incident' is an unforeseeable or difficult to predict action, limited in time and space, of high intensity of force or resulting from human activity, endangering the life or health of persons, property or the environment. Other definitions have been introduced in the legislation for concepts related to the problems of our society associated with its threats. In general, we can say that disaster impacts can include loss of life, injury, illness and other negative effects on human physical, mental and social well-being, along with damage to property, destruction of assets, loss of services, social and economic disruption and environmental damage. In this direction, we will consider the impact of disasters and accidents as factors in the reduction of the quality of the healthy environment and access to quality medical care (Popzaharieva, V.1995)

Development of disaster prevention processes in rural areas. The basic principles of disaster protection formulated in the legislation are the right to protection of every person, the priority of saving human life over other protection activities, publicity of information on disaster risks and on the activities of the executive authorities in disaster protection. All this places emphasis on preventive measures in providing protection, responsibility for the implementation of protection measures, phased provision of protection forces and resources. Medical provision of the population as part of disaster protection activities is subject to general principles, while at the same time there are certain specificities related to the complex and complex nature of medical activities and the structures that provide them. Disaster medical management is defined as a complex activity of the leading health authorities (at district level this is the PHI) to assess the medical situation, make management decisions and lead the medical forces and resources in carrying out rescue activities. Thus, spatial plans are important for the development of the regions, which determine the general structure and predominant use of the territories, the type and purpose of technical infrastructure and the protection of the environment and heritage sites are mandatory in the preparation of detailed spatial plans. They practically give the image of the region and the pace for its development and management (Tsonkov, N. 2023).

The existence of a prepared health management system in disaster situations plays a crucial role in achieving high efficiency in the activities of medical forces and means (teams, formations and facilities) in the medical provision of the population in the complex operating conditions, mass casualties and shortage of medical resources. Management of medical provision in the course of rescue works is subject to certain principles, which are largely uniform for all levels of management in health care and the general principles of protection of the population, which is associated with unity and subordination

in management. It is expressed to focus the activity in a purely territorial plan, the district or the municipality as the general design for the organization of rescue works in disasters are determined by the respective disaster protection headquarters. In this sense, the considerations and management decisions of the respective health head of medical provision are subject to the overall design and coordinated with the respective disaster protection headquarters (Lawangen, A. 2022).

The second essential factor is a judicious combination of the principles of centralisation and decentralisation, which is conditioned by the dynamic and complex nature of rescue operations and is expressed in the manifestation of initiative and rapid decision-making in accordance with the situation. The third factor is unity of command, which is a fundamental and important principle in management decision-making and in the leadership of medical forces and assets during rescue operations. However, this does not preclude discussing the problems encountered, requesting opinions, making suggestions and drawing up considerations. At district level, this means that decisions are taken by the Director of the RHI, actively supported by the Medical Assurance Board. The combination of vertical and horizontal hierarchy of the territorial systems studied by geography enables it to participate creatively in management and planning at different levels and territorial configurations. The requirements for governance are universal, both for the health system in terms of medical provision and for the actions of other bodies to manage the protection of the population in disasters. The management of medical forces and assets must be characterised by rigidity, flexibility, continuity and operability. First and foremost, robustness in management is reflected in the rapid and competent decision-making of the health authority and the specific requirements for their implementation, regardless of the difficulty and complexity of the situation. This requirement is essential both to save the life and health of people and to prevent various complications in the course of rescue work. On the other hand, a firm and competent decision and high rigour reassures the population and prevents the occurrence of mass psychoses. Secondly, flexibility and initiative are other important requirements which, to some extent, complement firmness. Flexible application of management decisions is necessitated by the complex nature and frequent changes in the environment. In these cases, the original solution no longer corresponds to one degree or another to the real needs at a given time, and initiatives are needed to adapt it to the new circumstances. Thirdly, continuity in management is a requirement that is closely linked to the constant monitoring by the governing bodies of changes in the situation, directing the efforts of medical units to the most difficult sections of the work, conducting manoeuvres with forces and means, etc. The ultimate goal of continuity in management appears to be the beneficial impact on the course of rescue activities. Last but not least, the emphasis on operability in medical support activities is largely determined by the business qualities and operational preparation of the management bodies. This requirement leads to a shortening of the terms and an increase in the efficiency of the management activity (Tsonkov, N. 2022)..

When a disaster situation arises, complex and difficult tasks are presented to the health authorities to solve. In a short time, based on the preliminary planning and the specific situation, it is required to draw up an operational plan for the medical provision of the population and, after its approval, to put it into practice and ensure appropriate effective control.

The first and foremost task facing managers after a disaster situation occurs is to clarify and assess the medical situation and to specify the goals and objectives of the health authorities. This requires the organisation of medical reconnaissance in the area of the outbreak, the most appropriate being the inclusion of a competent medical professional in the composition of the general reconnaissance groups. In certain cases, an independent medical intelligence team may also be formed in coordination with the on-site manager (Romanova, Hr. 2009).

It is important to note that the creation and maintenance of an operational picture of the general and medical situation is absolutely necessary for effective medical management. This includes

activities to collect, collate, synthesise and summarise disseminated information on the disaster and the general and medical situation created from all relevant information sources. Achieving a common operational picture allows all entities involved in the management of an incident to have the same information on the timing, actual damage and consequences, on-scene and off-scene resources available, the status of requests for assistance, and any other data needed to support decision-making at different levels. In addition, an operational picture of the medical situation is needed by the authorities managing the overall protection activities at national, district and municipal levels, NGOs, private sector organizations, critical infrastructure owners and operators, and all other organizations and individuals who have a role in managing and containing the effects of a disaster for effective, consistent and timely decisions. Having an operational picture during an incident helps to ensure the coherence of the entire disaster protection system (Romanova, Hr, 2012)

In order to maintain situational awareness, information must be continuously updated, much of this information can be used for a variety of purposes within the incident management system. For example, the same piece of information could be used to assist in the planning process to develop an operational plan of action for the incident. So too for deciding to provide public information, determining the resources needed and associated costs, determining the need for additional NGO involvement, private sector or NHS resources, identifying a safety issue and following up to provide additional information. On the basis of the information received on the situation and the design of the rescue activities, an assessment of the general and medical situation is carried out, including an assessment of the overall situation. It determines the size, location and timing of the disaster. Attention shall be paid to the nature and extent of the destruction, fires, floods, secondary outbreaks and contamination, etc. This assessment should clarify the extent of the damage and its impact on the conduct of medical rescue operations. The next important step is to assess the quantity and structure of medical losses. It is performed on the basis of the estimated and conducted medical intelligence. This assessment should justify conclusions on the localities, areas, neighbourhoods or individual buildings where the main rescue medical activities should be directed. Third, an assessment of the status of medical forces and assets is made. The number of health personnel killed and injured, the medical property destroyed or to be assessed for contamination, the number of medical teams, formations and hospitals prepared, manned and able to operate are taken into account. The hygiene and epidemiological situation must then be assessed. On the basis of the data on the hygienic-epidemiological situation of the area and the disaster situation, a conclusion is drawn on the influence of epidemiological factors on the organization of medical care, evacuation and treatment of the injured, removal of the population from the disaster area, etc. The assessment of the locality (area) is also important. The specific medico-geographical analysis of the disaster area and of the entire territorial unit, as well as of the state of the road network, enables appropriate decisions to be taken on the introduction and operation of medical formations, on the method of evacuation of the victims, on the conditions and locations for opening medical stations, etc. Last but not least, an assessment of the weather is carried out in terms of quantity (astronomical time) and quality (meteorological conditions) in order to clarify to what extent it will influence the organization of medical provision.

CONCLUSION

It is evident from the above discussion that in practice the impact of disasters and accidents is significant in rural areas and the health of the population is important to attract investment. Bulgaria is exposed to a number of natural hazards such as floods, landslides, earthquakes, forest fires, droughts, strong winds, heavy snowfalls, extreme temperatures and hail, the first three being the most prominent. Disaster risks facing the country are expected to increase given increasing urbanisation and industrial development and climate change. For this reason, disaster risk management (DRM) plays an

important role in the sustainable development of the country and is among the priorities for any government. In practice, when health infrastructure is disrupted, we notice significant difficulties and contingencies related to the normalization of the situation in the respective territorial communities. The condition of 238 municipal hospitals is not good, there are problems with the functioning of the Civil Protection. On the other hand, we can summarise a group of problems. First of all, at national level, there is no financial instrument that would make it possible to act in a timely and decisive manner when occupational health conditions deteriorate. Secondly, there is no clear generation of financial resources for preventive policies and implementation of projects related to disasters and accidents. In Bulgaria, climate change may significantly increase the occurrence and scale of weather-related disasters. A study by the National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (NIMH-BAS) projects an increase in annual air temperature in Bulgaria of between 0.7°C and 1.8°C by 2020. Even higher temperatures are expected by 2050 and 2080, with projections of increases of between 1.6°C and 3.1°C and 2.9°C and 4.1°C respectively. In general, the increase is expected to be more significant during the summer season (July to September). In terms of precipitation, a general decrease is expected, leading to a significant limitation of the country's water resources. It is clear from the presentation that the emphasis on prevention is related to the organization of activities to reduce the effect of disasters and accidents, without providing solutions to the case and ways of effective recovery of the quality of health infrastructure. In practice, the integration of this complex set of activities and structures, in the process of disaster medical insurance is only possible through competent advance planning and assignment of tasks within the framework of the general regulations for disaster protection at the municipal and district levels, and regulation of the powers of disaster medical insurance management by state health authorities so as not to disrupt the state of the health infrastructure.

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MODERN MANAGEMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on examining the specifics of modern management in the context of global business, with an emphasis on the global landscape of the 21st century. It discusses the positive and negative trends of contemporary globalization processes and their impact on economic flows and the global market. Additionally, the paper considers the unique aspects of an intercultural approach to managerial processes in global business conditions, outlining the main characteristics of ethnocentric, polycentric, and geocentric approaches to adapting to new markets. It also examines the specificities of performing fundamental managerial functions—planning, organizing, leading, managing human resources, and controlling—in the constantly changing global market.

KEY WORDS: globalization, management, cultural diversity, intercultural management approach, global business

ABSTRAKT

In diesem Beitrag werden die Besonderheiten des modernen Managements im Kontext der globalen Wirtschaft untersucht, wobei der Schwerpunkt auf der globalen Landschaft des 21. Jahrhunderts liegt. Es werden die positiven und negativen Trends der gegenwärtigen Globalisierungsprozesse und ihre Auswirkungen auf die Wirtschaftsströme und den globalen Markt erörtert. Darüber hinaus werden die besonderen Aspekte eines interkulturellen Ansatzes für Managementprozesse unter globalen Geschäftsbedingungen betrachtet und die Hauptmerkmale ethnozentrischer, polyzentrischer und geozentrischer Ansätze zur Anpassung an neue Märkte skizziert. Außerdem werden die Besonderheiten bei der Ausübung grundlegender Managementfunktionen - Planung, Organisation, Führung, Personalmanagement und Controlling - auf dem sich ständig verändernden globalen Markt untersucht.

STICHWORTE: Globalisierung, Management, kulturelle Vielfalt, interkultureller Managementansatz, Global Business

RÉSUMÉ

Ce document se concentre sur l'examen des spécificités de la gestion moderne dans le contexte du commerce mondial, en mettant l'accent sur le paysage mondial du 21e siècle. Il examine les tendances positives et négatives des processus de mondialisation contemporains et leur impact sur les flux économiques et le marché mondial. En outre, le document examine les aspects uniques d'une approche interculturelle des processus de gestion dans des conditions commerciales mondiales, en soulignant les principales caractéristiques des approches ethnocentriques, polycentriques et géocentriques de l'adaptation aux nouveaux marchés. Il examine également les spécificités de l'exercice des fonctions managériales fondamentales - planification, organisation, direction, gestion des ressources humaines et contrôle - dans un marché mondial en constante évolution.

MOTS-CLÉS: mondialisation, gestion, diversité culturelle, approche de la gestion interculturelle, entreprise mondiale

INTRODUCTION

With the development of information, capital, products, services, and people, along with the tendency to erase national borders, globalization is perceived as a world without borders. The advancement of the Internet and advanced communication technologies enables virtual access,

instant availability of information, and participation in business processes occurring in all parts of the world. In the 1960s, Canadian communication theorist Marshall McLuhan anticipated the life of the new age as life in a global village through the medium of computer networks and media. Considering the medium as the message, he predicted the life of the new age as a "mass-age" or the life of the electronic era in new virtual spaces on the planet, which depend on information. Some of his phrases, such as the global village and the medium as the message, have become part of everyday language, embodying their own message. McLuhan's metaphor of the world as a global village depicted processes that have indeed become global today, especially those related to the development of communication technologies, migration, and economic globalization.

The trend of rapid development in mass communications, information technologies, and the removal of time and space barriers has influenced the reduction of time distances, bringing distant countries closer, and initiating the creation of a global culture. On the other hand, the removal of borders has led to the formation of global financial markets and the facilitation of economic activities on a global scale. However, it has also led to the emergence of negative and destructive elements, such as global drug trafficking, narco-mafias, human trafficking, and terrorism. Consequently, the great potential for new forces and hopes from the 1990s transformed into an open threat (Dahrendorf, 2004). The beginning of the 21st century is considered a time of uncertainty and increasing general global dissatisfaction, where resistance to inequality, poverty, and the imposition of ruthless market rules by developed countries is expressed through social unrest and local wars. This discontent is further supported by anti-globalization movements and the activities of various non-governmental organizations and civil society at national and transnational levels, which take on a protective role of a corrective nature (Milardović, 2004).

As globalization continues to evolve, it brings both opportunities and challenges that require careful management and strategic planning. The interconnectedness of global markets means that economic fluctuations in one part of the world can have far-reaching impacts elsewhere. This interconnectedness also fosters competition, pushing companies to innovate and adapt quickly to changing market conditions.

In terms of management, the global business environment necessitates a deep understanding of cultural diversity and intercultural communication. Managers must be equipped to navigate the complexities of different cultural norms, values, and business practices. This includes adopting various management approaches, such as ethnocentric, polycentric, and geocentric strategies, to effectively operate in diverse markets.

Ethnocentric management focuses on applying the company's home-country practices universally, often leading to challenges in adapting to local cultures. Polycentric management, on the other hand, emphasizes local responsiveness by tailoring strategies to fit the unique cultural and business environments of each market. Geocentric management seeks to integrate a global perspective, combining the best practices from around the world to create a cohesive and adaptable strategy.

The dynamic nature of the global market also demands a robust approach to core management functions. Planning involves not only setting objectives but also anticipating global trends and potential disruptions. Organizing requires creating structures that can efficiently manage operations across different countries and regions. Leading in a global context means inspiring and guiding a diverse workforce while fostering an inclusive and collaborative culture. Managing human resources involves understanding and leveraging the diverse talents and perspectives of employees from various cultural backgrounds. Finally, controlling entails establishing metrics and monitoring systems that can provide timely and relevant insights into global operations.

The increasing importance of sustainability and corporate social responsibility (CSR) is another critical aspect of modern management in global business. Companies are expected to operate in an environmentally and socially responsible manner, considering the long-term impact of their actions on the planet and society. This includes adopting sustainable practices, reducing carbon footprints, and ensuring fair labor practices throughout the supply chain.

Moreover, technological advancements, particularly in artificial intelligence (AI) and data analytics, are transforming the landscape of global business. AI and machine learning can provide valuable insights into consumer behavior, optimize supply chains, and enhance decision-making processes. However, these technologies also raise ethical considerations, such as data privacy and the potential for bias in AI algorithms.

As global business continues to evolve, it is essential for managers to remain agile and forward-thinking. This involves continuous learning and development to stay abreast of the latest trends and technologies. Additionally, building strong relationships with stakeholders, including customers, employees, suppliers, and communities, is crucial for long-term success.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Global Picture in the 21st Century. At the dawn of the 21st century, for many theorists of change, the world represents a transitional period between modernism and postmodernism. Modernism, as a result of industrialization, the scientific and technological revolution, and overall economic and civilizational progress, began to show its negative side at the end of the 20th century. Industrialization led to pollution, ozone depletion, and the greenhouse effect; urbanization resulted in alienation; informatization endangered privacy; and globalization increasingly threatened local cultures, traditions, and customs. On the other hand, postmodernism, as a paradigm advocating individuality, openness, critical thinking, and a departure from rigid theories, dramatically heralded the unstoppable social upheavals and profound changes at the end of the last century—a time when the "old" began to die and the "new" had not yet been born.

In such conditions, the world of the new era is characterized by the rapid flow of information, capital, services, products, and people, the tendency to erase interstate borders, and new social, political, economic, and cultural relationships that are completely different from those previously known. Theorists of globalization in this context speak of a connected world based on information technology and planetary communication. The unprecedented and rapid development of technology has influenced the establishment of virtual communication, facilitating and accelerating economic activities between countries regardless of spatial distance and national borders. The internet and communication technologies enable simultaneous use of visual, audio, and textual communications, where the free flow of information globally allows for instant access to information, virtual presence, and direct participation in various events, regardless of where they occur in the world.

Globalization as a worldwide process has significantly impacted global social balance by networking the world in all areas of human interdependence, from economic to political to cultural systems. Along with trends that have influenced the changing global picture, such as the disproportionate population growth in underdeveloped parts of the world, increasing economic insecurity, deregulation of the social sector, and the changing role of the state, several new factors have emerged on a global level. These include the global expansion of markets aimed at economic and financial integration, the strengthening of supranational groups that limit state monopolies over individuals, society, and development, and the widening gap between the rich and the poor on both national and international levels. Economic globalization, as the foundation of the process that drives all other forms of globalization, strongly influences the unstoppable increase in trade and investment, enhanced and increased financial flows, the creation of a global, unified world market, transnationally

integrated production, and the weakening of national economies. These trends give globalization the characteristics of an unstoppable process, which is now considered a way of life in the 21st century (Bedečković, 2010). The concept of globalization in current public and scientific discourse is mentioned in two contexts: as a challenge or as a potential danger, with an increasing number of warnings directed at globalization risks. These risks, caused by global hyperproductivity, manifest in the form of illegal migration, the global drug market, globally organized crime, and global terrorism, which exceed the control capabilities of national states. The question of ethics and global solidarity arises as a fundamental issue for the future course of globalization, not in McLuhan's virtual, but in our real, living global village.

Modern Management and Global Business. As a process of integration, interconnection, and interdependence of economic, social, cultural, and political activities that transcend national borders, globalization today manifests in the increased volume of global exchange of goods, capital, services, and energy. Thanks to unprecedented levels of connectivity, there is a growing trend of global market expansion and the strengthening of supranational groups, which limit state monopolies. This brings into focus the issue of economic growth, the power and influence of multinational and transnational companies whose share in the global economy is dynamically increasing, creating conditions for new investment opportunities, access to new technologies, and access to new labor, capital, and raw material markets, as well as greater productivity and organizational success. The changing business conditions inevitably impact both the macro and micro environment, presenting numerous opportunities and threats to organizations and their management. In a world of globally interconnected activities, global standards related to product competitiveness, innovation, and customer service apply even to organizations without global ambitions. Therefore, for organizations aiming to survive and succeed in the market, thinking globally is no longer an option but a strategic imperative (Bahtijarević-Šiber et al., 2008).

In the context of dynamic global changes, which lead to shifts in business philosophy and an orientation of organizations towards their core business while outsourcing other activities (Sikavica et al., 2008), modern management faces new challenges. These challenges highlight the role of the modern manager, whose skills range from general conceptual and technical knowledge necessary for business success to interpersonal, communication, and group skills for dealing with people, and specific skills for managing change.

Recognizing people as the source of all value and the fundamental resource of management implies a shift from the "era of power" to the "era of adaptation," characterized by people-oriented managers. Modern management, as part of the ongoing narrative of human organization (Sikavica et al., 2008), emphasizes the importance of "soft variables," which include respecting knowledge, abilities, and leadership styles. The key issue and fundamental requirement of modern management in global business conditions is the application of a new paradigm in global business, which entails managing "intangible" material, with a necessary emphasis on knowledge and specific managerial skills as essential prerequisites for quality and efficient business operations in the global market.

One of the fundamental characteristics of organizations operating in the global market is their approach to the world market as a single entity, orientation towards teamwork, focus on employees and consumers, and constant monitoring of the latest information and technological advancements. Meeting the needs of the global market and adapting products and services to global trends requires an effectively designed global strategy for the organization, which must be led by management where the functions of planning, organizing, leading, human resource management, and control are adapted to conditions in the global environment.

When it comes to trends related to business efficiency in the global market, one of the greatest challenges for modern organizations is managing business teams composed of members from different

cultures, worldviews, religions, and languages. Managing diversity is considered one of the biggest challenges for modern management in the context of global business.

To elaborate further on the complexities and intricacies of managing in a global environment, it's essential to understand the role of technological advancements in shaping contemporary management practices. For instance, the integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning in decision-making processes has revolutionized how managers approach problem-solving and strategic planning. These technologies provide managers with the ability to analyze vast amounts of data quickly and accurately, enabling more informed and effective decisions.

Furthermore, the rise of digital communication tools has transformed traditional management structures. Virtual teams and remote working have become commonplace, necessitating new strategies for maintaining productivity and engagement. Managers must develop skills in virtual leadership, including the ability to foster collaboration and a sense of community among geographically dispersed team members.

Additionally, the concept of sustainable management has gained prominence in the global business landscape. Organizations are increasingly recognizing the importance of incorporating environmental and social considerations into their business strategies. This shift towards sustainability requires managers to balance economic objectives with ethical responsibilities, ensuring that their companies contribute positively to society and the environment.

The emphasis on corporate social responsibility (CSR) has also led to the development of new management practices. Managers are now expected to lead initiatives that promote social and environmental sustainability, which includes everything from reducing carbon footprints to ensuring fair labor practices in the supply chain. This holistic approach to management not only enhances the company's reputation but also attracts socially conscious consumers and investors.

Moreover, globalization has underscored the importance of cultural intelligence in management. Managers must be adept at navigating cultural differences and leveraging diverse perspectives to drive innovation and growth. This involves not only understanding cultural norms and practices but also fostering an inclusive organizational culture where all employees feel valued and respected.

In conclusion, the landscape of modern management in the context of global business is marked by rapid change and increasing complexity. Managers must be equipped with a diverse set of skills and knowledge to navigate this environment effectively. By embracing technological advancements, fostering sustainability, and valuing cultural diversity, managers can drive their organizations towards success in the global market. The continuous adaptation and learning will be key to thriving in the ever-evolving landscape of global business.

Business Processes in the Context of Global Operations. Global market expansion beyond national borders to operate in the most profitable, competitive, and promising world markets offers organizations the opportunity to engage in activities that ensure a competitive edge. The development of modern technologies and communications supports the localization of specific parts of organizations in the most favorable business locations, which, thanks to virtual connections, become accessible in a short time regardless of spatial distance. Communication among people working and conducting business in various parts of the world requires effective management of international operations, which entails performing managerial functions (planning, organizing, leading, human resources management, and controlling) with a necessary understanding of the complexities of the international environment and the specificities arising from the diversity of economic, legal, political, and socio-cultural systems (Bahtijarević-Šiber et al., 2008).

Operating in the international business environment implicates a need for high-quality and efficient management based on an understanding of the interplay of various cultural elements in

building successful business relationships. In this context, an intercultural management approach can be discussed, wherein the expansion into the global market, rapid development of new technologies, transportation, and communication media expand the concept of national and ethnic identity, creating space for new intercultural identities. The interaction, interdependence, and need for cooperation among different cultures to achieve successful business relationships and competitiveness in the global market presupposes managers' awareness of the impact of societal culture on business behavior. Success in global business significantly depends on the flexibility and appropriate response of managers to practices and values different from their own business environment. A positive attitude of managers towards values different from those they are accustomed to in their own business environment requires openness to differences and values, opinions, and ideas that arise from these differences.

On one hand, economic boundaries are blurring, while on the other, new boundaries conditioned by cultural differences are emerging, presenting challenges and opportunities in establishing business relationships while facing different political systems and legal and customs regulations. In this sense, the intercultural management approach in global business conditions entails promoting intercultural understanding and building business intercultural communication aimed at improving business cooperation and effective operations in the global market.

Operating in the global market involves shaping multicultural and corporate identity, whereby multinational companies and their managers start from different approaches to adapting and conquering new markets. According to Bahtijarević-Šiber et al. (2008), in practice, three basic approaches to adapting to new markets in the context of adjusting to business on the global cultural-plural market can be distinguished: ethnocentric, polycentric, and geocentric approaches.

The ethnocentric approach to adapting to new markets involves strictly controlling the activities and operations of the company's headquarters in foreign countries, where the company operates abroad in the same way as it does in its home country, often causing dissatisfaction among the local population due to the lack of respect and consideration for local culture, customs, and traditions. Polycentrically oriented companies approach activities and operations in new markets with more freedom, respecting the differences between the markets of different countries. When designing products and services and devising marketing campaigns, they consider the specifics of each country as a separate area with specific cultural characteristics. Geocentrically oriented companies prefer complete integration of operations at the global level, operating in different countries worldwide without prejudice. Their top management consists of managers from various countries who think globally when making strategic decisions, distributing work while respecting the strengths, potentials, and advantages of different countries. The operations of multinational companies on the global market generate both positive and negative effects in practice. The benefits of polycentric and geocentric oriented multinational companies for the countries in which they operate include better and more favorable employment opportunities, technology and knowledge transfer, and the stimulation of new industries significant for the development of local resources.

Multinational companies also influence the policies and national cultures of individual countries and, considering the profit they generate, have a significant impact on the gross national income level of less developed countries.

Group and efficient achievement of goals as a basic premise of management points to the necessity of coordination among individuals, implying that human resources are an extremely important resource for achieving goals. The main task of management is to train people for effectively achieving common goals. People, their knowledge, skills, creative and other abilities, and the specificity of their relationships form a unique profile and identity that cannot be copied or presented as a general matrix (Jurić, 2004). Therefore, general knowledge about management can be the same for all

organizations regardless of their activity, while their specificity arises from the application of general management knowledge in different environments, correlating with Drucker's assertion (1992:204) about the rootedness of management in culture and the description of the managerial job as "completely identical" regardless of where managers perform their job, but "how they do it can be completely different."

Delving into the humane, management primarily deals with people, their values, growth, and development. The humanistic orientation of management reflects its concern with its effects on society and the community. In this context, Drucker (1992:204) considers management a "humanistic art," humanistic because it deals with the fundamentals of knowledge, self-awareness, and leadership, and art because it deals with practice and application. Managers, therefore, in their daily work, use the knowledge of humanistic and social sciences (and their disciplines: economics, psychology, philosophy, history, and ethics) directed towards efficiency and results, regardless of the basic activity of the organization they work for. Their job, despite new, changed circumstances in the global market, remains the same. What differs is the way it is done.

Successful management in changing circumstances, particularly in the execution of core managerial functions—planning, organizing, leading, managing human resources, and controlling—requires understanding the complexities of the international environment and the specificities arising from the diversity of various economic, legislative, political, and socio-cultural systems. To effectively carry out these basic managerial functions, a manager must comprehend these complexities.

The planning function in international business involves considering the specificities arising from different economic, legislative, political, social, and cultural contexts. This includes the necessity to adapt products and services, as well as their promotion and distribution, to cultural and national differences. Therefore, planning in an international business context entails thinking globally and acting locally. It requires a broad understanding of issues on one hand and the adaptation of strategies and specific activities to local circumstances and needs on the other. Focusing planning on the international scene implies planning partnerships in joint international business ventures and joint investments, which involves achieving shared organizational goals. Conversely, developing partnerships to achieve common organizational goals also necessitates a local perspective that respects local resources and needs.

Analyzing the organizing function in international business on the global market emphasizes the organizational structure, specifically the design of the organization concerning the situational factors of each country. The design of the organizational structure of multinational companies in practice depends on various environmental factors, which usually depend on the business functions performed by the organization, the services or products it sells, and the areas in which it operates. Consequently, there is no single best way or universally applicable organizational design for all multinational companies. Instead, the organizational structure evolves depending on situational factors and cultural differences in each country.

Effective leadership in an international environment primarily requires managers to be sensitive to differences and to adapt their leadership style to the cultures with which they establish and develop business relationships. Culture, with all its components such as attitudes, beliefs, habits, customs, traditions, and attitudes toward new technologies and education, emerges as a crucial factor contributing to the complexity and challenge of management in an international environment. These cultural aspects significantly influence the behavior of employees and business partners in different countries. Generally, a manager's approach to international business in various countries is linked to the previously described ethnocentric, polycentric, and geocentric approaches to adapting multinational companies to new markets, and consequently to the perception of the superiority of one's own managerial practices or the awareness of the need to adapt one's managerial style to the

traditions of the country in which the company operates. The turbulence, unpredictability, and cultural plurality of the global market demand new leaders for the 21st century who will replace the fatigued managers of the industrial age through the effective combination of different leadership theories and styles (Sikavica et al., 2008).

In international business, where human resources are considered the primary competitive strength, special attention must be directed toward the managerial function of human resource management. This includes supporting the recruitment, retention, and development of culturally diverse employees and managing diversity. In practice, activities focused on accumulating human resources for international business often involve identifying individuals who know foreign languages, are willing to live and work abroad, and are open to differences. This also includes forming intercultural teams whose heterogeneity is reflected in different personality traits, attitudes, and value systems. Some multinational companies have specially developed training programs for employees and managers who are assigned to international tasks in various organizational units and branches worldwide (Certo & Certo, 2008).

The specific challenge of the managerial function of controlling in the context of international business on the global market is reflected in the need to control geographically dispersed organizational units (branches) of multinational companies operating in cultural environments with different levels of control requirements.

CONCLUSION

Operating in the global market is characterized by turbulence, uncertainty, rivalry, and an increasing need for flexibility. The changing and dynamic environment, along with the diverse workforce of contemporary organizations, are fundamental challenges of global business in the 21st century. The new business conditions on the global market and the specific needs of culturally pluralistic environments require managers to be aware of a broad spectrum of cultural differences and the value systems, behaviors, and business practices they entail. Managers must also be willing to acknowledge and accept these differences to establish business relationships that ultimately result in profit.

The success of managers in global business conditions, therefore, depends on their adaptability and openness to the values, behaviors, opinions, and attitudes of culturally diverse business partners. The efficiency of business processes in the global market hinges on the knowledge, abilities, skills, and acquired intercultural competencies of managers, who today are considered the most valuable asset and the most important source of competitive advantage and sustainable competitiveness of modern organizations.

In this context, the primary challenges of contemporary management are achieving and maintaining competitiveness and taking responsibility for global engagement in developing the necessary knowledge and skills essential for professional performance and business success in a culturally pluralistic global market. Effective management in such an environment necessitates a deep understanding of intercultural management, which addresses the interactions and relationships between members of different cultures, facilitating effective communication aimed at successful cooperation and business achievement on the international stage.

Managers must develop new perspectives on intercultural education and training to effectively manage intercultural relations, which is considered one of the most significant intercultural challenges in global business. The rapid advancement of information and communication technologies has somewhat simplified the control systems, yet managerial practices still differ widely due to cultural differences. This variation underscores the conclusion that no universally applicable managerial theories, systems, principles, or practices exist.

The modern global market is marked by the necessity for organizations to adapt continuously to the dynamic conditions and the diverse cultural backgrounds of their workforce. Managers must be equipped with intercultural competencies that enable them to navigate and lead effectively in such a multifaceted environment. This includes understanding and respecting cultural differences, adapting leadership styles to fit different cultural contexts, and fostering an inclusive workplace culture that leverages diversity as a competitive advantage.

The evolving nature of global business also demands that managers are proficient in managing human resources across different cultural settings. This involves recruiting, retaining, and developing a culturally diverse workforce, managing cross-cultural teams, and ensuring that all employees feel valued and included. Multinational companies often invest in specialized training programs for employees and managers assigned to international tasks, which aim to enhance their intercultural skills and prepare them for the challenges of working in different cultural environments.

Moreover, the control function in international business is particularly challenging due to the need to manage geographically dispersed units operating in various cultural environments. This requires an understanding of the different levels of control required in different countries and the ability to compare performance across units that may operate in different time zones and use different currencies. Despite the advancements in technology that facilitate control, cultural differences still present significant challenges that managers must navigate.

In conclusion, successful global management requires a deep understanding of cultural differences, a willingness to adapt and learn continuously, and the ability to lead diverse teams effectively. Managers must embrace the complexities of the international environment and leverage cultural diversity as a strength to achieve business success. The development of intercultural management as a specialized field will continue to be crucial in addressing these challenges and ensuring that managers are equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary to thrive in the global market. By fostering an inclusive and adaptive organizational culture, managers can create a competitive edge that drives sustainable success in the ever-evolving global business landscape.

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ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF SUSTAINABILITY IN AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

Over the next 40 years, a drastic increase in the world's population is expected, from 6.7 billion in 2009 to 9.2 billion by 2050. This demographic growth will be accompanied by economic development, leading to an increased demand for meat, dairy products, fruits, and vegetables (Halliday et al., 2009). Consequently, there will be growing pressure to produce sufficient quantities of food. Current assumptions suggest that food production will need to double by 2050, utilizing existing and likely diminished resources due to irresponsible use.

A plausible solution to this issue involves introducing the concept of sustainable agricultural production or sustainable land management. This implies that agriculture must be sustainable on a global and local level.

KEY WORDS: sustainability, management of agriculture, efficiency

ABSTRAKT

In den nächsten 40 Jahren wird mit einem drastischen Anstieg der Weltbevölkerung gerechnet, von 6,7 Milliarden im Jahr 2009 auf 9,2 Milliarden im Jahr 2050. Dieses Bevölkerungswachstum wird mit einer wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung einhergehen, die zu einer erhöhten Nachfrage nach Fleisch, Milchprodukten, Obst und Gemüse führt (Halliday et al., 2009). Folglich wird der Druck, ausreichende Mengen an Lebensmitteln zu produzieren, zunehmen. Aktuelle Annahmen gehen davon aus, dass sich die Nahrungsmittelproduktion bis 2050 verdoppeln muss, wobei die vorhandenen und wahrscheinlich durch unverantwortliche Nutzung geschrumpften Ressourcen genutzt werden müssen.

Eine plausible Lösung für dieses Problem ist die Einführung des Konzepts der nachhaltigen landwirtschaftlichen Produktion oder der nachhaltigen Landbewirtschaftung. Dies bedeutet, dass die Landwirtschaft auf globaler und lokaler Ebene nachhaltig sein muss.

STICHWORTE: Nachhaltigkeit, Bewirtschaftung der Landwirtschaft, Effizienz

RÉSUMÉ

Au cours des 40 prochaines années, une augmentation drastique de la population mondiale est attendue, passant de 6,7 milliards en 2009 à 9,2 milliards en 2050. Cette croissance démographique s'accompagnera d'un développement économique qui entraînera une augmentation de la demande de viande, de produits laitiers, de fruits et de légumes (Halliday et al., 2009). Par conséquent, la pression pour produire des quantités suffisantes de nourriture sera de plus en plus forte. Les hypothèses actuelles suggèrent que la production alimentaire devra doubler d'ici 2050, en utilisant les ressources existantes et probablement diminuées en raison d'une utilisation irresponsable.

Une solution plausible à ce problème consiste à introduire le concept de production agricole durable ou de gestion durable des terres. Cela implique que l'agriculture doit être durable au niveau mondial et local.

MOTS CLÉS: durabilité, gestion de l'agriculture, efficacité

INTRODUCTION

Over the next 40 years, a drastic increase in the world's population is expected, from 6.7 billion in 2009 to 9.2 billion by 2050. This demographic growth will be accompanied by economic development, leading to an increased demand for meat, dairy products, fruits, and vegetables (Halliday et al., 2009). Consequently, there will be growing pressure to produce sufficient quantities of food. Current assumptions suggest that food production will need to double by 2050, utilizing existing and likely diminished resources due to irresponsible use.

A plausible solution to this issue involves introducing the concept of sustainable agricultural production or sustainable land management. This implies that agriculture must be sustainable on a global and local level.

The concept of sustainability is based on resource constraints, environmental impact, economic viability, biodiversity, and social justice (Dumanski et al., 1991; Harmsen and Kelly, 1992). According to Smyth et al. (1993), sustainability is essential whenever there are limitations in agricultural production. The first limitation is resources, namely land for food production. Globally, the total land area (excluding ice-covered areas) is approximately 13.4 million square kilometers. Only 24% or 3.2 million square kilometers are potentially cultivable land. Of this, 1.3 million square kilometers (40%) are categorized as highly productive soils, while the remaining 60% consists of low-productivity areas.

The second limitation is the size of the human population, which increases by about 90 million people annually. This necessitates the inevitable expansion of agricultural areas, including less fertile resources such as pastures and forests. Statistical data shows that in the last 300 years, arable land has increased by about 12 million square kilometers, but simultaneously, around 6 million square kilometers of forests and 1.6 million square kilometers of wetlands have been lost. According to WRI estimates (1992), approximately 17 million hectares of tropical forests are cleared annually (0.9%). Such expansion of arable land directly contributes to increased CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere and the greenhouse effect.

The third constraint relates to the depletion of the biological potential of land resources due to advanced degradation processes. Smyth et al. (1993) emphasize that approximately 1.2 billion hectares of agricultural and forest lands are affected by moderate (75%) to severe soil degradation (25%). An additional 750 million hectares are under mild degradation. Causes of degradation include inappropriate agrotechnical practices in food production, deforestation, and various forms of industrial pollution. The secondary effect of soil degradation often manifests locally through surface and groundwater pollution, salinization, alkalization, eutrophication, and more.

The concept of sustainable land management can be defined as the utilization of land resources (soil, water, animals, plants) for food production that satisfies basic human needs, ensures the long-term productive potential of the soil, and maintains environmental functions. Sustainable land management is the foundation of sustainable agriculture and part of a strategy for sustainable development and poverty alleviation (Alemu, 2016). It involves cultivation practices, socio-economic policies, and activities that integrate socio-economic principles with environmental care, meeting the following conditions simultaneously:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The contribution of agriculture to sustainable development is evident through the territorial dynamics of rural and peri-urban areas. The EU Common Agricultural Policy (EU CAP) has initiated regional development programs using the LEADER approach in European countries (Tomić et al., 2009).

European Union members, like other developed countries, have been able to lead in implementing the multifunctional role of agriculture. In the early 1990s, multifunctional agriculture emerged as a European model capable of "maintaining villages, preserving nature, and making a crucial contribution to the vitality of rural life" (EC, 1997). Such agriculture must respond to consumer demands for food quality and safety, environmental protection, and animal welfare.

Nevertheless, Hajduković and Radić Lakoš (2008) highlight the increasing awareness in the human population of various ecological factors influencing the quality of life, intensifying pressure on authorities to ensure environmental protection. They also state that, in sustainable agriculture, the most crucial resource for a farm or family farm is the soil, which must not be degraded in any way.

In line with this, Batelja Lodeta et al. (2011) write that sustainable agriculture is food production capable of environmentally and economically sustaining itself over an extended period. This particularly pertains to soil, which in sustainable agriculture must consistently maintain an approximate level of fertility. It is production that occurs at the expense of future generations. In other words, sustainable agriculture governs how the soil and other natural riches are not only inherited from our fathers but also borrowed from our sons.

In the macroeconomic discourse, certain economic sustainability criteria are frequently discussed, such as the rate of production and income growth, effectiveness, efficiency, innovativeness, competitiveness, and public debt. While criteria like inflation, unemployment rate, and trade imbalances hold political significance, they are seldom framed within the sustainability context. Traditional metrics like aggregated demand, consumption levels, and savings rates receive less attention in contemporary debates. Although the economic literature explores the environmental, social, and occasionally institutional sustainability of economic systems, scant information exists on the economic sustainability of the economy, and criteria for economic sustainability in other dimensions remain underdeveloped (Spangenberg 2005).

Parameterizing achievements in sustainable agriculture proves more intricate than in conventional agriculture, which typically prioritizes intensification and quantifiable economic criteria like efficiency, profit, or profitability (Baum 2003). Recent endeavors to gauge progress towards sustainable development have targeted specific issues such as climate change or the environmental and social impacts of sectors like agriculture, energy, and transport. Nevertheless, measuring sustainable development at an aggregate level necessitates integrating indicators of economic, environmental, and social changes. One approach to achieving this involves extending the National Accounts to encompass environmental changes and environment-related transactions. Similar extensions to the social area could link accounts measuring employment, human capital, and income distribution among socio-economic groups (OECD 2001).

The OECD is actively developing various indicators: resource indicators to measure levels and changes in economic, environmental, and social assets, and outcome indicators covering the quantity and quality of development, including income distribution, health, and environmental quality. Initial synthetic indices of sustainability, developed by the UN Commission on Sustainable Development and currently under evaluation, face the challenge of encompassing all aspects of sustainable development in a single index. Most suggested social development indices fail to consider income differences, simplifying the reality they aim to represent (Indicators 2001).

For agriculture, the OECD is developing agri-environmental indicators (AEIs) within a framework addressing the linkages between causes, effects, and actions in agriculture's environmental impacts. These include indicators for nutrient, pesticide, and water use, as well as impacts on soil and

water quality, land conservation, biodiversity, habitats, and climate change (OECD 2001). Commonly used indices in international and national statistics include average fertilizer use, pollution emissions, quality of natural resources, organic cultivation area, number of eco-farms, and state expenditure on environmental programs.

Income, encompassing environmental, economic, social, and institutional impacts, is a fundamental category for assessing agriculture's economic development. This involves measuring added value in the national economy, gross and net incomes, farm incomes, and farmers' family incomes. Evaluating sustainable development has both macroeconomic and microeconomic dimensions, requiring various indices to build synthetic sustainability indices. Loss calculations consider private, social, environmental, and institutional costs (Income 1985).

Income inequality, an aspect of economic sustainability, is studied in terms of income distribution theory, considering vertical and horizontal equity in tax policy and equal pay in wage policy. Income disparities reflect differences in earning opportunities and capital resources among regions and countries, often analyzed using statistical methods like the Lorenz Curve, Florence Coefficient, Pearson Coefficient, and Gini Coefficient, as well as the Sen Index (Black 2008). For farming households, income is measured by disposable income and farming income, with comparative analyses requiring representative data.

To summarize, evaluating economic sustainability involves examining income in the context of professional or social groups, with spatial comparisons between urban and rural areas. This research also necessitates quantifying environmental effects and considering regional economic and environmental differences (Leszczy ska 2007).

Economics of Sustainable Agriculture. A significant step in the development of economic theory regarding sustainability in agriculture began in the 20th century, when awareness of resource depletion and potential limits to economic growth became prominent. Disregarding the input-output relationship, that is, the use of natural resources to produce goods in a way that leads to waste of resources and energy, results in inefficient production development. Through social and ecological activities, there is a confrontation between economics and sustainability.

Some authors believe that due to today's global economic situation, this type of sustainable agriculture has multiple advantages. In recent years, the unemployment rate in Kosovo has been high, with the largest share of total unemployment found in rural areas. It is believed that ecological production will increase the need for employment more than conventional agriculture. The sustainable development strategy has been a political direction that existed only as a written document and was not realized in practice. Another reason for ecological agriculture is that there is an increasing emphasis on ecological products through the purchase of food products.

Economic growth can only occur if it is separated from environmental degradation. Considering that production resources are limited, human needs as a whole are not satisfied. To meet human needs and desires to that extent, producers must strive for innovation, improvement in the quality, and quantity of available resources.

The usual division of fundamental production factors includes means of work, objects of work, and human labor. Means of work are used in multiple work processes and are gradually consumed. In production activities, this includes various tools, machines, and buildings. Objects of work are entirely consumed through a single work process. This includes human labor, encompassing both mental and physical efforts.

Economic growth undergoes constant changes. These changes cause differences in the economic structure, driven by the actions of labor and capital that enter and exit the economic sector in various ways. Over the years, this has led to changes in traditional small farms and enterprises. Through economic growth, the following dimensions develop:

- a. Economic dimension: This economic growth creates material wealth and better living conditions,
- b. Social dimension: Social development influences all spheres of life, including education, healthcare, housing, and employment,
- c. Political dimension: It is believed that through the development of politics, human rights, democracy, and political freedom are established,
- d. Cultural dimension: Individuals create their own identity and personality, encouraging creativity.

The ultimate goal of these dimensions is to improve the well-being of the population. However, to achieve such conditions, the participation of all segments of economic development is necessary.

Enterprises and Sustainable Development. Enterprises are one of the key components of the community that must continuously strive for modern techniques, technologies, and knowledge. Today, companies increasingly aim towards sustainable development processes to minimize environmental pollution, comply with regulations, fulfill social responsibilities, and enhance their innovation and competitiveness in the market. Environmental protection within a company must be planned and initiated well in advance and correctly incorporated into the company's work and development programs.

When companies invest in a project, it is crucial to conduct analytical studies that demonstrate the impact of the investment on the environment. This analysis shows how justified the investment is.

In this area, we encounter the concept of the "quality system." Considering the economic and ecological management of all processes, an environmental management system is developed. In this system, overall quality is very important. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) issues, publishes, and prescribes various standards that later become laws. These standards ensure the safety, reliability, and high quality of products and services.

The State and Sustainable Development. Laws regulate incentive systems such as ecological fees, guarantees, refundable, and other compensations. When it comes to financing environmental protection, there are environmental protection funds. These funds are now one of the essential parts of the economy. They change economic relationships, decentralize state functions, and develop new financing system methods.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) is an international economic organization that aims for goals such as supporting sustainable development, increasing employment, raising living standards, and promoting global trade growth. The main objective of the organization is to bring together countries that support sustainable economic growth within a market economy.

Cost Management for Sustainable Development. Environmental accounting is a concept encountered when discussing accounting and the environment together. This concept adapts accounting to new requirements. The scope of this term ranges from the lowest level of eco-accounting or so-called green accounting. Each of these different levels requires sufficient data and information to create an eco-balance sheet.

Green accounting is a part of modern accounting that provides the information representing management's responsibility for undertaken eco-actions, which may have been more or less successful or not undertaken at all. In this case, accounting influences all parts, starting from management. The aim is to improve environmental relations while simultaneously financially supporting this sector. Investing in new technologies is a key part of every enterprise, alongside optimizing costs and environmental impact.

The offering must attract target groups by ensuring a favorable product-to-value ratio. The green-conscious consumer is a new group representing a new destination and offer within the business system through an eco-image.

One of the concepts encountered in the development of this system is the eco-balance sheet. This new economic category emphasizes environmental protection issues and its development. Encouraging management to undertake positive eco-actions depends on knowing the environmental costs, preparing, and presenting information, which determines the success of implementation. Environmental accounting can be found as a separate part of financial and managerial accounting.

Environmental costs arise from natural activities. They affect the product range, choice of technique, technology, and technological processes. This type of cost encourages sustainable development and prioritizes reducing negative environmental impacts while ensuring profitable operations. Environmental accounting reports must contain reliable information according to the principles of:

- Timely recognition of environmental costs,
- Inclusion and classification,
- Recording in accounting records and business books.

By classifying and recording relevant accounting information in records and business books, appropriate cost classification is achieved, and through recording, additional business adjustments are possible.

Cost-Benefit Analysis. According to the author Rajković, who elaborated on Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) in his work, he concluded that it is a methodological procedure for making correct decisions when implementing any project. The concept emerged in the 1930s in economic theory as a way to evaluate different projects. The Italian economist Vilfredo Pareto best defined the essence of Cost-Benefit Analysis, from which the term Pareto improvement is derived. His premise is that in today's modern world, it is impossible to implement a project without causing some harm to society. Understanding the concept of Pareto improvement led other economists to introduce the term Potential Pareto improvement. This concept explains that any project worth investing in has benefits greater than the costs incurred.

In the context of sustainable development, Pareto improvement can be described as the type of benefits and costs that impact the broader community and future generations. CBA considers the total societal effects of a project, making it an objective analysis. A temporary economic activity or permanent project can disrupt ecological stability, biodiversity, and impact the environment. The analysis can assess the societal readiness to bear the costs and environmental damage in relation to the benefits for society. Costs must be evaluated for all alternatives, including those that cannot be expressed monetarily. The willingness to accept environmental damage relates to:

- Ecosystem;
- Human Health;
- Economy;
- Society.

According to the CBA script in environmental impact assessment, there are two main interpretations of the analysis:

- Determining measurable environmental benefits and costs expressed in monetary units.
- Determining immeasurable environmental costs and benefits through scales comparing the value of impacts.

Environmental costs in some variants are generally assessed as external costs and do not burden the business. By determining multiple variants of an environmental intervention, it is necessary to evaluate the impact of the benefits and costs through analysis. This results in external costs.

According to Pareto's principle, internal costs should also be included in the analysis. Including internal costs provides more options for choosing alternatives as it reduces both external and internal costs. Internal costs are expressed through environmental compensation, various contributions for the use or protection of the environment.

When making correct decisions, it is necessary to connect measurable and immeasurable values. CBA is conducted before initiating any intervention. Table 3 lists the phases through which the analysis must go to obtain relevant information.

Table 1. Determining the Need for Cost-Benefit Analysis. Source: own interpretation.

Procedure	Explanation
Defining the problem	It is necessary to clearly define and document the problem.
Reviewing current documentation	If the documentation is not clearly defined and updated, supplementation is required.
Evaluating the work process	The evaluation can be made by answering questions: Do we need an analysis? Is progress necessary?
Defining requirements for a new process	It is necessary to define requirements at a general level. They must also be reliable and secure.
Determining measures for assessment	Identifying indicators and evaluating the process, as well as determining how to collect and store data.

After clearly defined problems and goals, further undertakings are determined. It is important to have one person who will assemble a team of experts and be responsible for monitoring and conducting the analysis. The following table shows the required steps.

Table 2. Process of Conducting a Cost-Benefit Analysis. Source: own interpretation.

Step	Explanation
Defining goals	Must include project goals and other information for management.
Documenting the current process	Define what society gains from the process/project, its current benefits, possibilities, and current costs (equipment, services, procurement, staff).
Evaluating future interventions	Determine and evaluate the life cycle (current environmental state) and demand cycle (society's need for the intervention).
Collecting cost data	Historical data, current costs, market research, analytical estimates, special environmental studies.
Selecting at least three alternatives	It is customary to include at least three alternatives.
Documenting assumptions	Numerous assumptions arise; they need to be documented and justified based on data.
Estimating costs	Direct and indirect costs, as well as total annual costs, are considered.
Estimating benefits	Define benefits, which are assessed based on actual or approximate value (visible and invisible benefits).

Step	Explanation
Discounting costs and benefits	Convert costs and benefits into a common unit of measurement.
Evaluating alternatives	Evaluate when all values are monetary, and when benefits are not expressed monetarily.
Conducting sensitivity analysis	Good parameters are those significant cost factors with a wide or narrow range of values.

It is easiest to carry out a quality analysis and cover all aspects through these phases comes to the conclusion of how much is gained and how much is lost by a certain project. Cost-benefit analysis is an instrument that quantifies all financial and economic losses on the one hand, while on the other hand he realizes the expected income and benefit of a venture.

CONCLUSION

One of the key requirements of sustainable development is finding a solution to achieve a balance between economic development and the rational utilization of economic resources. It is necessary to use natural resources in a way that does not jeopardize them for the future. The sustainability rule dictates that resources should not be consumed at a faster rate than they can be replenished. Over the years, there have been changes in people's understanding of environmental needs. The Green Revolution endangered agricultural production, leading to the realization of the need for environmental protection and sustainable agriculture. Agenda 21 was the first document to set sustainability standards, emphasizing the need for local action above all.

The implementation of the Nitrates Directive aims to achieve a stable and balanced ecosystem by controlling the excessive input of nitrates into the soil, with the goal of protecting water and soil. The fundamental pillars of sustainable development are the economy, the environment, and society. Organic or ecological agriculture, which is well-known worldwide, is still relatively underrepresented in our country. It is based on economically and socially acceptable food production practices, aligned with laws and regulations on the use of permitted plant protection products and acceptable mineral fertilizers.

Economic growth and development cannot be considered without including economic aspects. Significant development of economic theory in the context of sustainability began in the 20th century. Developing the economy of sustainable development requires additional education in ecology, sustainability, and quality and efficient management. The aspiration of economic development lies in innovations, new techniques, and technologies to strengthen the economy.

A key part of economic development is enterprises, which must analyze the environmental impact of every investment. The state, through its laws and regulations, determines incentive measures such as ecological fees, guarantees, and refundable and other compensations. The costs associated with environmental protection and sustainable business practices are encompassed by green accounting and included in the eco-balance. Cost-benefit analysis is a method for making correct decisions when implementing a project. It considers the overall social effects of the project and assesses the society's willingness to accept environmental damage in light of its social benefits.

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ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION IN AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the paper is to present innovation entrepreneurship in agriculture as practiced on modern farms. Modern agricultural enterprises utilize innovations and information communication technology in their work, all aimed at achieving maximum profit.

In addition to product and service innovation, the paper defines and emphasizes the importance of innovating business models. A business model is the way a company operates in the market, making it recognizable within it. The importance of innovating business models is illustrated through examples of companies that have successfully innovated their business models and the results that innovation has had on their operations and their position in the global market. The paper presents three types of business model innovation: Blue Ocean Strategy, Business Model Canvas, and WOIS.

KEY WORDS: innovation management, agricultural management, entrepreneurial skills

ABSTRAKT

Ziel dieses Beitrags ist es, das Innovationsunternehmertum in der Landwirtschaft darzustellen, wie es in modernen landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben praktiziert wird. Moderne landwirtschaftliche Unternehmen setzen bei ihrer Arbeit Innovationen und Informations- und Kommunikationstechnologien ein, die alle auf die Erzielung maximaler Gewinne abzielen.

Neben der Produkt- und Dienstleistungsinnovation wird in diesem Beitrag die Bedeutung der Innovation von Geschäftsmodellen definiert und hervorgehoben. Ein Geschäftsmodell ist die Art und Weise, wie ein Unternehmen auf dem Markt agiert, und macht es auf dem Markt erkennbar. Die Bedeutung innovativer Geschäftsmodelle wird anhand von Beispielen von Unternehmen veranschaulicht, die ihre Geschäftsmodelle erfolgreich erneuert haben, sowie anhand der Auswirkungen, die diese Innovation auf ihre Geschäftstätigkeit und ihre Position auf dem Weltmarkt hatte. In dem Papier werden drei Arten von Geschäftsmodellinnovationen vorgestellt: Blue Ocean Strategy, Business Model Canvas und WOIS.

STICHWORTE: Innovationsmanagement, Agrarmanagement, unternehmerische Fähigkeiten

RÉSUMÉ

L'objectif de ce document est de présenter l'esprit d'entreprise en matière d'innovation dans l'agriculture, tel qu'il est pratiqué dans les exploitations agricoles modernes. Les entreprises agricoles modernes utilisent les innovations et les technologies de l'information et de la communication dans leur travail, dans le but d'atteindre un profit maximal. Outre l'innovation en matière de produits et de services, le document définit et souligne l'importance de l'innovation en matière de modèles d'entreprise. Un modèle d'entreprise est la manière dont une société opère sur le marché, ce qui la rend reconnaissable. L'importance de l'innovation des modèles d'entreprise est illustrée par des exemples d'entreprises qui ont réussi à innover leurs modèles d'entreprise et les résultats que l'innovation a eus sur leurs opérations et leur position sur le marché mondial. Le document présente trois types d'innovation en matière de modèles d'entreprise: Stratégie Océan Bleu, Business Model Canvas, et WOIS.

MOTS CLÉS: gestion de l'innovation, gestion agricole, compétences entrepreneuriales

INTRODUCTION

There are numerous definitions of entrepreneurship in the literature, resulting from different perspectives on entrepreneurship throughout history, and some of them are mentioned in the paper. The importance of entrepreneurship is reflected in its role as a driver of change and development, and today, most countries recognize its significance for the growth of their national economies. Contemporary definitions of entrepreneurship emphasize the strong connection between innovation and entrepreneurship.

The aim of the paper is to present innovation entrepreneurship in agriculture as practiced on modern farms. Modern agricultural enterprises utilize innovations and information communication technology in their work, all aimed at achieving maximum profit.

In addition to product and service innovation, the paper defines and emphasizes the importance of innovating business models. A business model is the way a company operates in the market, making it recognizable within it. The importance of innovating business models is illustrated through examples of companies that have successfully innovated their business models and the results that innovation has had on their operations and their position in the global market. The paper presents three types of business model innovation: Blue Ocean Strategy, Business Model Canvas, and WOIS.

Educational institutions can indirectly promote entrepreneurship by introducing programs that develop entrepreneurial thinking and familiarize young people with processes present in entrepreneurship. The importance of knowledge and education is also emphasized as the foundation for better understanding and utilization of modern technologies and business practices, which are integral parts of modern agricultural production.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought new challenges for the entire world, including entrepreneurship. On the other hand, it can be seen as an incentive for many companies to start innovating their business models and thus ensure their survival in the market.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneur. There are various definitions of entrepreneurship that stem from different historical periods in which people operated. It has evolved throughout history, thereby changing its meaning and definition.

In addition to economic theorists, the concept of entrepreneurship has been explored by experts from other social sciences, resulting in a variety of perspectives on entrepreneurship and a large number of definitions. Some approach entrepreneurship from an economic standpoint, others from a psychological perspective, and still others from an organizational standpoint. Definitions of entrepreneurship generally differ in terms of the importance they attribute to specific entrepreneurial characteristics or activities (www.efos.unios.hr-efos3).

Entrepreneurship can be defined as the ability to initiate and undertake certain activities aimed at achieving a predetermined goal, while being prepared to combat obstacles, uncertainty of outcomes, and risk (Kružić, 2007.).

Furthermore, entrepreneurship can be viewed as the combination of production factors and the enhancement of existing potentials, a creative process involving the transformation of invention into innovation, self-employment and the establishment of one's own business, introducing creative changes for the purpose of societal transformation and renewal, the emergence and development of small businesses, the materialization of creative products, taking on business risk, identifying new opportunities, and specific attitudes and behaviors (Kružić, 2007.).

According to Škrtić and Mikić (2011.), entrepreneurship is the process of creating value by combining and integrating resources in a unique way to seize an opportunity. These are all activities

undertaken by entrepreneurs related to expanding into new markets, investing and combining necessary inputs, creating new products, new technologies, and new consumers.

According to Škrtić (2006.), entrepreneurship is a set of organizational, innovative, and managerial capabilities that create new value by exploiting opportunities and available resources.

The forms of entrepreneurship are (Turuk, n.d.):

Traditional entrepreneurship - refers to small and medium-sized enterprises that engage in innovative activities, take risks, organize to achieve predetermined goals, and take all necessary actions to achieve profits,

Corporate entrepreneurship - business within large organizations that require skills to achieve excellent business results and maintain competitiveness in the market,

Social entrepreneurship - a form of business with the main goal of creating positive social and environmental impact. The profit generated is reinvested in community investment or programs that improve living conditions, environmental preservation, and sustainable development.

Kolaković (2006.) emphasizes the creation of new value as the main goal of entrepreneurship, which arises from the establishment of new companies, innovation development, employment creation, new product creation, expansion into new markets, and the introduction of new technologies.

The most common advantages of entering entrepreneurship include: achieving unlimited profits, control over one's own destiny, and recognition in society, creativity, and the ability to work on things one loves. Disadvantages of entering entrepreneurship include: income uncertainty, the risk of losing invested capital, hard work and undefined working hours, high levels of stress, unlimited responsibility, low quality of life, and discouragement (Šipić and Najdanović, 2012.).

The state plays a very important role in promoting entrepreneurship as it establishes laws and regulates the financial market, sets framework rates for long-term economic growth, and influences the allocation of resources aimed at increasing the productivity of economic activities (Šipić and Najdanović, 2012.).

The importance of contemporary entrepreneurship is evident in its ubiquity in politics, economics, media, and various sciences (economics, law, sociology). Throughout the history of civilization, entrepreneurship has been a driver of change and development, and it is expected that this century will be the century of great entrepreneurship expansion (Kružić, 2007.).

An entrepreneur is a person characterized by business acumen and leadership ability, readiness to take on the risk of managing a company based on innovation and continuous development, as well as a good understanding of business and people. They find new products and services to introduce into their business, thus driving the economy (Škrtić and Mikić, 2011.). An entrepreneur invests their own resources in a particular economic activity and makes business decisions, organizes, supervises, and manages all business processes and bears all business risks (Škrtić, 2006.). Additionally, an entrepreneur can be defined through the activities they undertake. They are innovators and creators who identify and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities, turn them into entrepreneurial ideas, organize the realization of those ideas, and, through the investment of their time, energy, and money, create additional value. They take on the risk to realize the idea and ultimately reap financial rewards for their efforts (www.efos.unios.hr-efos3).

Key characteristics of a successful entrepreneur include responsibility, risk-taking readiness, quick response, belief in oneself and one's ability to succeed, high energy levels, organization, and certainly a desire for success above money. It is very important for a successful entrepreneur to know how to handle themselves in times of crisis in business and consider all possible solutions calmly and rationally (Šipić and Najdanović, 2012.). A good and successful entrepreneur can be created through

education and scientific education, and entrepreneurship can then be discussed as a science and profession (Kružić, 2007.).

An entrepreneur plays a very important role in society as their actions motivate people around them, create business opportunities and space for other members of society through innovation, establish businesses and create new jobs, and contribute to the economic growth of the national economy. The concept of entrepreneurship is generally associated with small businesses because entrepreneurs, in order to realize their entrepreneurial ideas, establish new small businesses, which in many cases grow into large organizations. As the company grows, the role of the founding entrepreneur changes. They begin to engage in operational tasks and the allocation of available resources for better achievement of business goals, thereby diminishing their creativity and ability to recognize market opportunities, and the entrepreneur becomes a manager. To avoid this, many entrepreneurs hire managers who take over the management of the company, while they dedicate their time and energy to seeking new market opportunities (www.efos.unios.hr-efos3).

Innovation. Innovation is not a new phenomenon. It's hard to imagine a world without cars, airplanes, televisions, and so on. Despite its importance, innovation was not a focus of economic theorists for a long time, as they mainly dealt with topics such as capital and market functioning. However, in recent years, this trend has changed, and the number of social science publications on the topic of innovation has increased much faster than the total number of such publications. This indicates the importance that innovation assumes in today's global market (Fagerberg, 2003.).

Innovation is a realized idea that improves or introduces a new product or service or business process. Innovation must prove its value in the market (Radman, 2011.).

There are two main types of innovations according to their subject (OECD, 2018.):

- Product innovations,
- Process innovations.

Product innovation is a new or improved product or service that significantly differs from the company's previous products or services and is introduced to the market. Process innovation is a new or improved business process for one or more business functions that significantly differs from the company's previous business processes and has been implemented by the company (OECD, 2018.).

According to the degree of novelty, we distinguish between incremental and radical innovations. Incremental innovations represent continuous improvements to a product, process, or service (e.g., online banking, LED televisions). They make companies more competitive. Radical innovations involve replacing products with completely new forms of products, processes, or services (Galović, 2016.).

Innovativeness is the ability to do something in a new way. In business, this means improvement that brings about positive changes and increases the value of work. Innovation is the result of an innovative process (Radman, 2011.).

Innovation is often equated with the terms creativity and invention, but there is a difference in the meanings of these terms. Creativity precedes innovativeness and represents the effort to find an original solution to a problem or create something new in a new way. Creativity does not concern whether these ideas will be useful now or in the future but is solely focused on creating something new (Huljenić, 2021.). Creativity is the generation of new ideas, and innovation is the value they can generate. Being creative is not the same as being innovative, and innovation is essentially applied creativity (Dabić and Potočan, 2012.). Invention precedes innovation and denotes the idea or description for a new product or process that could become usable, while innovation is a proven useful novelty (Galović, 2016.). While invention is the first occurrence of an idea for a new product or procedure, innovation is the first commercialization of the idea. Sometimes invention and innovation are linked, and it is difficult to distinguish between them, but in most cases, there is a time gap between

invention and innovation. Inventions can be carried out anywhere (labs, universities), while innovations mainly occur in companies in the commercial sphere. For an invention to become an innovation, it is necessary to combine different knowledge, abilities, skills, and resources (Fagerberg, 2003.). Innovation is not an invention, but every invention is an innovation (Nikolić, 2018.).

The first economic revolution promoted the worker as the bearer, the second favored the expert, and the third IT experts as promoters of the development of microprocessor electronics and telematics. The new phase in development, the fourth technological revolution (symbolized by the fusion of atoms, artificial intelligence, artificial raw materials, biochips, etc.), focuses on innovators and large investments that will open up new areas of human activity. The 21st century is the century of knowledge, information, development, and innovative ideas, and competition in the market will be based on advanced technologies (Dabić and Potočan, 2012.).

Innovative Entrepreneurship in Agriculture. Given the importance of agriculture as an activity that feeds the population, produces raw materials for the processing industry, and connects services (tourism), entrepreneurship in agriculture is of particular importance because it drives the entire economy. Practicing entrepreneurship in agriculture results in the development of new products with new technologies and technical solutions, expanding the consumer network, and opening up new markets (Deže et al., 2008.). In modern economic conditions, family farms are the drivers of family farming development. In every economy, including agriculture, the entrepreneur plays an important role in development. European Union guidelines for agricultural development introduce the concept of agricultural entrepreneurship, which deals with primary production, processing, or placing agricultural products on the market (Deže, 2016.).

Technological, informational, and communication development opens up numerous new opportunities for agricultural development. Business entities involved in agriculture (companies and family farms) must operate in line with upcoming changes and integrate them into their operations to develop their businesses (Deže et al., 2008.). It is crucial to recognize and successfully manage the changes that occur in the market in which one operates or intends to operate. Introducing new technologies in agriculture leads to shortened production times and lower prices for the final product (Deže et al., 2008.).

Modern agricultural business entails encountering innovative techniques that require changes in business practices, new knowledge, and skills. This can cause dissatisfaction among traditional farmers who often resist any changes. However, this is contrary to the requirements of the modern market, which demands adaptable and dynamic economies. Support needs to be provided to such farmers to facilitate the adaptation and modernization of their businesses. Trends show the direction in which traditional agriculture needs to transition to modern methods because failure to adapt to changes leads to stagnation in the production and operations of agricultural farms (Deže et al., 2008.).

Global trends show a decline in mass production of goods and that business activities and production are increasingly based on recognizing consumer needs, i.e., market segmentation. By applying marketing concepts, agricultural farms can change their approach to the market or consumer. It is important to understand the needs, desires, and expectations of consumers and put the consumer at the center. Market research provides necessary information on which marketing objectives, programs, and strategies are based (Deže et al., 2008.).

Cooperative organization in agriculture is becoming increasingly prevalent among successful modern entrepreneurs. The advantages of cooperation include easier access to markets, knowledge, incentives, technology, streamlined operations, increased competitiveness, and higher profits (Deže et al., 2008.).

As agriculture is a strategic activity of every country, the state is involved in its financing by increasing the creditworthiness of agricultural farms through various measures and thus helping them

become attractive to commercial banks. State support systems for agricultural production and funds from European funds are essential sources of financing to achieve development, increase quality, and modernize agricultural production processes (Deže et al., 2008.).

Information and communication technology have a significant impact on modern agricultural production because they enable greater transparency. Customers can compare prices online and choose more favorable suppliers or market their products to markets that suit those (Deže et al., 2008.).

Education, knowledge, expertise, and entrepreneurial skills are the foundation for modern agricultural business.

Contemporary Management of Agricultural Farms. Management of agricultural farms is based on decisions regarding the utilization of resources aimed at achieving profitability in operations. Every successful business relies on quality management, and agriculture is no exception. Agricultural management encompasses defining economic and social goals, ensuring the continuous availability of resources, organizing them effectively, and exploring alternative business approaches (Hadelan & Franić, 2006).

In traditional agricultural production, decision-making is often based on the experiences of older farmers rather than modern business decision-making methods. The demands of modern agriculture are much higher than they were thirty years ago. Intense market competition necessitates that agricultural producers adopt new management approaches used by farmers in more developed economies. Today's farmers must pay more attention to business decision-making and the development of managerial skills than they did in the past (Hadelan & Franić, 2006).

Contemporary farmers face modern mechanization, adaptation to new cultivation methods, securing investment funds, selecting market alternatives, and greater business risk. These challenges can also present opportunities for modern farmers and their farm management (Hadelan & Franić, 2006).

Modern management of family agricultural farms, in the context of increased competition, is significantly more dynamic and requires a wide range of knowledge and skills. This includes gathering and storing necessary production data, information on diseases and pests that could jeopardize operations, and utilizing modern technology to maximize yields and produce high-quality products. Additionally, understanding financial statements and business performance indicators (profitability, liquidity, and business activity) is crucial (Hadelan & Franić, 2006).

Financial management emerges as a crucial element of agricultural management because agriculture relies on external sources of financing. Banks are generally reluctant to finance agricultural farms that cannot provide a financial overview of their operations and quality business plans demonstrating the creditworthiness of the farm. Managing agricultural farms requires knowledge and skills similar to those of managers in non-agricultural companies (Hadelan & Franić, 2006).

Information literacy is becoming increasingly important, especially in large commercial farms, where computers are used to process and analyze financial data, communicate with professional services, and settle obligations. Internet access enables better and timely information dissemination and the ability to check and compare market prices. All of the above indicates that agricultural policy must aim to develop managerial skills among farmers because effective management of agricultural farms is a factor that can influence competitiveness in the market (Hadelan & Franić, 2006).

Education as a Prerequisite for Innovative Agriculture. Innovative entrepreneurship in agriculture requires knowledge and expertise to effectively utilize innovations and modern technologies in farming operations. The education level of farmers plays a significant role as it provides the foundation for easier adoption of new agricultural technologies and innovations. Acceptance of innovations is influenced not only by education but also by the age of farmers. Older populations tend

to be more resistant and less receptive to modern technology, new cultivation methods, and new varieties because they are less inclined towards change and find it challenging to accept (Jež Rogelj et al., 2019).

According to Jež Rogelj et al. (2019), there is a positive correlation between the level of education of the population and GDP per capita. Similarly, there is a positive correlation between the proportion of highly educated population and the development index of counties in Croatia. Higher education levels among farmers also result in higher levels of agricultural development.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the introduction and acceptance of innovations in Croatian agriculture will progress slowly due to the unfavorable age structure of family farm operators in Croatia. Specifically, 38.7% of family farm operators are over 65 years old, and 5.96% have not completed primary school, while only 21.71% have completed only primary school, which is not good news for the survival and development of Croatian agriculture. Since younger and more educated farmers are more likely to accept innovations more easily and quickly, rural development programs encourage them to enter agriculture and take over farms from older farmers (Jež Rogelj et al., 2019).

Smart agriculture. In contemporary conditions, agriculture faces numerous challenges, including the production of an adequate quantity of safe food, business profitability, and minimizing negative environmental impact. Modern technologies are believed to have the potential to support the agricultural sector in overcoming global challenges. While modern technology has many positive effects, such as increased productivity, lower prices for consumers, and higher income for producers, it also faces criticism. Arguments against modern technology often revolve around ethical issues, the monopolistic position of certain companies, depletion of natural resources, accessibility of modern technologies to farmers in developed countries, and the widening gap between the rich and poor.

Science has introduced many new technologies into the agri-food sector, with some considered highly controversial in terms of their consequences. In conventional agriculture, there is intensive land use, resembling mass industrial production oriented towards maximizing profits. Terms such as intensive, industrial, and commercial agriculture are used synonymously for this type of agriculture, enabling higher production volume but being unsustainable in the long run due to negative environmental consequences (Nikolić and Gajinov, 2014).

One of the most controversial issues and a focal point of longstanding debates is genetically modified food. Genetically modified organisms (GMOs) are obtained through genetic engineering or recombinant DNA technology, which involves transferring functional genes to an organism to produce organisms with new traits. Some countries invoke ecological and agricultural policy goals, as well as socio-economic impact, rather than just proving that GM crops pose a health risk, to ban the cultivation of GM plants. The debate on the use of GMOs varies across multiple directions, including risks associated with incorporating GMOs into the food chain, economic-political reflections, ethical and technical issues, bringing food production and distribution under the control of a smaller number of companies, the emergence of monopolies, and questions about preserving national sovereignty and international food trade, among others. Critics emphasize that GMOs possess an entire genome altered in a way that does not occur in nature. While GMO proponents expect this technology to bring about many positive changes, critics express open fear of potential consequences of gene transfer from one organism to another. According to proponents, GMO food is crucial in the fight against hunger as GMOs are resistant to many pests and viruses, provide higher yields, have improved nutritional and other characteristics, all aimed at producing larger quantities of food. Conversely, critics consider GMO technology a real danger, threatening the environment and potentially creating "monstrous" organisms with unforeseen consequences. They view GMO food as insufficiently perfected and tested, highlighting the danger of tampering with the boundaries set by nature. Concerns about releasing GMOs into the environment relate to the possibility of GMOs crossing with

related species, negative impacts on biological diversity, and unpredictable consequences due to potential genetic modification instability. When the first GM food was introduced to the market, concerns arose about its inclusion in the food chain, among farmers and consumers, as well as among members of the scientific-expert community and in political circles. For scientists and the entire human population, GMOs pose a significant challenge that requires more extensive and transparent research. It is crucial for this technology to be more comprehensively and qualitatively controlled (Trkulja et al., 2008).

Sustainable agricultural development is now imperative due to the emergence and rapid spread of various controversial technologies. This demands modern education and lifelong learning, innovative approaches, increased investments in research and development of "clean" technologies, and the implementation of appropriate policies in this field. Sustainable agriculture is significant as it preserves land, water, and biodiversity, avoids environmental degradation, and is economically and socially acceptable, managing natural resources to meet the needs of current and future generations.

While the abundance of natural resources was once the predominant factor in development, the modern era of technology and increasing reliance on knowledge has relativized the natural factor. However, current energy problems, pollution, environmental degradation, and resource scarcity highlight the importance of natural resources for human populations, ensuring their survival and sustainable development (Đukić, 2014). In this context, organic farming promotes ecosystem conservation, biodiversity, and biological cycles, encouraging methods that largely exclude the use of off-farm inputs (FAO, 2017). Although organic farming represents a sustainable agriculture system based on high standards for natural resource use, it is limited or considered insufficiently profitable to supplant conventional land use (Nikolić and Gajinov, 2014). Unfortunately, agriculture based on the best ecological means is not always highly productive and economically successful, so it is often not prioritized in practice.

farming, emphasizing the more modern use of agricultural land, with a restrictive application of synthetic substances and a broader use of organic materials.

Figure 1. Precision agriculture is based on high technological capabilities, requiring (Gvozdenac, 2017):

Integrated crop production focuses on minimizing disruptions to agroecosystems, promoting natural mechanisms for disease and pest control. This approach requires careful selection and coordination of agronomic measures, taking into account the interests of producers and consumers, as well as environmental capacity. Integrated crop production supports the multifunctionality of agriculture, is applied holistically, requires continuous improvement of farmers' knowledge, maintains stability and balance in agro-ecosystems, and emphasizes soil fertility preservation and animal welfare, as well as good agricultural practices.

In practice, there is often the coexistence of different types of agricultural production. However, problems can arise in this case as well, as contamination processes may go unnoticed for a long time, and harmful effects may only manifest in later stages of the food chain. It is also challenging to establish causal relationships, such as the cause of damage related to the production of GM crops on adjacent plots, as many other external factors influence crops (Nikolić and Gajinov, 2014).

New technologies in agriculture, based on computer technology and integrated systems, offer numerous application possibilities and various benefits. The advent of information and communication technologies in agriculture, with satellite guidance for self-propelled agricultural machinery and automatic control in farming operations, has enabled the development of precision agriculture. This has become more commercially accessible for wider use, especially since the use of satellite navigation and related constellations (Luecke & Katz, 2003).

Global Positioning System (GPS): The GPS navigation system uses gathered information to precisely determine the position of agricultural machinery. This information helps determine the exact material requirements for a specific location rather than an average for the entire agricultural area.

Geographic Information System (GIS): GIS allows the collection, analysis, visualization, and storage of data from a specific location. It enables farmers to manage real-time field operations and plan future activities based on timely information obtained directly from cultivated areas. Implementation of such a complex system requires various prerequisites, including the existence of a digitized cadastral base, an updated real estate cadastre system, monitoring of relevant indicators for analytics, and appropriate technical, software, and personnel readiness (Manić et al., 2016).

Remote Sensing (RS): Remote sensing involves collecting data from a distance using handheld devices, sensors mounted on agricultural machinery, satellites, etc. The goal is to obtain precise information about relatively large areas. Geocoded measurement data are sent through communication channels to a central hub for analysis and interpretation. Sensors in the field or on machinery enable the integration of spatial and temporal data, precise irrigation, fertilization, and pesticide use, timely information, detection of parameter variabilities affecting yield during the season, better visibility and early detection of crop conditions, yield forecasting, plant development monitoring, simultaneous monitoring, etc.

Variable Rate Technology (VRT): The application of variable quantities involves adjusting input quantities to the conditions in the field. Software includes tools for planning and reporting, recording data on field conditions, soil preparation, spraying, fertilization amounts, seeding variations, plant population during planting, and weather conditions. The software can be installed on a PC, tablet, mobile phone, etc.

In precision agriculture, drones are used, ranging from lower-cost ones that farmers deploy themselves to more expensive devices with military-style equipment (equipped with infrared cameras, sensors, and other ground-controlled pilot technology). The use of drones in agriculture is considered a good platform for monitoring crop development, early detection of plant development disturbances, determining vegetation height, identifying irrigation needs, detecting diseases, pests, and soil erosion, terrain scanning, obtaining a detailed documented report on plot and crop conditions, checking machinery operation, assessing yields and resource savings, aerial surveillance, and unauthorized access detection.

While many consider commercial robot use to still be far from reality, much is already being automated on farms in developed countries (Figure 2). Robots are already being used for (New Scientist, 2012): milking cows (robots perform readings with lasers); livestock monitoring (unmanned aerial vehicles); crop inspection; weed recognition and elimination; fruit picking and counting; seeding (satellite-guided seeders that operate in all weather conditions); checking plant health; weed removal between crops using infrared sensors, etc. The use of electronics and computers involves sensors, microprocessors, agricultural software, etc. Drones and UAVs are increasingly used for crop monitoring, and experiments are conducted with robotic technology in livestock farming, crop mapping, yield monitoring, etc. Farmers in developed countries are already applying some of the technological possibilities of precision agriculture (Štefanek, 2014): intelligent tires that can quickly change pressure during operation without stopping; automatic tractor control during plowing, providing perfectly straight furrows and a perfect field appearance; on-land plowing with modern plows that use sensors to precisely determine the plowing depth; on-line fertilization - crop feeding based on plant needs and soil potentials, where sensors on the tractor or special carriers read the reflected signal from the plant, send it for processing to the computer, and then send information to the device about the amount of fertilizer to apply; modern inter-row cultivators for mechanical weed control, simultaneous crop feeding; yield mapping - yield maps show the heterogeneity of yields across production tables and the causes of yield reduction; 3-D scanning of plots in preparation for seeding; mobile robotized solar generators - remotely controlled automated devices for electricity generation; devices for scanning the presence of weeds to spray only parts of the plot where they are located; lasers for crop protection from pests, and more.

For more extensive use of robots in agribusiness, access to a wide range of technological possibilities is required, from new robotics and sensory technology applications to LED lighting in greenhouses. The introduction of new technologies requires significant financial resources, which is more realistic in developed countries as they have the capacity to provide greater support to economic entities and make the purchase of sophisticated equipment more accessible.

CONCLUSION

Leveraging innovation as a key factor for competitiveness and market success is the fundamental characteristic of innovative entrepreneurship. Besides innovating products and services, there is an increasing emphasis on innovating business models by which companies operate. Given the intense competition in the global market, saturated with products and services that are increasingly difficult to differentiate, along with the shorter lifespan of products, customers begin to lose interest and often base their purchasing decisions solely on price. Therefore, innovating business models should be embraced by more companies, including agricultural entities, to establish and secure their market position. An excellent business model can be decisive in determining whether a company will be successful or not. The current Covid-19 pandemic has demonstrated that businesses that managed to quickly revise their business models not only survived but also thrived.

Innovative entrepreneurship is the entrepreneurship of the 21st century, grounded in knowledge, technology, and information. The adoption of advanced technologies is imperative in innovative entrepreneurship, requiring a workforce that can harness technology to enhance productivity. This implies that educational institutions must implement programs that cultivate skilled labor capable of proactive and innovative thinking, ready to continually upgrade their knowledge to create new products and technologies.

The level of innovation depends on the business environment. Given that contemporary entrepreneurship is expected to address unemployment issues, it holds significant importance for all national economies. Therefore, governments and policies must ensure a favorable business environment conducive to fostering innovative entrepreneurship. Successful agriculture in the 21st century must embody all the characteristics of innovative entrepreneurship.

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GUIDELINES FOR IMPROVING STRATEGIC MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN AGRIBUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

The agrarian business in Bulgaria has potential for development by applying a marketing approach in its management. Agricultural production can be developed by satisfying the needs of the market. The supply of Bulgarian agricultural products faces many market challenges, which forces farmers to look for means to improve the market image of their products.

The purpose of the article is to determine guidelines for improving the management of Bulgarian agricultural holdings.

Implementation of strategic marketing activities by farmers can improve their economic performance based on better market performance. The correct implementation of these activities requires that they be considered as part of a systemic process that affects all elements of the production and marketing system. This requires that the management functions related to planning, execution and control of marketing activities are performed in the context of the market environment for each particular business.

KEY WORDS: process, system, marketing chain, analysis, marketing objectives

ABSTRAKT

Die Agrarwirtschaft in Bulgarien verfügt über ein Entwicklungspotenzial, das durch die Anwendung eines Marketingkonzepts in der Betriebsführung genutzt werden kann. Die landwirtschaftliche Produktion kann entwickelt werden, indem die Bedürfnisse des Marktes befriedigt werden. Das Angebot an bulgarischen Agrarerzeugnissen steht vor vielen Herausforderungen auf dem Markt, was die Landwirte zwingt, nach Mitteln zu suchen, um das Marktimage ihrer Erzeugnisse zu verbessern. Ziel des Artikels ist es, Leitlinien für die Verbesserung des Managements der bulgarischen landwirtschaftlichen Betriebe festzulegen.

Die Umsetzung strategischer Marketingaktivitäten durch die Landwirte kann ihre wirtschaftliche Leistung auf der Grundlage einer besseren Marktleistung verbessern. Die korrekte Umsetzung dieser Aktivitäten erfordert, dass sie als Teil eines systemischen Prozesses betrachtet werden, der alle Elemente des Produktions- und Vermarktungssystems betrifft. Dies setzt voraus, dass die Managementfunktionen im Zusammenhang mit der Planung, Durchführung und Kontrolle von Marketingaktivitäten im Kontext des Marktumfelds für jeden einzelnen Betrieb ausgeführt werden.

STICHWORTE: Prozess, System, Marketingkette, Analyse, Marketingziele

RÉSUMÉ

L'activité agricole en Bulgarie a un potentiel de développement si l'on applique une approche marketing à sa gestion. La production agricole peut être développée en satisfaisant les besoins du marché. L'offre de produits agricoles bulgares est confrontée à de nombreux défis commerciaux, ce qui oblige les agriculteurs à rechercher des moyens d'améliorer l'image de leurs produits sur le marché.

L'objectif de cet article est de définir des lignes directrices pour améliorer la gestion des exploitations agricoles bulgares.

La mise en œuvre d'activités de marketing stratégique par les agriculteurs peut améliorer leurs performances économiques grâce à de meilleurs résultats sur le marché. La mise en œuvre correcte de ces activités exige qu'elles soient considérées comme faisant partie d'un processus systémique qui affecte tous les éléments du système de production et de commercialisation. Cela implique que les fonctions de gestion liées à la planification, à l'exécution et au contrôle des activités de commercialisation soient exercées dans le contexte de l'environnement de marché de chaque entreprise.

MOTS CLÉS: processus, système, chaîne de commercialisation, analyse, objectifs de commercialisation

INTRODUCTION

The strategic marketing process begins with articulating the organization's mission and setting its long-term goals. Although these activities are not purely marketing, they are the basis for all others because they are general in nature and operate over a long period of time. Thus, at this stage, the boundaries within which the business will move (develop) in the future are determined and the attitude of the top management and shareholders towards the business is expressed.

Although it was established (in the course of the research) that the respondents gave the highest percentage of positive answers to the question regarding the clear formulation of the organization's mission, there are reservations regarding the content of this activity, the utilization of which will increase the quality of the entire marketing process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First of all, it should be noted that it is common for the mission statement to be too narrow in nature, focusing on the product being offered. Such an expression contradicts the basic principle of the marketing concept that the consumer with his needs is the main (starting) point for any business. This also determines the need for the needs that the company wants and believes it could satisfy through its products to be the basis of its mission. Thus, the mission will acquire a permanent character over time, due to the fact that the needs exist objectively, and the products are only a means of satisfying them.

The second direction for improving the formulation of the organization's mission is related to its reality. This problem has two sides - on the one hand, the mission may have an unrealistic character, as it is impossible to fulfill, and on the other hand, in case of a strong underestimation of the company's capabilities, the stimulating function of the mission for the staff is lost, i.e. it is easy to achieve. Therefore, a balance must be found here between these two extremes. To be real and achievable, the mission must be tailored to the company's capabilities and market characteristics, taking into account both the current state and expectations for their future development. Alsothus, the mission should stimulate the staff in their activities, which can be achieved by expressing a broader understanding of the business, setting the basic requirements by which the staff should be guided in the performance of their duties. Of course, it is no less important that the staff is familiar with and shares the company mission, which is the result of their motivation. In this way, unidirectionality is achieved in the actions of each of the employees and empathy with the philosophy of the organization. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the efficiency of the business unit's operation and achievement of its goals.

After the company mission is formulated, it needs to be detailed, through the main (main) goal and strategic goals of the organization (Borisov and Behluli, 2020). The main objective indicates the specific intentions of the company in the long term, and the strategic objectives take into account those areas that are recognized by managers as key to the realization of the mission and the main objective. For this detailing to be successful, managers need to have information about the needs and state of the market and, through strategic goals, to direct the efforts of associates to meet market conditions. For agricultural producers, it is appropriate that the strategic goals are related to the quality of the products offered; compliance with sanitary and hygienic requirements; establishment of partnership relationships with other economic entities; conservation of natural resources; staff training etc.

After defining the mission and strategic goals and before conducting a strategic analysis, market segmentation and target market selection are performed (Borisov and Garabedian, 2020). Thus, on the basis of the expressed mission and goals, the market will be segmented in such a way as to create an opportunity to choose the target market(s) that best suits them. After which to proceed to the next stage - carrying out a strategic analysis. We recommend that such an analysis be carried out, not only on the selected target markets, but also on the others that are currently not in the focus of the company, as this will allow to reveal both the common and the different between the individual segments, as well as to monitor their development so that, under certain conditions, the company can promptly direct its activities to serve new segments.

From the results of the conducted research, it is clear that there are significant reserves for increasing the effectiveness of strategic marketing activities at this stage. Market segmentation is the first step, without which it is unthinkable to carry out the next ones from this stage. Its successful implementation requires solving two problems: to define the relevant market, then to select appropriate criteria by which to segment it. According to Krastevich, the relevant market includes the entire set of consumers who will be the subject of the segmentation. It differs from the widely known category of target market. While the target market includes those market segments that are of particular interest to the business organization and to which marketing impacts are directly directed, the relevant market includes the entire set of potential and actual consumers with their needs that are relevant to it. There are different concepts according to which an enterprise can define its relevant market. The most important of them are the following: elementary market concept; concept of physical-technical similarity; cross price elasticity concept; concept of functional similarity; concept of expected competitive response; concept of subjectively perceived interchangeability. When solving the first problem, we recommend approaching it not from the point of view of the offered products, but from the point of view of what needs they satisfy in the user. This allows a broader view of the market to be formed, taking into account other products satisfying consumer needs. The broader definition of the relevant market allows to identify more segments that can be fully covered with specially developed company offers.

In order to achieve this, it is necessary not only to segment, but also to outline the user profile of each of the segments. Unfortunately, this activity is among the least represented in the enterprises of the branch. Its implementation requires the collection of rich information about users, which is assigned to the relevant specialists. Here is the place of the marketing specialist, researching the market to provide this information, through which to know the characteristics of each of the segments, by answering the questions: "Who are the consumers?"; "What is their social status?"; "How old are they?"; "What motivates them to make a purchase decision?"; "What is their lifestyle?" etc. Collecting this information requires additional costs, but it enables the company to offer a specific marketing mix

tailored and meeting exactly the needs of the given segment. This would save significant resources to produce and market products that are not based on consumer characteristics and would be difficult to adopt. Not a small part of the enterprises have focused on offering a mass product, without a clear idea of its user and competition based on price advantage. The creation of specific marketing mixes will personalize consumers and enable the transition to non-price competition, effectively using the other elements to influence demand.

Development of such marketing mixes can be undertaken after conducting a strategic analysis of the target markets. It examines all elements of the internal and external business environment, which requires obtaining information about each of them. Without sufficient information in terms of quantity and quality, the results of this analysis cannot be used further, that is why the construction and operation of a company information system has a leading role here. In fact, the quality of strategic analysis is determined by the availability of the necessary information and the methods used to collect and process it, and the improvement of the information-documentary base is a prerequisite for its improvement.

The presence of multiple subjects in the analysis necessitates the use of registries to gather information about each of them. While for the elements of the macro environment (economic, political, demographic, etc. conditions), various official publications (State Gazette, Statistical Yearbook, publications of governmental and non-governmental institutions, etc.) can be used, which provide the information in a ready form and it only needs to be classified. For the elements of the microenvironment and the internal environment, documents can be developed in which the collected information can be summarized according to certain parameters characterizing the state and actions of each element. The use of ready-made forms would facilitate the process of processing the information and improve its visibility. Samples of such forms are proposed, and we recommend that they be completed by year, after which they should be kept for a longer period of time (7-8 years).

In particular, the following forms have been developed:

When developing a distributor form, the main indicators by which they can be characterized and are relevant in the analysis of this element of the macro environment are included. Since the filling of the form is annual, it contains summary information about each economic entity, which is the result of the information collected throughout the year. This, in turn, requires that all interactions between the company and the distributor be recorded in chronological order. The form also contains ratings that can be given by experts and information about the distributor that the marketing specialists are responsible for recruiting.

A competitor form contains information about the products it offers, as well as how it operates in the market. We recommend filling in this form for each target segment separately, i.e. for the same company they can draw up more than one form depending on how many segments it participates in. In this way, the collected information about all competitors is relevant to the specific segment, which makes it easier to carry out a strategic analysis for each segment.

Collecting the information contained in a supplier form allows a company to both monitor and evaluate its interactions with each supplier and compare them among themselves. For this reason, the forms must be classified by type of product supplied, and also filled in for potential suppliers who, under certain conditions, would become partners for the company.

The emergence of new entrants to the market exacerbates competition, which is why it is necessary to analyze them. Through the proposed form, all new products on the market are registered, and here, too, the filling must be by segments. Despite its usefulness, this form is intended only for already developed and proposed products, and the analysis of this element of the external

microenvironment (new entrants) requires also assessing the possibilities of their appearance, which is why only the proposed forms cannot be used. Evaluating the possibilities for the emergence of new participants can be done on the basis of expert assessments, using the information from the competitors section. Also, in addition to the appearance of new products on the market, it is also possible for new economic entities to enter the sector.

Forms for registering information about the state of the elements of the internal company environment.

The proposed forms can be used both to analyze the elements of the internal environment and to compare the achievements with your competitors.

During the development of the financial form, 6 main indicators are included, which represent the financial situation of the company. To fill it in, information is used from the company's annual balance sheet and from its income and expense report.

Personnel is an important element of the internal company environment due to the fact that it is involved in all business processes. The proposed indicators show how labor resources have been used and their analysis makes it possible to reveal existing potential for their development.

A production form can be filled in either by plots (in case they are located at a great distance from each other or there are differences between them), or by varieties grown in the massifs. The information contained in this form makes it possible to analyze how the different plots are used and, on this basis, to foresee measures to improve those that do not meet the established company standards (Nikolov, boevsy, Borisov and Readev, 2020). Also, the registered information allows to reveal the real potential of the company for production.

Form marketing contains information characterizing the products offered by the company. It can be completed both for each segment of the markets in which the company participates, and in general for all segments, thus the significance of each of them would be easily assessed.

So the proposed forms yesa large volume of information is collected, which is often difficult to access. Each completed form participates in the strategic analysis and through them the status of the different farmers involved in the marketing chain can be compared, which is important to reveal their development potential.

Although the use of such forms requires the allocation of resources from companies, they have the following advantages:

- The collected information clearly and accurately describes the state of the market;
- The use of ready-made formats facilitates the collection and processing of information;
- Changes in indicators over time can be tracked;
- The information is available and it is possible to use it for other purposes, not only for the needs of strategic analysis.

Another strategic marketing activity that can increase the effectiveness in formulating, implementing and controlling the marketing strategy is setting quantitative marketing goals in written form (Kolaj, Osmani, Borisov and Skunca, 2019). Its non-performance by a significant proportion of the studied sites indicates an underestimation of this stage, which can be overcome by understanding its role. Goal setting is an important part of any management process and is the basis for planning. Quantifying marketing goals is necessary for at least two reasons: the numbers accurately express what we want to achieve, and they facilitate control over the achievement of those goals. As for their written form, marketing objectives are part of the marketing plan (and of other strategic documents), so they must inevitably be present in it.

In order for the set marketing goals to be effective, we recommend that they be aligned with the mission, the main goal and the goals of the other functional areas. Marketing objectives derive from the mission and the main objective, and together with the other functional objectives ensure their implementation during the period for which the marketing plan is developed. Aligning marketing goals with those in other areas will make them real, achievable, which is among the most important requirements in goal setting. In this way, setting marketing goals becomes a process in which managers from all company areas participate, which will make them empathetic to their achievement. After the marketing goals have been set, the goal setting process continues with the determination of specific goals for all elements of the marketing mix, the achievement of which will lead to the realization of the first ones. As a result of this process, the so-called a tree of goals, with the mission at the top, followed by the main goal, from which the goals by functional areas (including the marketing ones) derive, which are detailed in goals by their individual elements. The development of a tree of objectives not only presents clearly and clearly what the organization strives for, but it is also the basis for developing the operational objectives that are the subject of operational management. The binding of all these goals in one network shows not only what the company wants to achieve, but also what intermediate states it must go through, which necessitates setting specific deadlines for their achievement.

Another problem area in the formulation, implementation and control of the marketing strategy in the studied enterprises is the construction of a system to control its implementation. Control is an important management function, which aims to constantly compare the actual state of the organization regarding the implementation of the marketing strategy and the set desired state. The essence of the marketing strategy requires control to cover the state of the external as well environment, by monitoring the changes that occur in it. In this way, inconsistencies between the changed external environment and the current marketing strategy would be identified at an early stage, which would allow management to take corrective actions in order to establish alignment between them. The construction of a system for controlling strategic marketing activities is based on:

- creating standards for the state of intra-firm dimensions;
- monitoring of the elements of the external business environment;
- evaluating the effectiveness of the organizational structure;
- evaluating the implementation of the delegated rights and responsibilities for the implementation of the marketing strategy;
- procedure for correcting registered deviations;
- evaluating the implemented marketing strategy.

Thus, the proposed system monitors the current implementation of the company's marketing strategy, which is summarized at the end of its implementation period with an assessment of its effectiveness. This allows management to use these results in the next management cycle, which ensures continuity between time periods and justification of newly adopted management decisions. Building such a system will inevitably increase efficiency in formulating, implementing and controlling a marketing strategy.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be summarized that implementation of strategic marketing activities by farmers can lead to improvement of their economic results based on better market performance. The correct implementation of these activities requires that they be considered as part of a systemic process that affects all elements of the production and marketing system. This requires that the

management functions related to planning, execution and control of marketing activities are performed in the context of the market environment for each particular business.

Agribusiness has its own inherent characteristics and the implementation of strategic marketing activities helps to improve the service of the market. Strategic marketing activities determine the essence of the marketing strategy of the business and form the basis on which the agricultural holding interacts with the business environment. The need to manage this interaction is provoked by the prospects for business development and the desire for long-term development of agrarian business.

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THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF EXECUTIVE MANAGEMENT IN THE INTERNATIONALIZATION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The business environment today is undergoing dynamic changes due to globalization, market liberalization, and other modern trends. Additional pressures in recent times are caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russo-Ukrainian conflict. These trends bring numerous challenges but also opportunities for businesses. Most companies choose internationalization as a key strategy for achieving success and improving competitive positions. The success of this process depends on many factors, and a deep understanding of the target market is fundamental. The subject of this paper and its objectives are to determine the strategic role of top management in the internationalization process and to thoroughly examine the factors that influenced decisions to expand into international markets. Special emphasis will be placed on analyzing internal and external factors affecting internationalization. The paper will also explore how digitalization and technological advancements aid companies in this process. It will discuss the role of cultural differences and how they can impact international business operations. Strategies used by companies to adapt to different markets will be analyzed. Furthermore, the paper will address the role of innovation in the internationalization process. In conclusion, recommendations will be offered for companies planning to expand into international markets. The paper will also consider how geopolitical factors can influence internationalization decisions. The role of financial resources and their management in the internationalization process will be explored.

KEY WORDS: top management, internationalization, strategic management, market

ABSTRAKT

Das Unternehmensumfeld unterliegt heute aufgrund von Globalisierung, Marktliberalisierung und anderen modernen Trends einem dynamischen Wandel. Zusätzlicher Druck entsteht in letzter Zeit durch die COVID-19-Pandemie und den russisch-ukrainischen Konflikt. Diese Trends bringen zahlreiche Herausforderungen, aber auch Chancen für die Unternehmen mit sich. Die meisten Unternehmen entscheiden sich für die Internationalisierung als Schlüsselstrategie, um erfolgreich zu sein und ihre Wettbewerbsposition zu verbessern. Der Erfolg dieses Prozesses hängt von vielen Faktoren ab, und ein tiefes Verständnis des Zielmarktes ist von grundlegender Bedeutung. Gegenstand und Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es, die strategische Rolle des Top-Managements im Internationalisierungsprozess zu bestimmen und die Faktoren, die Entscheidungen zur Expansion in internationale Märkte beeinflussen, eingehend zu untersuchen. Besonderes Augenmerk wird auf die Analyse der internen und externen Faktoren gelegt, die die Internationalisierung beeinflussen. Außerdem wird untersucht, wie die Digitalisierung und der technologische Fortschritt die Unternehmen bei diesem Prozess unterstützen. Es wird auf die Rolle kultureller Unterschiede eingegangen und wie sie sich auf internationale Geschäftstätigkeiten auswirken können. Es wird analysiert, welche Strategien Unternehmen anwenden, um sich an unterschiedliche Märkte anzupassen. Außerdem wird die Rolle der Innovation im Internationalisierungsprozess erörtert. Abschließend werden Empfehlungen für Unternehmen gegeben, die eine Expansion in internationale Märkte planen. Der Beitrag geht auch darauf ein, wie geopolitische Faktoren Internationalisierungsentscheidungen beeinflussen können. Die Rolle der finanziellen Ressourcen und ihres Managements im Internationalisierungsprozess wird untersucht.

STICHWORTE: Topmanagement, Internationalisierung, strategisches Management, Markt

RÉSUMÉ

L'environnement des entreprises subit aujourd'hui des changements dynamiques dus à la mondialisation, à la libéralisation des marchés et à d'autres tendances modernes. La pandémie de COVID-19 et le conflit russo-ukrainien ont exercé des pressions supplémentaires ces derniers temps. Ces tendances entraînent de nombreux défis, mais aussi des opportunités pour les entreprises. La plupart des entreprises choisissent l'internationalisation comme stratégie clé pour réussir et améliorer leur position concurrentielle. Le succès de ce processus dépend de nombreux facteurs, et une compréhension approfondie du marché cible est fondamentale. Le sujet de ce document et ses objectifs sont de déterminer le rôle stratégique de la direction générale dans le processus d'internationalisation et d'examiner en profondeur les facteurs qui ont influencé les décisions d'expansion sur les marchés internationaux. L'accent sera mis sur l'analyse des facteurs internes et externes affectant l'internationalisation. Le document explorera également la manière dont la numérisation et les avancées technologiques aident les entreprises dans ce processus. Il abordera le rôle des différences culturelles et la manière dont elles peuvent avoir un impact sur les opérations commerciales internationales. Les stratégies utilisées par les entreprises pour s'adapter aux différents marchés seront analysées. En outre, le document abordera le rôle de l'innovation dans le processus d'internationalisation. En conclusion, des recommandations seront formulées à l'intention des entreprises qui envisagent de se développer sur les marchés internationaux. Le document examinera également la manière dont les facteurs géopolitiques peuvent influencer les décisions d'internationalisation. Le rôle des ressources financières et de leur gestion dans le processus d'internationalisation sera exploré.

MOTS CLÉS: direction générale, internationalisation, gestion stratégique, marché

INTRODUCTION

The global business environment has significantly changed due to the increasing pressures of globalization, primarily the liberalization of markets. Globalization brings numerous opportunities but also challenges for businesses. To maintain competitiveness, companies are increasing their international presence and defining internationalization as a key strategy for market competition. The success of internationalization largely depends on the in-depth understanding of foreign markets by top management. The role of top management in the internationalization process is to identify opportunities and challenges in entering international markets, interpret relevant information, consider organizational capabilities and constraints, and formulate and implement internationalization strategies.

Differences between domestic and foreign environments, such as a lack of knowledge about the local market and physical and psychological barriers arising from cultural, linguistic, religious, and institutional differences, influence the risk perception of top managers. Therefore, top management with diverse characteristics, skills, and experiences is crucial for a company to leverage a wealth of knowledge and thereby enable the company to handle the challenges and uncertainties of the internationalization process. Diversity within the management team leads to various authentic and constructive opinions, increasing creativity and the quality of decision-making, which helps overcome the obstacles arising from the heterogeneity of foreign markets.

Additionally, top management plays a critical role in fostering a corporate culture that supports international expansion. This involves promoting flexibility, adaptability, and a global mindset among employees. By doing so, management can facilitate smoother transitions and better integration into new markets. Effective communication strategies are also essential, ensuring that information flows seamlessly across different geographical locations and organizational levels.

Furthermore, top managers must engage in continuous learning and development to keep abreast of global trends and innovations. This ongoing education enables them to make informed decisions and stay competitive in a rapidly changing global landscape. Strategic partnerships and alliances with local firms can also be instrumental, providing valuable insights and facilitating market entry. Finally, ethical considerations and corporate social responsibility (CSR) should be integral to international strategies, ensuring that the company operates sustainably and maintains a positive reputation worldwide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conceptual Definition and Development of the Internationalization Process.

Internationalization is a long-term and highly complex process often hindered by numerous differences in culture, language, economic, and political systems. It is a topic encountered in various fields of academic literature, such as strategic management, international business, and international marketing. Internationalization involves the geographical expansion of business activities across national borders and the creation of networks of business relationships in other countries through the process of penetration, expansion, and integration (Johanson and Vahlne, 1977). The simplest definition was provided by Welch and Loustarinen (1988:36), stating that it is "increasing involvement in international operations," which is a very broad definition. Thus, internationalization manifests through the mode of operation, the object of sale, the orientation towards the target market, and organizational capacities, with a focus on international business and international engagement.

Many scholars define internationalization, and it is presented in numerous models. Some authors, through in-depth analyses, have provided various definitions of internationalization, noting that it is "the process in which a company becomes aware of the direct and indirect impacts of international transactions in the future," or that it is "a gradual process in which a company develops a network of global trade relationships" (Alkaabi, Dixon, 2014:24). Internationalization involves crossing the borders of one country and generally constitutes a strategy for expanding a company abroad to achieve goals such as better business cooperation, creating space for imports/exports, and achieving better business conditions.

The internationalization process experienced the greatest growth from 1870 until the outbreak of World War I. After the war, business connections began to re-establish but were again halted by World War II. In the second half of the 20th century, especially from the 1990s, there was a greater fragmentation of the process, during which the largest global companies moved their production facilities to countries with cheaper or more accessible resources (Andrijić and Pavlović, 2012). From then until today, every expansion into new foreign markets represents an opportunity for companies to achieve higher profits and foster innovation and growth (Previšić and Došen, 1999).

The first significant attempts to analyze the internationalization process are linked to the Uppsala model. Within the Uppsala model, authors Johanson and Vahlne (1977) view the internationalization process as a series of several stages: a) No export activities; b) Export through an independent representative; c) Establishing a sales subsidiary in a foreign country; d) Establishing a production unit in a foreign country. In other words, all decisions regarding activities are made after acquiring the necessary knowledge, and the market to be entered is chosen based on various criteria. The Uppsala model is thus a dynamic model where the results of one cycle represent the input variable for the next cycle. This means that market knowledge influences the decision on commitment and subsequently on business activities. All this represents a gradual internationalization and forms the innovation model, whose fundamental premise is the adoption of innovation (Andersen, 1993). This process is based on a gradual approach that can be linked to new needs in a new company, new opportunities, or resources (Johanson and Vahlne, 1977).

In the internationalization process, the aim is to expand business to markets outside the domestic country, which generally means the mobility of goods and services beyond domestic borders. For example, a company's subsidiary operating in a particular market can apply an international marketing mix that can be developed and monitored by the foreign company. The goal of this process is to optimally utilize all potentials and resources and produce as much output as possible. Therefore, in the internationalization process, five different concepts are used:

- Export concept;
- Plurinational concept;
- Multinational concept;
- Multiregional concept;

Global concept (Malenica and Dorbić, 2014). The objectives of these concepts are the adaptation of domestic programs to foreign markets, maximum adaptation of the marketing program to domestic activities, and the creation of a global market as a single market with a global program (Previšić and Došen, 1999). In other words, the purpose of internationalization is to create globally widespread operations to achieve goals in both foreign and domestic markets simultaneously.

One of the products of internationalization is the economic integration of countries. This creates a market for expanding the economy and achieving better prosperity for countries and developing new entrepreneurial ventures. Previously, most international strategies focused primarily on a single product, but today large companies operate with a portfolio of brands and sophisticated clients worldwide, adding a whole new level of complexity to the challenges of internationalization (Vukosav, 2016).

Operating on the international stage and internationalization are not new phenomena; this strategy has been relevant throughout history, as evident from the earlier text. Increased interest in international business emerged due to its impact on supply and demand. It is a significant challenge that requires an appropriate response. Success in the international market results from the influence of many factors, regardless of whether the company is large or small. Generally, larger business entities engage in activities in multiple foreign markets, while small and medium-sized enterprises typically engage in one or a smaller number of foreign markets (Grbac, 2009).

In other words, foreign markets represent new places for achieving profit and goals while simultaneously participating in the domestic market. By opening new branches and expanding operations, importing, and forming other business partnerships abroad, companies can gain numerous advantages. However, each company has different motives for entering a foreign market.

Strategic Motives for Companies Entering Foreign Markets. Globalization, the removal of barriers, and the weakening of national borders, along with strategic orientation and the equality of participants, characterize modern international trade. Internationalization has become a condition for the survival of companies regardless of their size or country of origin. Today, most companies worldwide are exporters of products or services, whether actively, occasionally, or potentially. During the 1990s, one of the more dynamic forms of business internationalization was acquisition and merger. The motives driving companies towards internationalization are numerous and mainly concern entering new markets, increasing market share, accessing new markets, eliminating competition, and similar objectives (Lazibat et al., 2006). According to research by Malenica and Dorbić (2014), the most important factors or motives for participating in foreign markets are: a) Realizing profit; b) Business expansion; c) Better utilization of production capacities; d) Greater employment opportunities; e) Marketing skills of the company; f) Entrepreneurial motivation; g) Innovativeness; h) Saturation of the domestic market; i) Advantages of foreign markets over domestic ones.

Thus, numerous factors influence a company's decision to internationalize its operations, which can be grouped into internal and external factors. Internal factors are those that impact the

process within domestic borders, while external factors affect the internationalization process itself. The most significant factors in the domestic market that drive the desire for expansion to foreign markets include a small domestic market, limited opportunities, high domestic competition, and the product life cycle. Additionally, economic conditions, legal regulations, organizational, and managerial capabilities play a role. External factors influencing the decision to internationalize include favorable market conditions, positive market growth in other countries, demographic changes, and foreign incentives (Andrijanić and Pavlović, 2012).

Internationalization thus becomes a survival condition for most companies, especially in certain industrial sectors (e.g., the automotive industry). The internationalization of activities has made competition transnational, leading to a more equitable distribution of knowledge (Lazibat et al., 2006). The internationalization of a company requires the development of a complex organizational structure, the integration of domestic and foreign business models, systematic monitoring and reporting of trends, to ensure effective coordination and execution of company activities, and to adequately adopt new practices and technologies.

Another challenge in the internationalization process is the external environment that the company faces. For example, companies operating in multiple countries encounter multiple competitors, forcing them to function as more integrated units. Survival in foreign markets depends on heterogeneous cultural and institutional factors. Therefore, companies must harmonize their business models and local regulations to meet customer needs (Vallone et al., 2019).

By entering foreign markets, companies seek to leverage various strategic motives to enhance their competitiveness and sustainability. This often involves adapting products and services to meet the specific demands of local markets, investing in local talent, and forming strategic alliances with local businesses. Furthermore, international expansion allows companies to diversify their market base, reducing dependence on a single market and spreading risk across multiple regions.

Successful internationalization requires a comprehensive understanding of the target market's cultural, economic, and regulatory environments. Companies must also be prepared to invest in market research, build robust supply chains, and develop flexible business strategies that can be adjusted as conditions change. In doing so, they can better navigate the complexities of international markets and capitalize on new opportunities for growth and innovation.

The Strategic Role of Top Management in the Internationalization Process. Globalization, technological development, and the integration of countries have led to increased international competition and a growing need for business internationalization. In this process, many international business studies recognize the role of top management and management in general in internationalization, while the challenges faced by top management are often overlooked. Therefore, it is essential to understand the role of top management in organizational choices, strategies, and market presence (Heijltjes, Olie, Glunk, 2003). The business environment has significantly changed in today's widespread market and liberalization, making the business world increasingly global. Consequently, more companies are opting for previously mentioned business internationalization, encouraging international presence to remain successful and competitive (Vallone et al., 2019). The complexity of management is reflected in managers working on multiple levels and with different organizational capabilities (Vukosav, 2016).

Management is essentially a system of people responsible for managing a company, primarily organized hierarchically. It is possible to distinguish between top, middle, and lower management (Rupčić, 2018). Top management consists of one or more individuals who collectively bear overall responsibility for business success. In large companies, top management includes the Chief Executive Officer (CEO), Chief Operating Officer (COO), Chief Financial Officer (CFO), and in modern companies, the Chief Knowledge Officer (CKO). In American companies, this also includes the president and vice

president. Together, they form the executive team accountable to the supervisory board or board of directors (Rupčić, 2018).

Top management, therefore, is a group of one or more individuals who collectively bear responsibility for the organization's success and goal achievement. They generally answer to the supervisory board and are responsible for formulating the mission, vision, strategies, and similar directives. Middle management ranks immediately below top management, reporting to them and leading autonomous or semi-autonomous organizational units (departments and divisions). Their role is coordinative or communicative, managing the work of organizational units. In large companies, middle management's role is also very important and often crucial for survival and development (Rupčić, 2018). Middle management thus aligns top and lower management. Lower management consists of individuals acting as supervisors or team leaders, managing smaller groups of people or units to achieve operational goals (Rupčić, 2018).

From this, it can be concluded that at lower management levels, the purpose of operations is supervision and leadership of smaller groups. All management levels collectively form a complete management system, each dependent on the other. The planning process begins from the top and moves to lower levels. Thus, top management defines key planning parameters (e.g., missions, goals, and strategies), which are concretized into formal plans at lower levels (Vukosav, 2016). Therefore, all three levels are crucial for driving business and achieving goals, but everything essentially starts with top management.

The primary task of top management is shaping the global strategy and setting long-term goals for the company while defining the vision and mission. Top management monitors the implementation of strategies and the degree of goal realization, thus having a significant impact on shaping organizational culture and entrepreneurial orientation. Often, it consists of founders or owners of the company. They make strategically important decisions, focusing more on the external environment than the internal. Their primary task is to study the external environment. Given all the above, it is important for top management to think strategically and systematically, considering many factors and potential risk manifestations (Rupčić, 2018).

Additionally, top management must be flexible and capable of overcoming adversities and business risks. This is the fundamental way of management functioning, especially top management, as the inability to achieve this can lead to various risks and problems. In this regard, the flexibility of top management implies good organization, crisis management, longevity, high reliability, and future growth perspective (Carmeli et al., 2013). Thus, top management should consist of a relatively small team of executives who control the company, setting strategic goals and making business decisions, including those about investments, market entry, and internationalization (Vukosav, 2016).

Over the years, numerous studies have explored the impact and importance of top management in the business process in general, and in the internationalization process specifically. For example, Tihany et al. (2000) conducted a study examining the links between top management characteristics and various organizational outcomes. The research found that younger top managers are more likely to influence strategic changes in companies compared to older top management members. The results also indicated that younger executives make riskier but potentially more beneficial decisions, while teams with longer tenures tend to pursue international diversification more, likely due to higher levels of communication, shared cognitive abilities, and characteristics necessary for internationalization. Additionally, these authors conclude that in today's business environment, internationalization is an inevitable process and an economic necessity. Therefore, companies must be capable of leveraging international opportunities to successfully operate in a global environment.

Thus, top management plays a crucial role in corporate diversification (Tihanyi et al., 2000). It is possible to conclude that top managers have a pivotal role in business operations, particularly in

internationalization. When they set decisions and strategies well, it becomes easier for the company to adapt to foreign markets, facilitating future operations and ensuring higher levels of success.

Factors Influencing Strategic Decisions of Top Management in the Process of Internationalization. Management at all levels must possess the necessary competencies and knowledge to successfully perform their duties. Given that individuals from various professions and backgrounds perform management roles, it is evident that acquired skills and knowledge hold greater value for such positions than formal education alone. A manager's success depends precisely on the knowledge and skills they possess. Therefore, top management is tasked with making decisions regarding the vision, mission, and strategic goals, with the primary challenge being to balance profit generation and quick return on investment (Uvodić et al., 2021).

Top management is also responsible for analyzing all crucial environmental factors (both external and internal) whose effects can impact long-term business operations or certain aspects of the business. Hence, it is crucial to analyze, establish relationships, and understand the implications on the business with due diligence and to design appropriate solutions. Environmental analysis is thus an important prerequisite for setting goals and defining global strategies. As such, this level of management possesses a broad spectrum of expertise and must have adequate social skills, such as advisory or mentoring skills. Networking, communication skills, listening skills, presentation skills, and negotiation skills are also essential.

Strategic decisions made by top management in the internationalization process can be influenced by the mission and vision, which must be strategically determined beforehand. For instance, they may relate to improving the current financial situation, enhancing offerings, and so on. Strategic decisions can be made by top management using two approaches – top-down or bottom-up (Rupčić, 2018). The expansion into the international market is a corporate-level strategy for which top management is responsible. Being at the very top of the organization, top management plays a vital role in the internationalization process by overseeing and coordinating domestic and foreign activities of the company and is responsible for formulating and implementing the internationalization strategy.

The top management team can be viewed as an information processing center where internal and external information is collected, processed, and analyzed, ultimately to be shared with the rest of the organization. Therefore, top management must have adequate information processing capacities, and the lack of this and other important skills can jeopardize internationalization (Vallone et al., 2019).

In other words, better knowledge of a specific market or industry, gained through personal or professional experience in different cultural environments, will help top management more easily handle problems. Additionally, innovative thinking will facilitate the internationalization process (Vallone et al., 2019). Top managers must have certain decision-making skills regarding internationalization and must be well-versed in the motives driving them and the capabilities of the company for which they are making decisions. All of this is a prerequisite for easier navigation through the internationalization process and achieving goals in the international market.

Research conducted by Heijltjes, Olie, and Glunk in 2003 on the level of internationalization of Dutch and Swedish companies indicates that having more foreign managers is an important factor in the decision to internationalize. Consequently, a company with more foreign managers will have a higher preference for internationalization. Ownership internationalization is also a significant factor and can influence internationalization; for example, companies listed on international stock exchanges will be more oriented towards this process. To attract international investors, an international image is important, as is the presence of foreign investors, owners, and members of top management (Heijltjes, Olie, Glunk, 2003).

Therefore, top managers can significantly influence the capability and success of entrepreneurial activities. Some top management teams are more capable of generating successful entrepreneurial ideas compared to others, less successful ones. This is generally more easily achieved in larger teams whose diversity and size, often along with shared work history, facilitate this process. Of course, top managers can help their teams with effective strategic decision-making and decision-making, which must be quick without compromising team cohesion (Eisenhardt, 2013). Top managers must have a broad perspective on the business context of the company due to their knowledge and experience, and international top managers are often more risk-inclined and thus more open to new ideas and innovations. International exposure allows individuals to expand their perspective beyond domestic foundations, developing valuable abilities and skills. Therefore, top managers can integrate part of their national culture into international business, adding additional value to the company (Wrede, Dauth, 2020).

Challenges and Problems of Top Management in the Internationalization Process.

Internationalization, as previously noted, is a highly complex process in which top management must know how to deal with all possible obstacles and problems. The multiple levels of complexity in internationalization require companies to possess a high degree of information processing capabilities, problem-solving abilities, and various forms of knowledge and experience. The extent to which a company can rely on the capabilities of those responsible for the decision-making process regarding internationalization, i.e., the top management, depends on this (Vallone et al., 2019).

Challenges that top management may face include dealing with vastly diverse international environments, including different languages, cultures, regulations, and physical distances. All of these factors influence the risk perception of top management and significantly increase the demands for information processing driven by differences between domestic and foreign environments. Therefore, for international organizations, it is important to have top managers with diverse characteristics, skills, and experiences to leverage a larger set of knowledge, capabilities, and perspectives that enhance the company's capacity to process and address international risks (Vallone et al., 2019). Furthermore, problems that may arise are usually the result of a lack of market knowledge, as well as physical and psychological barriers that stem from it. It is important to be aware of potential difficulties to reduce the possibility of risks and failures (Vallone et al., 2019). All of these issues can be addressed by investing in the development of human capital, from top to lower levels of management and employees (Carpenter, Sanders, 2004).

Companies often tend to fail, a phenomenon known as the "liability of newness," which arises from various reasons. For instance, companies often have limited resources that restrict their resilience and ability to adapt to the market. In preserving the ability to succeed and facilitating the internationalization process, top managers play a crucial role and have a significant impact on success. Establishing top-notch management teams is highly productive for the future performance of the company as they can set the direction of establishment and further progress (Eisenhardt, 2013).

Global strategies are much more complex than domestic strategies. For example, the Swedish furniture and home goods company IKEA initially had a development strategy only in its domestic market, later expanding to other parts of Scandinavia and Europe, while facing difficulties in markets such as the USA and Japan. Therefore, the company decided to redefine its customer relationships in order to standardize its sales and operations in foreign markets. The main challenge for managers lies in determining the extent to which they should adapt to the market without compromising the core corporate image (Perkov et al., 2018).

CONCLUSION

The process of internationalization presents top management with a myriad of challenges and complexities, demanding adept navigation through diverse international environments. These environments encompass varying languages, cultures, regulations, and geographical distances, significantly impacting the risk perception of top management and intensifying the need for comprehensive information processing. Consequently, international organizations must cultivate top management teams with diverse characteristics, skills, and experiences to effectively leverage a broad spectrum of knowledge and perspectives essential for addressing international risks. Problems arising from internationalization often stem from a lack of market knowledge and the presence of physical and psychological barriers, necessitating proactive measures to mitigate risks and failures. Investing in the development of human capital across all levels of management and employees is crucial for overcoming these challenges and fostering success in the internationalization process.

The phenomenon known as the "liability of newness" underscores the inherent risks companies face, especially when venturing into new markets with limited resources. In this context, top managers play a pivotal role in preserving the company's ability to succeed and facilitating the internationalization journey. Establishing high-performing management teams is instrumental in charting the company's course and ensuring future growth and success. However, devising global strategies presents a formidable task, far more intricate than formulating domestic strategies.

For instance, IKEA, the Swedish furniture giant, initially struggled in markets like the USA and Japan, prompting a reevaluation of its customer relationships to standardize operations across foreign markets. The main challenge for managers lies in striking a delicate balance between adapting to foreign markets and upholding the core corporate image. Such complexities underscore the critical importance of top management's ability to navigate the internationalization process effectively.

Overall, the success of internationalization hinges on the adeptness of top management in addressing multifaceted challenges, ranging from cultural differences to regulatory complexities. By fostering a culture of innovation and strategic decision-making, top managers can steer the company towards sustainable growth and competitive advantage in the global marketplace.

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MODEL FOR ORGANIZING JOINT MARKETING ACTIVITIES BY AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS

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ABSTRACT

Farmers have little market power and improving their market positions can be achieved by organizing and implementing joint marketing activities. Joint marketing activities contribute to addressing the market challenges faced by Bulgarian farmers.

The purpose of the article is to propose a model for organizing and conducting joint marketing activities.

Implementation of joint marketing activities can only be achieved if successful management models are developed in agribusiness. The correct design of the interaction between independent agricultural holdings requires the construction of relevant structures to which specific rights and responsibilities for the implementation of joint marketing activities will be delegated. The activities themselves are implemented through the management functions - planning, organizing, implementation and control.

KEY WORDS: market power, cooperation, coordination, marketing unit

ABSTRAKT

Die Marktmacht der Landwirte ist gering und eine Verbesserung ihrer Marktposition kann durch die Organisation und Umsetzung gemeinsamer Marketingaktivitäten erreicht werden. Gemeinsame Marketingaktivitäten tragen dazu bei, die Marktherausforderungen der bulgarischen Landwirte zu bewältigen.

Der Zweck des Artikels besteht darin, ein Modell für die Organisation und Durchführung gemeinsamer Marketingaktivitäten vorzuschlagen.

Die Umsetzung gemeinsamer Marketingaktivitäten kann nur gelingen, wenn in der Agrarwirtschaft erfolgreiche Managementmodelle entwickelt werden. Die richtige Gestaltung der Interaktion zwischen unabhängigen landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben erfordert den Aufbau entsprechender Strukturen, an die spezifische Rechte und Pflichten zur Durchführung gemeinsamer Vermarktungsaktivitäten delegiert werden. Die Aktivitäten selbst werden durch die Managementfunktionen – Planung, Organisation, Umsetzung und Kontrolle – umgesetzt.

STICHWORTE: Marktmacht, Kooperation, Koordination, Marketingeinheit

RÉSUMÉ

Les agriculteurs ont peu de pouvoir sur le marché et il est possible d'améliorer leur position sur le marché en organisant et en mettant en œuvre des activités de commercialisation conjointes. Les activités de commercialisation conjointes contribuent à relever les défis du marché auxquels sont confrontés les agriculteurs bulgares.

Le but de l'article est de proposer un modèle d'organisation et de conduite d'activités marketing conjointes.

La mise en œuvre d'activités de commercialisation conjointes ne peut être réalisée que si des modèles de gestion efficaces sont développés dans l'agro-industrie. La conception correcte de l'interaction entre les exploitations agricoles indépendantes nécessite la construction de structures pertinentes auxquelles seront délégués des droits et des responsabilités spécifiques pour la mise en

œuvre d'activités de commercialisation conjointes. Les activités elles-mêmes sont mises en œuvre à travers les fonctions de gestion - planification, organisation, mise en œuvre et contrôle.

MOTS CLÉS: pouvoir de marché, coopération, coordination, unité de commercialisation

INTRODUCTION

In order for joint marketing activities to ensure the achievement of planned results, they must meet certain requirements. According to Galbraith, any document to be a strategy must satisfy four conditions: 1) purpose, 2) collateral, 3) actions and 4) coordination.

The first condition refers to the objective(s) of the strategy in the context of which the joint marketing activities are carried out. Every strategy must have a clear, strictly and unambiguously defined end goal. This goal should be decomposed on a hierarchical basis into sub-goals and tasks from different levels of the decomposition. The decomposition must be carried out on a non-contradictory basis, so that there is no conflict between the goals and objectives of a given level of the decomposition, nor between the goals and objectives of different levels of the decomposition. With the decomposition of the ultimate goal carried out in this way, the achievement of the sub-goals (corresponding to solving the tasks and sub-tasks) of the lower levels of decomposition is a condition leading to the achievement of the goals, respectively the tasks) from the higher level of the decomposition. The second condition refers to the necessary and sufficient resources of any kind (material, human, financial, technical) for the realization of the goals and tasks of the decomposition. According to this condition, a document claiming to be a strategy cannot be recognized as such, if the necessary resources of any kind for the achievement or fulfillment of the goals and tasks are not identified and identified (including parameterized quantitatively and qualitatively) from decomposition. The third condition refers to the derivation of the necessary measures and actions, without which it is impossible to achieve, respectively, the fulfillment of the goals and tasks of the decomposition. Without presented and identified events and actions of any kind (economic, social, technical-technological, psychological, etc.), it is not possible for a document to have the character of a strategy. The fourth condition refers to the coordination in place and time between the necessary resources of any kind and the necessary events and actions also of any kind in accordance with the requirements of the technology to achieve each goal, respectively for the implementation of each task of the decomposition. Without such coordination in place and time, a document claiming to be a strategy has no right to such a claim.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Another author, George Day, states that for a management model to be successful, it must meet the following three conditions: feasibility, maintenance, and consistency.

Feasibility – does the business have the necessary experience and resources? Financial and physical resources are the first constraints against which the strategic alternative must be weighed. Strategic marketing activities are designed within constraints. The next constraints on which the chosen strategy for joint marketing activities should be checked are access to markets, technology and service capabilities. Are there prepared salespeople to cover the target market? Are these sellers capable of doing their job under the strategy in question? Are advertising efforts sufficient? What is the relationship with intermediaries, suppliers and retailers? What are the costs, efficiency and utilization of the current distribution system, how are orders, inventory and delivery handled? These questions must be answered in the course of designing the strategy for joint marketing activities. The most difficult limitations to overcome are related to those activities of individual collaborators and

organizations, which are difficult to present in numerical form. The main question is whether the organization has ever demonstrated that it can provide the necessary degree of coordination and integration of habits necessary to implement the strategies in question. Any strategy that depends on the performance of tasks that go beyond the limits of reasonable reality is unacceptable.

Support - to what extent do the key people involved in the implementation of joint marketing activities understand their essence and are ready to engage in such a strategy? To reliably ensure successful implementation, two conditions are necessary: 1) the basis and elements of the strategy must be interconnected, if the collaborators do not understand them, not only will the strategy end in failure, but also it will not receive the necessary support. A good strategy is one in which all functions are clear and these functions do not contradict each other. For this reason, a good strategy is one that can sufficiently explain everything in 2-3 pages. 2) the strategy must stimulate and motivate the employees. The strategy must be supported not only by those who develop it, but also by those who will implement it. If managers have serious objections to a given strategy, or they do not accept the goals and methods for achieving them, or actively support an alternative strategy, the strategy in question should be determined as unworkable.

Consistency – is the strategy interconnected and logical? It needs to be compatible with other functional strategies. Without an acceptable degree of such compliance, effective coordination cannot be ensured. The consumer often observes such internal contradictions in strategies: assertion of high quality accompanied by unattractive packaging, or an intensive sales program without ensuring timely delivery of the product. The "consistency" test often turns out to be the main one, and so the strategy is rejected for lack of consistency. It can be useful for improving and refining the strategy so that all its elements work in concert. This test may also show that the changes necessary to align all elements of the strategy with the given resources are not feasible.

Although the requirements defined by the two quoted authors largely overlap in essence, there are some secondary differences between them that are not insignificant (Borisov and Behluli, 2020). In the second necessary condition, Galbraith brings out the need to determine all the necessary resources for the implementation of the strategy. While Day emphasizes the possession of these resources or the ability to attract or develop them in the course of carrying out the chosen marketing strategy, ie. not only for them to be determined (which is rather expressed in the sequence condition he set), but also for the ways of their attraction to be indicated. Also J. Day pays special attention to the fact that when implementing the marketing strategy, not only internal company parameters are important, but also relationships with external entities, such as suppliers, intermediaries, etc. The coordination of the company's actions with those of its partners can facilitate the implementation of the chosen marketing strategy, and vice versa, if there is no such coordination, its successful implementation can be endangered. Another very important point that Day adds is the support that the marketing strategy must receive from everyone who will implement it. In this way, the human factor is defined as leading in the implementation of the chosen strategy, without its essence being understood and supported by people, it will remain only a theoretical tool.

Due to the above reasons, we believe that the cited authors complement and enrich each other when defining the requirements for marketing strategies. Although we accept the opinions of these authors, we think it is appropriate to add two more requirements according to which every marketing strategy should be assessed, namely the level of risk it contains and compliance with the technology for its development and implementation.

The degree of risk is an important factor due to the fact that strategies are always forward-looking and cover a larger time horizon, therefore, in its development, predictions are made and

meanings of future characteristics of the external environment are assumed, which may not coincide with their real state during the implementation of the strategy. Therefore, it is necessary that the level of risk be at an acceptable level, so that not only the successful implementation of the marketing strategy, but also the functioning of the business as a whole, is not threatened.

The second condition we add relates to compliance with the technology for developing a marketing strategy. During its development, it goes through certain stages, which must be carried out in the specified sequence and at the same time each stage must be performed accurately and meaningfully (fully). Thus formulated, the marketing strategy has a complete, comprehensive look, which is an important prerequisite for it to be successful and lead to the achievement of the set goals.

The discussed issues for designing joint activities are the basis of the developed model for organizing and conducting joint marketing activities by agricultural producers. The model is suitable for application by small farms that want to improve their market positions and achieve higher economic results from their activities. The number of farmers participating in joint marketing activities should be tailored to the specificities of the markets served. The developed model covers the management functions performed in agricultural holdings and the activities of their provision. A central place in the model is occupied by the marketing structure, which coordinates joint marketing activities and helps to realize the goals of agricultural holdings. The individual structural elements of the model for organizing joint marketing activities are presented in the following figure.

Stage "Planning" - Functioning of a marketing information system is an important part of ensuring joint marketing activities by collecting information on all elements of the external and internal environment, as well as its processing and storage for the purpose of using it in making informed management decisions. Providing joint marketing activities with necessary resources aims to ensure their feasibility. Providing the necessary resources is an important prerequisite for the successful implementation of the activities and the achievement of the goals. Developing a marketing mix for each target segment aims to meet the needs of existing and potential customers by offering them products, packaging, etc. tailored to their requirements. The performance of these activities is influenced by both the profile of the target market and the results of the analysis of the external environment, due to the influence of various entities on the final decision of what marketing mix to develop.

Stage "Organize" - Clearly defining the marketing strategy aims to select a specific strategy for execution. Her choice is influenced by the set business and marketing goals. The main purpose of the analysis of the business environment is to determine the characteristic features of the micro- and macro-environment and the resulting opportunities and threats to the competitive position. Also, the results of the analysis help to assess the attractiveness of the target market and outline its profile, as well as to set quantitative marketing goals. The activities include an analysis of the internal environment, which evaluates the activities of agricultural holdings in many aspects. The goal is to identify their strengths and weaknesses. The results of this analysis help to set quantitative marketing goals and ensure that marketing activities are provided with the necessary resources. Analysis of the interaction between producers aims to assess how their strengths combine to exploit the opportunities of the external environment and minimize the impact of its threats. These activities help to set reasonable marketing goals and choose reasonable marketing strategies.

Figure 1. Model for organizing and conducting joint marketing activities. Source: own interpretation.

Implementation Stage –When setting prices, a five-stage procedure is followed: 1) selection of a price target; 2) determining demand; 3) analysis of pricing factors; 4) selection of the pricing method and 5) formation of the final price. Issues related to product distribution relate to how to structure the sales force, how many associates will be involved in the process, how orders will be handled, the location of delivery, and customer service schedules. An important part of joint marketing activities is conducting a communication policy towards consumers and society as a whole. When developing a communication policy, eight steps are followed: 1) to identify the target audience; 2) to define communication goals; 3) compose the message; 4) to decide on the communication structure; 5) to choose the communication channels; 6) to determine the general communication budget; 7) to measure the results of communication; and 8) manage the integrated marketing communications process.

Stage "Control" - The construction of a system to control the implementation of the marketing strategy aims to control the implementation of joint marketing activities and, on the basis of identified significant changes in the external environment, to support the initiation of measures to improve its implementation. This sub-stage affects the choice on the marketing structure and the delegation of rights and responsibilities for the implementation of the marketing strategy.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be summarized that the implementation of joint marketing activities can only be achieved if successful management models are developed in agribusiness. The correct design of the interaction between independent agricultural holdings requires the construction of relevant structures to which specific rights and responsibilities for the implementation of joint marketing activities will be delegated. The activities themselves are implemented through the management functions - planning, organizing, implementation and control.

Farmers set their management decisions so as to achieve the necessary degree of interaction among themselves and to direct the agricultural holdings towards the achievement of the marketing objectives. Through joint marketing actions, farmers adapt their holdings to market requirements and ensure the effective implementation of marketing activities.

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AGRICULTURE AS THE CARRIER OF THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF KOSOVO

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ABSTRACT

In the past, agricultural production provided practically all the needs of life, not only providing food for the population and carrying out all processes of processing this food to its final forms within agriculture, but also providing housing, clothing, heat, light, etc. The process of economic development meant moving some of the economic functions from agriculture and turning them into specialized industrial branches. Today, agricultural production in developed countries is mainly reduced to the production of raw materials for the food industry. However, as a food producer, agriculture is largely dependent on other sectors, as the products of those sectors enter as a significant component in the costs of agricultural production. The basic role of agriculture in economic development, which consists in ensuring sufficient agricultural yield, agriculture also performs other functions that are also significant. In the initial stages of development, with the expansion of agricultural production, the most important source of means of payment is acquired, which serve for the purchase of modern means of production necessary for development. This function is closely related to the function of producing agricultural output. In the absence of other sources of funds, the agricultural output is not only used to supply food, but a part is exported for the purchase of industrial fixed capital

KEY WORDS: agricultural management, economic development, Kosovo

ABSTRAKT

In der Vergangenheit deckte die landwirtschaftliche Produktion praktisch alle Lebensbedürfnisse ab, indem sie nicht nur die Bevölkerung mit Nahrungsmitteln versorgte und alle Prozesse der Verarbeitung dieser Nahrungsmittel zu ihren endgültigen Formen innerhalb der Landwirtschaft durchführte, sondern auch Wohnungen, Kleidung, Wärme, Licht usw. Der Prozess der wirtschaftlichen Entwicklung bedeutete, dass einige der wirtschaftlichen Funktionen aus der Landwirtschaft in spezialisierte Industriezweige verlagert wurden. Heute ist die landwirtschaftliche Produktion in den Industrieländern hauptsächlich auf die Erzeugung von Rohstoffen für die Lebensmittelindustrie reduziert. Als Nahrungsmittelproduzent ist die Landwirtschaft jedoch in hohem Maße von anderen Sektoren abhängig, da die Erzeugnisse dieser Sektoren einen erheblichen Anteil an den Kosten der landwirtschaftlichen Produktion ausmachen. Neben der grundlegenden Rolle der Landwirtschaft für die wirtschaftliche Entwicklung, die darin besteht, einen ausreichenden landwirtschaftlichen Ertrag zu gewährleisten, erfüllt die Landwirtschaft auch andere wichtige Funktionen. In den Anfangsstadien der Entwicklung wird mit der Ausweitung der landwirtschaftlichen Produktion die wichtigste Quelle für Zahlungsmittel erworben, die für den Kauf der für die Entwicklung notwendigen modernen Produktionsmittel dienen. Diese Funktion ist eng mit der Funktion der Erzeugung landwirtschaftlicher Produkte verbunden. In Ermangelung anderer Geldquellen wird die landwirtschaftliche Produktion nicht nur für die Versorgung mit Nahrungsmitteln verwendet, sondern ein Teil wird für den Kauf von industriellem Anlagekapital exportiert.

STICHWORTE: Agrarmanagement, wirtschaftliche Entwicklung, Kosovo

RÉSUMÉ

Dans le passé, la production agricole répondait pratiquement à tous les besoins de la vie, non seulement en fournissant de la nourriture à la population et en réalisant tous les processus de transformation de cette nourriture en ses formes finales au sein de l'agriculture, mais aussi en fournissant des logements, des vêtements, de la chaleur, de la lumière, etc. Le processus de développement économique a entraîné le transfert de certaines fonctions économiques de l'agriculture vers des branches industrielles spécialisées. Aujourd'hui, la production agricole dans les pays développés se réduit principalement à la production de matières premières pour l'industrie alimentaire. Toutefois, en tant que producteur de denrées alimentaires, l'agriculture est largement dépendante d'autres secteurs, car les produits de ces secteurs entrent pour une part importante dans les coûts de la production agricole. Le rôle fondamental de l'agriculture dans le développement économique, qui consiste à assurer un rendement agricole suffisant, l'agriculture remplit également d'autres fonctions tout aussi importantes. Dans les premiers stades du développement, avec l'expansion de la production agricole, la source la plus importante de moyens de paiement est acquise, qui sert à l'achat des moyens de production modernes nécessaires au développement. Cette fonction est étroitement liée à la fonction de production agricole. En l'absence d'autres sources de financement, la production agricole n'est pas seulement utilisée pour fournir de la nourriture, mais une partie est exportée pour l'achat de capital fixe industriel.

MOTS CLÉS: gestion agricole, développement économique, Kosovo

INTRODUCTION

Theories of economic development emphasize the need to achieve and maintain a balance between industrial and agricultural development. This need is particularly emphasized in theories of balanced development. Adequate development of agriculture reduces production costs in industry, reduces the country's dependence on internal imports, and provides a higher standard of living, which contributes to the general development, social and political stability of the country. The new theoretical literature on economic development, especially after focusing on the problems of the development of countries with little development, emphasizes the importance of agriculture in the process of economic development. While developed countries, in which agriculture is less important, can achieve economic growth, that is, an increase in economic sizes without significant changes in their relations and structures, underdeveloped countries, in order to achieve even modest growth, and must make significant changes in the economic structure. "The relative decline in the share of agricultural production in the total production does not mean, at least in the largest number of countries, an absolute decrease. Agricultural production just grows less than the growth of other sectors of the economy, which leads to its relative decrease. The reason for this lag is the lower speed of growth of the need for agricultural products compared to the growth of agricultural productivity, so that agriculture constantly frees a part of production resources, until then used in agricultural production, for other economic activities. (Ruttan, V., Hayami., Y., 1972) "

In the past, agricultural production provided practically all the needs of life, not only providing food for the population and carrying out all processes of processing this food to its final forms within agriculture, but also providing housing, clothing, heat, light, etc. The process of economic development meant moving some of the economic functions from agriculture and turning them into specialized industrial branches. Today, agricultural production in developed countries is mainly reduced to the production of raw materials for the food industry. However, as a food producer, agriculture is largely dependent on other sectors, as the products of those sectors enter as a significant component in the costs

of agricultural production. The basic role of agriculture in economic development, which consists in ensuring sufficient agricultural yield, agriculture also performs other functions that are also significant. In the initial stages of development, with the expansion of agricultural production, the most important source of means of payment is acquired, which serve for the purchase of modern means of production necessary for development. This function is closely related to the function of producing agricultural output. In the absence of other sources of funds, the agricultural output is not only used to supply food, but a part is exported for the purchase of industrial fixed capital.

The major contribution of agriculture to the economic development of the country consists in providing an abundant source of cheap labor for the development of the non-agricultural sector. The share of agriculture in total employment is still relatively high. The main reasons for the high dependence on agriculture are the reduced employment opportunities and the low investment activity, especially in rural areas. In the initial stages of economic development, the contribution of agriculture to the accumulation of capital for the non-agricultural sector in all countries is distinctly high. Through tax policy, low prices of agricultural products, compulsory purchase, and private savings in agriculture and in many other forms, the necessary funds for accumulation needed for the development of the non-agricultural sector are created. The more agriculture is developed, the more they can serve as a richer source for this accumulation. The special contribution of agriculture to economic development is the production of raw materials for the domestic industrial sector, as well as for export. The place and role of agriculture in economic development depends on the reached level of economic development of the country, on the natural conditions for agricultural production and on the relationship between agricultural resources and the population.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The importance of agriculture for the development of the national economy. Schultz began his acceptance speech for the 1979 Nobel Prize in Economics with the following sentence: "A large part of the world's population is poor, so if we were familiar with the economics of poverty, we would know a large part of the economy that is very significant. A large part of the world's poor earn their living from agriculture, so if we were familiar with the economics of agriculture, we would know much of the economics of poverty". (Dewbre, 2010).

Populations in developing countries are existentially dependent on the agricultural sector, which is usually overridden by those working in other economic sectors. Socially, it is the main population living in rural areas (FAO Food and Agriculture Organization, 2014).

Agricultural growth has long been recognized as an important instrument for poverty reduction. Many studies focus in particular on quantifying the relationship between agriculture and poverty, and this chapter provides an overview of the salient results from them. The agricultural sector plays a strategic role in the process of economic development of the country. Agriculture has contributed far to the economic well-being of advanced countries, and its role in the economic development of less developed countries is vital. In other words, where real income per capita is low, emphasis is placed on agriculture and other primary industries (Dewbre, 2010).

The history of England clearly shows that the Agricultural Revolution preceded the Industrial Revolution. In the United States and Japan, too, the development of agriculture greatly helped in the process of their industrialization. Also, various underdeveloped countries of the world that have participated in the process of economic development have so far learned the limitations of placing too much emphasis on industrialization as a means of achieving higher real income per capita. Therefore,

industrial and agricultural development are not alternatives, but complement and support each other in terms of inputs and outputs.(Adams, RH, 2004). It is evident that increased agricultural production and productivity tend to contribute significantly to the overall economic development of the country, so it is rational and appropriate to put more emphasis on the long-term development of the agricultural sector.

According to Nurks (Charlton and Castillo, 2020) agriculture contributes to economic development in several ways: (1) Provision of food and raw materials for the non-agricultural sectors of the economy, (2) Creation of consumption needs for the products produced in the non-agricultural sectors by the rural population with purchasing power, which earned by selling the market surplus, (3) Providing a surplus that can be invested in the form of savings and taxes for investment in the non-agricultural sector, (4) Earning valuable foreign exchange through the export of agricultural products, (5) Providing employment for a large number of uneducated, dismissed and unskilled workers. Therefore, if we want to start and make a process of economic development on our own, it must start with the agricultural sector. The agricultural sector is the foundation of the economy that provides humanity with the basic necessities of life as well as raw materials for industrialization. That's why countries often consider agriculture a "national security" priority, because these products are necessary for survival, while many products are not so important - therefore the demand for them is often related to the needs of consumers. With the difference in consumer needs for agriculture, agricultural production also differs from land-based production and other biological needs for primary agriculture; demand for low-skilled seasonal labor, especially for fruit and vegetable production; and seasonality. Therefore, the role of agriculture in the development of the economy can be described as follows. (Charlton and Castillo, 2020):

Contribution to national income: Lessons learned from the economic history of many developed countries show that agricultural prosperity has contributed significantly to driving economic progress. It is rightly noted that "today's highly industrialized countries were once predominantly agricultural, while developing economies still have a predominance of agriculture, which contributes significantly to national income."

Source of Food: Agriculture is the basic source of food for all countries in the world - whether they were underdeveloped, developing or even developed. Due to strong population pressure in underdeveloped and developing countries and rapid growth, the demand for food is increasing rapidly. If agriculture fails to meet the growing demand for food, it has been found to negatively affect the growth rate of the economy. Raising the supply of food from the agricultural sector, therefore, has great significance for the economic growth of the country.

Prerequisite for improving the supply of raw materials: Progress in agriculture is necessary to improve the supply of raw materials for agricultural industries, especially in developing countries. The lack of agricultural products affects industrial production and consequently the increase in the general level of prices. For example, flour and rice mills, oil mills, sugar, bread, meat, dairy factories, wineries, jute factories, textile mills and many other industries are based on agricultural products.

Provision of surplus: Advances in the agricultural sector provide surplus to increase the export of agricultural products. In the early stages of development, an increase in export earnings is desirable because of the greater pressure on the foreign exchange situation needed to finance imports of basic capital goods. Johnson and Mellor are of opinion (Johnston and Mellor, 1961): "Given the event's need for increased foreign exchange income and the lack of alternative opportunities, a significant expansion of export manufacturing production is often a rational policy, even though the world supply-demand situation for the product is unfavorable." (Charlton and Castillo, 2020):

Diversion of labor: Initially, agriculture absorbed a large number of labor. In India, about 62% of the workforce is still absorbed in this sector. Agricultural progress enables the diversion of labor from agriculture to the non-agricultural sector. In the initial stages, the diversion of labor from agriculture to the non-agricultural sector is desirable from the point of view of economic development, as it relieves the burden of surplus labor on the limited land. Therefore, the release of surplus labor from the agricultural sector is necessary for the progress of the agricultural sector and for the expansion of the non-agricultural sector.

Infrastructure creation: The development of agriculture requires the construction of roads, market centers, warehouses, rail transport, postal services and many other infrastructure facilities that create the need for industrial products and the development of the commercial sector.

Relief from shortage of capital: The development of the agricultural sector eases the problem of many developed countries facing shortage of foreign capital. For its development, the agricultural sector requires less capital, which reduces the problem of lack of foreign capital.

Benefits for reducing inequality: In a country that is predominantly agricultural and overpopulated, income inequality between rural and urban areas is greater. To reduce this income inequality, it is necessary to give more priority to agriculture. Agricultural prosperity would increase the income of most villagers, so income disparities could be reduced to some extent.

Creation of efficient demand: The development of the agricultural sector tends to increase the purchasing power of the farmers, which helps in the growth of the non-agricultural sector of the country, creating a market for increased production. In underdeveloped countries it is well known that most people depend on agriculture and namely they must be able to afford to buy the produced products.

Aid in the gradual removal of economic depression: Later in a period of depression, industrial production may be stopped or reduced, but agricultural production continues due to the production of basic needs. Therefore, despite the unfavorable conditions of the economy, it still continues to create effective demand.

Source of foreign exchange for the country: Many developing countries in the world are exporters of primary products. These products contribute 60 to 70 percent of the total export revenue. Therefore, the ability to import capital goods and machinery for industrial development depends significantly on the export income of the agricultural sector. If agricultural exports fail to increase at a sufficiently high rate, these countries will be forced into large deficits in the balance of payments, resulting in a serious foreign exchange problem.

Contribution to capital formation: For underdeveloped and developing countries, large capital is required for their economic development. In the early stages of economic development, agriculture is a significant source of capital formation.

Improvement of social status: Agriculture can improve the social status of people in rural areas. By increasing income and improving living conditions, the rural population can progress and receive better education and health services.

Promotion of sustainability: The development of agriculture in accordance with the principles of sustainable development can be promoted simultaneously with the protection of the environment, the use of appropriate farming methods and the sustainable use of natural resources.

Improving the life of the rural population: The development of agriculture can contribute to improving the quality of life of the rural population, including aspects such as health, education, infrastructure and living standards.

Preventing migration: Improved living conditions and agricultural work opportunities in rural areas can prevent people from migrating to urban centers in search of better work and living opportunities.

Fostering innovation: Agriculture can foster innovation in areas such as agronomy, farming technology and production methods, which can have long-term benefits for the economy and society.

Preventing hunger and improving food security: Agricultural development can contribute to reducing hunger and improving food security by increasing food production and access to it, especially in countries where the population is growing the fastest.

The importance of agriculture on the economic development of Kosovo. Agriculture is the basis of the economic development of all European countries, including Kosovo, and is defined as an economic branch that deals with the cultivation of plants and animals for the production of products that primarily satisfy the nutritional needs of the population.

Rural areas in Europe occupy more than 77% of the surface, of which 47% is agricultural land and 30% is forest, and almost half of the population of the European Union lives there. Kosovo has enormous potential to transform its agri-food system into an engine for greater growth, employment and rural incomes. The agri-food sector is a significant contributor to Kosovo's GDP, jobs and rural incomes. The sector benefits from numerous competitive advantages that could be used for increased growth and development, including unrestricted access to EU markets, diverse agro-ecological conditions, quality land and water resources, modern logistics infrastructure, as well as a growing domestic tourism industry. Therefore, Kosovo's agri-food sector is endowed with key resources needed to take advantage of growth opportunities in EU markets and in the domestic sector.

But in order to realize this potential, the structural limitations of competitiveness should be overcome. Kosovo is currently a net importer of agri-food products and faces growing trade imbalances in agriculture. At the same time, climate change poses an increased risk to food supply in agri-food chains. (Franić, Mikuš and Andabak, 2011)

Improvements are needed to increase the competitive position of the agri-food sector. (Franić, Mikuš and Andabak, 2011)

- The productivity of the primary sector, including its modernization and diversification with value addition
- The ability of agri-food chains to effectively respond to the opportunities for growth in the domestic and international market; and
- The ability to manage increased climate risks.

In this context, Kosovo's fragmented production structure represents a major obstacle to building a competitive agri-food sector that functions as an engine for growth, job creation and improved rural incomes.

Sectoral policies aimed at accelerating the structural transformation of the agricultural-food system can increase its competitiveness. The structural transformation of the agricultural-food systems is marked by the industrialization and modernization of agriculture, a significant increase in the labor force and productivity in all sectors, rural-urban migration and a decrease in the share of agriculture in total employment and GDP. (Bustos, Paula, Bruno Caprettini, and Jacopo Ponticelli. 2016.)

From this perspective, Kosovo can still be classified as "incompletely transformed" due to the relatively low levels of productivity of the agri-food system, the high share of GDP and employment that still depend on the primary sector, as well as the divide between rural and urban and the links between poverty and agriculture.

Increasing factor productivity is a key driver for transforming the agri-food system, building competitiveness in downstream food chains and alleviating poverty in rural areas. The structural transformation of agri-food systems follows the path of capitalization of agricultural farms through mechanization, together with improved knowledge of agricultural practices (eg lamb, pesticides, tillage, etc.), leading to significant growth in agricultural production due to higher productivity.

The expansion of agricultural production leads to an increase in the supply of raw materials at lower costs for agricultural processors in the current agri-food chain. This increased supply enables the expansion of operations, encourages horizontal integration and reduces overall costs, which strengthens the competitiveness of the agri-food system as a whole. (Franić, Mikuš and Andabak, 2011)

Moreover, improvements in labor productivity driven by capital investment divert rural workers who then migrate to suburban or urban areas to find employment in non-agricultural sectors. At the same time, increased labor productivity and rural mobility improve livelihoods in rural areas, enabling higher per capita incomes as well as lower poverty densities and poverty rates. (Tolušić, 2001).

Thanks to the primary sectors, i.e. the inputs they provide to other sectors, the growth of the agricultural sector affects the economic activity in the production of food products and beverages, trade, pre-sale and retail trade, hotels and restaurants, research and development, so that the multiplier effects of changes in agricultural production are particularly strong in Kosovo.

Table 1. Key indicators for economic development and contribution of agriculture, forestry and fishing. Source: Kosovo Institute of Statistics

Year	Gross domestic product (in '000)	GDP per capita (€)	GDP (Agriculture, hunting, forestry and fishing / '000 €)	Contribution of agriculture to GDP (%)
2015	5,807,009	3,277	599,608	10.3
2016	6,070,113	3,386	635,044	10.5
2017	6,413,861	3,566	586,136	9.1
2018	6,725,913	3,746	481,997	7.2
2019	7,103,759	3,986	545,221	7.7
2015 - 2020 variation	+22.33%	+21.64%	-9.07%	-25.24%

Kosovo poses substantial challenges in developing a competitive economy and reforming national policies to be closer to those in the European Union (EU). The new phase in the relationship between the EU and Kosovo began with the signing of the Stabilization and Association Agreement in October 2015. This agreement opened a new opportunity for free trade and the application of European standards in

various sectors. Kosovo has made progress in the process of developing national agrarian strategies, grant programs, control mechanisms, farm registers and statistics. Support from the EU through the Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA) 2014-2020 and the TAIEX aid encourages longer development of the agrarian sector and harmonization of national policies. However, the process remains very challenging to achieve all the objectives set by the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The agricultural sector in Kosovo plays a key role in providing opportunities for employment and income generation. According to the GDP survey results, GDP at current prices in 2019 was 7,103.8 million euros. Real growth in 2019, according to 2018, was 4.9%, while GDP per capita for 2019 was 3,986 euros. The contribution of agriculture to GDP decreased from 10.3% in 2015 to 7.2% in 2018, increasing in 2019 to 7.7%, and remaining stable in 2020 at 7.4%. With a 7.4% share of GDP in 2020, the agricultural sector is ranked fourth in the economy. The development of the agrarian sector in Kosovo is particularly important for improving the trade balance, reducing unemployment, increasing food security and environmental protection.

CONCLUSION

The agricultural sector is of key importance for the development and stability of any country. Providing sufficient quality food to the population is essential for their health and well-being, and agriculture is also an important source of raw materials for various industries, including food processing and the textile industry. The development of the agricultural sector has a positive effect on tourism and internal and external trade, which contributes to economic growth. The European Union has recognized the importance of agriculture for a long time and in 1958 introduced a Common Agricultural Policy to support this sector, which still constitutes a significant part of its budget. The Republic of Kosovo, as a candidate for EU membership, actively supports the agricultural sector through state programs that follow the standards of the European Union. The Law on Agriculture and Rural Development, introduced in 2009, regulates the planning and monitoring of agricultural policy, as well as the support of agricultural markets and the forms of organization in this sector. Agriculture is a key part of Kosovo's overall development policy, but it has the potential for greater progress. Application of strategies for agriculture and rural development can contribute to better use of resources and increased competitiveness in this sector.

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